

D1.1 Scoping Report on Non-for-profit Publishing Ecosystems

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Executive summary

This scoping report is designed to achieve two goals. First, it intends to establish *common definitions and terminology* that will be used consistently within the ALMASI project, providing a cohesive analysis and clearly defining what is within and outside the project's scope. In a project that comprises the publishing landscapes of three separate international regions (Africa, Europe, Latin America) it is essential that sufficient common ground and understanding is built before proceeding. Secondly, this report proposes *a mapping component* that leverages existing literature and bibliometric data sources to provide an overview of the current knowledge on Diamond OA publishing activities in these three regions.

The holistic analytical perspective adopted by this report tightly revolves around five foundational concepts: Funding mechanisms, Organisational structures & governance models, Platforms, Solutions and services, and Output types (i. e., journals, articles, books, and preprints). The report collects and summarises the available knowledge for these central concepts in each of the three regions, providing some fundamental insights into similarities and differences in the way in which they are operationalised to support Diamond OA publishing. The initial mapping exercise identified nuances in the availability and depth of documented knowledge across the three regions. Literature and systematic analyses for Europe are more comprehensive, largely due to recent policy-driven projects (such as DIAMAS) that provided detailed systematic overviews of institutional Diamond Open Access publishing, covering governance, funding, and technical solutions. The documentation on scholarly communication for Africa is more localized and less formally systematized, primarily case-based, being dispersed across a wide variety of sources. While documented knowledge in Latin America reflects a long-standing Diamond OA ecosystem supported by university-led, non-commercial infrastructures (e.g., SciELO, Redalyc, Latindex, AmeliCA), available evidence remains centered on institutional development and operational sustainability, distinct from systematic analytical overviews. The current findings inherently reveal a partial view of the broader ecosystem, where documented insights vary in focus and maturity across regions; this divergence illustrates and confirms the need for further exploration and documentation in future research.

The lack of an existing comprehensive registry of Diamond OA journals that are active in the regions necessitated the aggregation of a number of openly available international and national datasets that allowed for collating the most comprehensive representation of Diamond OA journal publishing activity in the regions. As expected, the three regions have various diverging characteristics, and appear to have organised Diamond OA publishing in different ways. In total we were able to identify 20,355 Diamond OA journals across the three regions, with 13,202 being based in Europe, 5,821 in Latin America, and 1,351 in Africa. Among the utilised international bibliometric indexing services OpenAlex contributed with the most comprehensive and unique coverage for Diamond OA journals across all three regions, however, using any of the current international indexing services has limitations and unevenness when considering how comprehensively they include content from the three regions. A common trait among the Diamond OA journals across all the three regions is that research institutions are the most common type of organisation acting in the role of publisher, highlighting the role that universities globally have particularly for this model of publishing.

As one of the first deliverables of the ALMASI project, this report lays the foundations for well-informed continued work that takes into account the different profiles of the three regions, enabling customised inquiries and interventions to take place as the project unfolds.

1. Introduction

The work presented in this deliverable was initiated in conjunction with the start of the ALMASI project in January 2025. This deliverable presents the outcome of a foundational scoping and mapping exercise that will inform the project activities during the following two years. The deliverable establishes key definitions for central concepts of the project and leverages existing data and literature to describe and map the structure of the nonprofit Open Access (OA) publishing ecosystems across three geographic areas: Europe, Africa and Latin America, focusing particularly on nonprofit (Diamond) OA publishing solutions led by scholarly organisations, institutions, or scholars.

An important challenge for establishing stronger communication and collaboration channels within the Diamond OA community internationally as well as for this scoping exercise, is that key information regarding current activities and stakeholders in this space across the three regions still remains sparse and fragmented. The largest global study on Diamond OA journals to date, the OA Diamond Journals Study (OADJS) from 2021, found that Diamond OA journal publishing is a highly distributed archipelago estimated to comprise between 17 000 and 29 000 journals ([Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al., 2021](#)). One of the main recommendations from the OADJS was that there should be greater alignment, coordination, and improvement of the sustainability of Diamond OA journals worldwide. That is exactly what the ALMASI project has set out to contribute to through its phases of exploration, analysis, co-creation, and sustainability enhancement. This scoping report collects the existing pieces of data to establish an initial profiling of Diamond OA in the three world regions. Still, both the project in its next phases and future action outside of it would benefit from further exploration and documentation of publishers and publications not accounted for in the current datasets and overview.

The diversity of the Diamond OA landscape is a treasure that should be nurtured and preserved. At the same time, the lack of systematic overviews poses a challenge for ambitious studies with a wide scope that intend to map and analyze the landscape, as aggregation of diverse data sources often requires some simplification and standardisation of data collection to make summarisation feasible. Acknowledging this dynamic, the ALMASI project involves tasks and outputs that provide both these broad overviews and more in-depth work that focuses on individual countries or key dimensions of Diamond OA publishing. This deliverable primarily contributes to the overview-type of outputs, establishing common terms and definitions that will be used throughout the project, and it provides an initial exploratory mapping of nonprofit Diamond OA publishing solutions in the three regions. This mapping has been conducted by building upon bibliometric information as well as aggregating the outputs from projects conducted within this topic area around the world. This task aimed to enhance the understanding of the disciplinary, linguistic, and geographical distribution of nonprofit OA publishing solutions, types of organisational models, as well as quality assurance tools and services provided, with special attention for sustainability in terms of

finances, policy, and governance. A central focus has been placed on identifying the key platforms and service providers in the regions, and considering what role these play in serving the local Diamond OA publishing communities.

The deliverable is structured as follows. Section 2 covers definitions and scope, establishing the central terms and boundaries for both the deliverable as well as for the project. Section 3 focuses on mapping, divided into three sub-sections corresponding to the three major world regions included in the project's scope, where existing information on platforms, output types, organisational structures & governance models, funding mechanisms, and solutions and services are summarised for each region. Section 4 presents the results of bibliometric mapping of Diamond OA journals in each of the three regions, based on a broad aggregation of open bibliometric data. The deliverable concludes with a summary section highlighting the main takeaways from the preceding sections.

In addition to this written document, this work also provides the collected bibliometric information as open data, made available through Zenodo (Taskin & Laakso 2025).

2. Scoping and definitions

This section provides the foundational definitions and descriptions of central concepts and their interrelationships used within the ALMASI project.

The DIAMAS project produced a scoping report in 2023 which established definitions and a foundational typology for the work to be conducted within the tasks and work packages of the project ([Bargheer, Bosman, Drahomira, et al., 2023](#)). As a starting point for the scoping work in ALMASI, we consulted the outputs of DIAMAS to avoid redundant effort and ensure cross-project continuity and alignment. However, the DIAMAS project was geographically much narrower in scope, and also had a conceptual anchoring in institutional publishers and service providers, which differs from the starting scope and perspective of ALMASI, which is geographically broader and is not exclusively centered around institutional publishers in the publishing landscape. As such, existing definitions have only been reused after careful consideration, discussion, and consultation with the ALMASI project consortium's members regarding their suitability and applicability in this specific project context.

Glossary: working definitions of terminology used in ALMASI

In this section, we present two categories of definitions and terminology to be used in the ALMASI project. 'General terms' is a list of widely used terms for which we provide a project-level definition to increase the clarity of their use, and 'Core concepts of the project' contains a hierarchically structured list of definitions and associated core concepts that represent how they interrelate with each other and are operationalised in the project.

General terms

Publishing = The set of activities that lead to making content available to the public first, only, or in its earliest form after some form of editorial treatment. Disseminating preprints via repositories is publishing.

Journal = An individual periodically published publication series containing peer-reviewed research articles and other materials.

Publisher = The instance responsible for publishing the journal, often an organisation, but can also be an individual, the Editorial Board, or some other entity. Information about the journal's publisher is included as part of ISSN registration data and forms part of the core data of most bibliometric databases.

Diamond Open Access (Diamond OA) = 'Diamond Open Access (OA)' refers to an equitable model of scholarly publication that charges no fees to authors or readers and in which the content-related elements of publication are owned and controlled by scholarly communities.

Nonprofit publishing = Publishing activities that make available original scholarly outputs whose quality, editorial procedures, and content are controlled by (members of) an Institution without the aim to generate a profit and without fees for readers or authors. (This excludes the hosting of content in repositories, educational materials, and archiving).

Institution = In the context of this project, an institution is defined as a not-for-profit academic or scholarly organisation. These include, but are not limited to, Research Performing organisations (RPOs), Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), organisations connected to RPOs (university libraries, university presses, faculties, departments, and labs), research institutes, scholarly societies, etc.

Institutional publishing = Academic publishing by an institution, unit, or person that is part of an institution.

Institutional repository = An online archive for collecting, preserving, and disseminating the intellectual output of an institution, particularly a research institution.

Subject repository = An online archive containing works or data of scholars in a particular subject area.

Funders, Sponsors, and Donors (FSDs) = Those organisations that offer financial or in-kind support to Diamond OA publishers. FSDs may be universities (including libraries), research institutions, associations, societies, academies, and regional, national, or international funding agencies, including governmental, charitable, and private organisations.

Editor-in-Chief/Executive Editor = Representative of a scholarly journal who has been entrusted by its ownership governance bodies and/or journal community to head the Editorial Team and Board, and who has final responsibility for production and publication of the journal.

Editorial Team = The group of (Associate) Editors, including the Editor-in-Chief / Executive Editor, that is jointly responsible for handling, selecting, and preparing materials for publication and for mediating communication between authors and reviewers of scholarly papers. Sometimes the Editorial Board carries out the functions of the Editorial Team.

Journal/platform community = the community of editors, editorial board members, governance bodies, authors, reviewers, and readers who are involved in a scholarly journal, publishing platform, or preprint server, and who informally recognize each other as members of that community, sharing scholarly norms and values.

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB) = A conceptual framework to support the fair treatment and full participation of all people, especially in the workplace, including populations who have historically been under-represented or subject to discrimination because of their background, identity, disability, etc.

Publication/ output (type) = journals, books, or preprints.

Core concepts of the project

The previous sub-section introduced and defined general terms. In this section we provide definitions for core concepts of the project as they apply to the Diamond OA context specifically.

Platforms

Publishing platforms are a key concept within the ALMASI project, as there is increasing evidence and experience from around the world that successful Diamond OA publishing at scale often builds upon some level of centralisation of technical facilities that serve national, disciplinary, geographical regions, or other types of scholarly publishing communities.

Publishing platform = A technical facility where (versions of) content are published, hosting online publications and their metadata and facilitating some editorial processes.

- Publishing platforms can be very large or very small, disciplinary and multidisciplinary, and host any kind of (scholarly) publication.
- Publishing platforms can be managed/provided by a publisher itself or by an external service provider.

Commonly used platforms rely on running open source software such as Open Journal Systems, Janeway, or Lodel.

Although some web hosting platforms might make use of software like WordPress, they are not considered publishing platforms as they do not afford the complex set of publishing services that dedicated platforms provide.

There are also different types of repositories (institutional, subject-oriented) that can be used for the distribution of publications (e.g. preprints or self-archived manuscripts), but since their intended and de facto use case is not for making primary peer-reviewed publications available, this project does not include them in the definition of a 'publishing platform'.

Journal portals = In some regional contexts the distinction is further made between platforms that only aggregate and index content published elsewhere on the web, and platforms where the publisher themselves publish their content directly on the platform as their primary way of distributing the content. In the case of the latter the term journal portals is used e.g. in the Latin American context.

Output types and publications

Scholarly communication and publishing take many forms, where different media are used to communicate both ongoing and finished research outputs to various audiences. There is considerable variation in how different disciplines and regions of the world have adopted various formats for scholarly publishing. For this project, the main focus is on peer-reviewed scholarly journals, which, within most disciplines, is the main way to disseminate new research. However, in this project we are also gathering supporting data to understand how closely related research outputs, namely open access books and preprints for scholarly journal article manuscripts, fare in the three regions. For all of these output types, the project is focused on investigating how they function as part of a Diamond OA publishing landscape.

Organisational structures & governance models

In order to understand how Diamond OA publishing organisations in the three regions are anchored to sustain publishing into the future, the ALMASI project places particular focus on organisational structures and governance. Gaining clarity on how Diamond OA publishing is governed is important for developing a deeper understanding of how publication outlets and underlying organisations operate now as well as how they are positioned to deal with future internal and external changes.

A key element in this context relates to *ownership* - both concerning the ownership background of the publishing organisation, as well as ownership of individual titles that are being published. Both of these aspects are covered within the scope of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS,) developed within the DIAMAS project, which includes a section with four requirements regarding ownership for a journal to be compliant with the standard ([Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2025](#): 18-19). While the ALMASI project will not map alignment with all these individual requirements, we will use these perspectives to frame different types of enquiries and interpretation throughout the project:

1. "The publisher of the journal must be owned by a public or not-for-profit organisation (or parts thereof) whose mission includes performing or promoting research and scholarship."
2. "The publisher has a defined statement about the ownership of the individual journals it publishes. It includes the legal parameters governing the relationship between the publisher and its published journal/s, the determination of ownership for each title, and the explicit definition of the rights/duties afforded to editors within the publisher in a precise and unambiguous articulation. This also includes details about the discontinuation of the individual journal, and the transfer and preservation of its assets."
3. "Changes in the ownership, relationships and rights/duties must be handled with care and transparently by publishers. A change in the service provider (for example, publishing infrastructure) can be achieved without changing the journal title, owner, or publisher."
4. "The publisher offers information about its ownership structure on its website."

In addition, DOAS includes a section on governance with four requirements that will be used for similar purposes, drawing on them as needed within the work packages of the project to frame and interpret aspects related to governance (Consortium of the DIAMAS project 2025: 19-20):

1. "All journals published by the publisher ensure that their mission statement, aims, or scope are easily accessible on their website, with a clear structure and content."
2. "The publisher makes sure that all its journals have procedures for the selection of members of editorial bodies that should include details of their mandate's length, the regular renewal process, and clearly defined procedures for the dissolution of the board. This information is displayed on each journal's website."
3. "The publisher makes sure that relationships among co-publishers are defined by a formal agreement. It is also clearly indicated that the publication is a co-publication on the publisher website."
4. "All journals of the publisher must have a clear definition of the roles and responsibilities of the publisher, editorial bodies, owners and publishers towards authors, reviewers, readers and the scholarly community, journal and platform owners, publisher, and the public. Roles and responsibilities related to the peer review process are described in detail on the publisher's website, and crucial aspects of the peer review process must not be left to publication technicians or AI."

Funding mechanisms

Funding mechanism = A source of financial support that enables Diamond OA publishing. Funding mechanisms can operate at the level of an individual journal or at a wider scale (e.g., national or regional programmes and infrastructures).

DOAS also includes a section on Funding, which we are using as scoping definitions for the ALMASI project:

- **Diamond OA model**

Journals are required to have no paywalls for either authors or readers, and provide this information transparently on their webpages, as well as whether there are any other types of fees involved such as Voluntary Author Contributions.

- **Sustainability**

Financial support. “The publisher is directly or indirectly funded by public funds or other revenue streams to enable free access to the author and reader, ideally covering all costs. (REQUIRED)”

Costs. “Costs are identified year-on-year. Publishers are able to plan their annual costs and to balance them with expected incomes and in-kind contributions using a tracking system, such as a budget. (DESIRED)”

Sustainability plan. “The publisher considers the medium-term economic viability of its Diamond OA model. It has a clear overview of available funding sources and other relevant external and internal (in-kind) resources, aligned with set expectations of future maintenance and developmental costs. In achieving its goals, a publisher preferably deploys collaborative strategies and uses common open infrastructures, to cut costs and raise efficiency. (DESIRED)”

- **Editorial Independence**

Editorial operations related to content and peer review are required to be completely detached from influence of any bodies that are providing funding to the publisher. A desired practice is that the origin of the revenue streams are openly disclosed by the author/s and by the publishing entity, in line with the values, expectations, and traditions in the disciplines that the publisher is serving, and do not have an impact on editorial independence. Any conflicts of interests between revenue streams and authors, reviewers, or editors should be clearly indicated.

Solutions and services

In ALMASI, we will work to map solutions and services through the following key considerations

- The platforms various publication types (i.e. journals, books, preprints) are provided through (if any)
- Do publishers rely on shared publishing services?
- How many journals/books/preprint servers does the publishing service provider maintain?
- Are the publishing services provided externally or by the parent organisation of the publishing service provider itself?
- Are the publishing service providers institutional, national, or regional?

By gathering evidence on these factors throughout the project, we will be able to provide insight into the (de)centralisation of the landscape in different regions and the editorial burden of running the publications. Good support in the following areas can mitigate fatigue and low quality output.

Technical	=	IT platform, PIDs & metadata
Production	=	Typesetting, production
Editorial	=	Journal guidelines/policies

Solutions

Specific ways in which publishers establish or access and combine services to support their publishing operations. A solution encompasses:

- A set of services required to support technical, production, and editorial functions (e.g. hosting, PID registration, peer review management, typesetting, etc.).
- Service provision models, i.e. how these services are delivered – internally by the parent organisation, externally by dedicated service providers (e.g. non-profit or for-profit providers, national platforms, etc.), or through hybrid arrangements (services are partly provided internally and partly through external service providers).
- Service usage models shaped by the structural environment in which services are embedded, e.g. whether an institution applies a uniform set of services and provision models across all its publications, whether journals selectively use only certain functionalities of available services, or whether different units (journals) within the same institution adopt distinct approaches based on their needs and capacities.

These solutions may vary significantly across regions and institutions, as well as among journals that use the same platform or software.

Services

Activities, tools, infrastructures, and forms of support that enable publishers to carry out and sustain the full publishing process. Services may be delivered through software platforms, human expertise, workflows, or organisational infrastructure.¹

Service provider = an organisation, unit, or person performing any subset of the activities and services that are related to the publishing process. Such activities include, but are not limited to, a) Editorial activities (selection of manuscripts, peer-review, etc.); b) Operational activities (with production activities like copy editing, proofreading, type-setting, creating metadata but also IT activities and communication activities (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc) as well as administrative and financial activities (contracts, accounting, documentation, etc.). A service provider can be commercial or non-commercial, and institutional or non-institutional.

The sustainability of Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing depends on the availability, reliability, and configuration of services – i.e. the activities, tools, and infrastructure that support the entire publishing process. In practice, services are combined, acquired, used, and managed in different ways, depending on factors such as available, financial, technical and human resources, institutional capacity, local skills, and cultural context. These specific arrangements can be understood as different service solutions. Even journals using the same software or hosted on the same platform may implement distinct service combinations and workflows, depending on their unique contexts, resources and strategic priorities. Also, they may not use particular service features, though they have access to them, for various reasons (e.g. a lack of human resources or skills).

Four main service types will be explored:

- **Technical services** associated with the infrastructure for digital publishing and dissemination ensuring discoverability, interoperability, and long-term access:
 - Software platforms (e.g. OJS, Janeway, Lodel, repositories)
 - Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs, ORCID, ROR)
 - Indexing support (metadata creation, management, and dissemination)
 - Preservation

While open-source platforms like OJS are widely adopted, implementation models differ. A platform may be self-hosted by an institution, externally hosted by a service provider, or managed through hybrid models. A platform can host one, several or many journals. Third-party plugins can be used to enrich functionalities and customize workflows. Amendments to the core code of OJS may be key in allowing large infrastructures to function as platforms. Finally, different systems can be used for different parts of the publishing workflow.

¹ [Brun, Pontille & Torny, 2024](#) present a list of services that are also used in the registration form for Diamond OA publishers in the EDCH Registry.

- **Editorial services** that focus on peer review, ethical publishing, and quality assurance, including:
 - Workflow management tools for peer review and editorial decision-making
 - Communication tools for editorial board coordination
 - Capacity-building initiatives for editors and reviewers
 - Support for editorial policies, ethics, and compliance

- **Production services** that transform accepted manuscripts into final, publishable content, including:
 - Typesetting and layout design
 - File conversion (PDF, HTML, XML, EPUB)
 - Multilingual production workflows
 - Accessibility compliance (e.g. WCAG standards)

Production services may be provided internally, outsourced to commercial or nonprofit providers, or coordinated through regional consortia or freelance networks. This information has high practical value but is often unavailable or incomplete.

Geographical scope

The ALMASI project will map the Diamond OA landscape in three world regions: Africa, Latin America, and Europe. In order to do that successfully, these large regions can be usefully subdivided into subregions. Initiatives and services that span more than one region should also be included. We know from existing information that across the countries within these regions, we have a large diversity in almost all attributes and activities, both within and outside the specific area of academic publishing.

In this document we propose a pragmatic minimal subdivision of regions and choices of countries within the scope of the project. This provides a good basis for discussion going forward, as well as a common understanding of the arguments that underpin the rationale for selecting these subregions over others.

Table 1 divides Africa and Latin America into four subregions. Europe is defined as the ERA, but for closer studies, we are focused on country level studies. The DIAMAS results indicated that a regional approach was not fruitful for scoping Diamond OA in Europe. In addition, we include three languages that span the three regions. French is used as a publishing language in both Europe and Africa, and Portuguese is used across the three world regions. Spanish is used in Spain and Latin America.

	Africa	Europe	Latin America
Subregion	Central and West Africa	ERA: Consideration for all ERA countries in general overviews where data is available. Closer analysis in the project for 10 specific countries identified in the DIAMAS project (Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Spain, The United Kingdom)+ 5 additional countries (Estonia, Ireland, Portugal, Serbia, Switzerland)	North Latin America (Mexico)
Subregion	East Africa		Central Latin America
Subregion	North Africa		The Caribbean
Subregion	Southern Africa		South Latin America
Language	Francophone Diamond OA initiatives		
Language	Lusophone Diamond OA initiatives		
Language	Multi-language Diamond support	Hispanophone Diamond OA initiatives	

Table 1 – A pragmatic division into subregions, countries, and languages

It is important to emphasise that these choices are pragmatic and a function of the available resources in the project. By using the term ‘francophone’ or ‘lusophone’, we only want to indicate that these languages are widely used as *lingua franca* in the relevant regions, independently of their official status, and we acknowledge the importance local languages play in these countries and regions.

Africa

There are two distinct yet interconnected regions in Africa: North Africa (sometimes referred to as Northern Africa, a region encompassing the northern portion of the African continent) and Sub-Saharan Africa (the area and regions that lie south of the Sahara). Sub-Saharan Africa includes four subregions: Central Africa, East Africa, Southern Africa and West Africa.

Central Africa, East Africa, North Africa, Southern Africa and West Africa are the five geographical subregions of the member states of the African Union.

In the ALMASI project we will combine Central and West Africa into one project subregion, following the approach of African regional organizations with which we plan to collaborate. ALMASI project activities will be targeting four African geopolitical subregions:

Central and West Africa: This subregion includes the Economic Community of Central African States and the Economic Community of West African States. In this subregion, members of the ALMASI project will collaborate with the West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)² that provides Diamond OA infrastructure and services for the West and Central African Research and Education community and manages African Diamond OA publishing Community of Practice that includes over 380 journal editors and publishers from all over Africa.

East Africa: This subregion comprises the countries that are members of the East African Community (EAC), an intergovernmental organisation that included open science principles in the regional Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (STI), launched in 2024. In this subregion we will collaborate with the East African Science and Technology Commission (EASTECO)³ and Inter-University Council of East Africa (IUCEA),⁴ the leading EAC institution that strengthens the common higher education area and develops mutually beneficial collaborations between member Universities and governments. EASTECO was instrumental in adopting EAC STI open science policy provisions and many IUCEA members publish Diamond OA journals.

North Africa: This subregion is grouped with the definition of Middle East and North Africa (MENA) as it is part of the Arab world, and most North African states are members of the Arab League. In this subregion we will collaborate with the Association of Arab Universities,⁵ Federation of Arab Scientific Research Councils⁶ and Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)⁷. Some North African countries - Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia are also a part of the European Research Area (ERA). National publishing platforms that host hundreds of Diamond OA journals is a distinct feature of this sub-region and an overview of Algerian Scientific Journals Platform (ASJP)⁸ and Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal (PRSM)⁹ are provided in the Platforms section below.

Southern Africa: This subregion includes the countries that are members of the intergovernmental Southern African Development Community (SADC) that also demonstrated commitment to mainstream open science. In this subregion we will collaborate with the Southern African Regional Universities Association¹⁰ - a membership-based association of public and private universities in the SADC building human capacity to advance Diamond OA publishing and UbuntuNet Alliance for Research and Education Networking¹¹ - the alliance of Eastern and South African National Research

² <https://wacren.net/>

³ <https://easteco.org/>

⁴ <https://www.iucea.org/>

⁵ <https://www.aaru.edu.jo/>

⁶ <https://fasrc.org/>

⁷ <https://www.asren.net/>

⁸ <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/>

⁹ <https://revues.imist.ma/>

¹⁰ <https://sarua.africa/>

¹¹ <https://ubuntunet.net/>

and Education Networks offering Diamond OA publishing infrastructure. UbuntuNet Alliance will also be our partner in the East African subregion.

Francophone and Lusophone Africa are two other linguistic subregions that we will target in the ALMASI project activities. As mentioned above, the project unfortunately lacks the capacity to have targeted communications in other languages spoken in Africa.

Francophone Africa: ALMASI project members will collaborate with the African and Malagasy Council for Higher Education (CAMES)¹² coordinating higher education and research systems in francophone Africa and CRUFOACI (Conférence des recteurs des universités francophones d'Afrique et de l'océan Indien)¹³. This sub-region doesn't have many Diamond OA journals yet and flipping from print to Diamond OA and from Article Processing Charges to Diamond OA will be a focus for ALMASI work leveraging WACREN shared Diamond OA publishing infrastructure and Francophone Diamond OA publishing Community of Practice that includes over 40 Diamond OA journal managers and publishers.

Lusophone Africa: This subregion includes the members of the Community of Portuguese Language Countries (CPLP). CPLP countries collaborate on the shared repository and organize the annual Lusophone Open Science Conference.

Members of the ALMASI project will collaborate with African organizations that operate across different subregions and disciplinary networks, e.g. African Academy of Sciences,¹⁴ Association of African Universities,¹⁵ African Research Universities Alliance,¹⁶ Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa,¹⁷ Network of African Science Academies,¹⁸ Regional Universities Forum for Capacity Building in Agriculture,¹⁹ Science for Africa Foundation²⁰ and Science Granting Councils Initiative²¹. The last on this list may well be worth additional outreach and advocacy efforts by the ALMASI project as a global community of endorsement, as these African countries' Governments are actively working towards our domestic, African government-funded efforts towards relevant research advancement and relevant research communications sustainable support channels.

Many members of these organizations publish Diamond OA journals and support Diamond OA publishing with policies and funding.

¹² <https://www.lecames.org/>

¹³ <https://www.crufaoci.org/>

¹⁴ <https://aasciences.africa/>

¹⁵ <https://aau.org/>

¹⁶ <https://arua.org/>

¹⁷ <https://codesria.org/>

¹⁸ <https://nasaconline.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.ruforum.org/>

²⁰ <https://scienceforafrica.foundation/>

²¹ <https://sgciafrica.org/>

Europe

Europe represents a diverse environment for nonprofit and Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing, with differences across countries in terms of governance models, policy coordination, and funding mechanisms, among other variables.

For closer analysis, the ALMASI project consortium has selected 15 countries among the EU Member States of the European Research Area (ERA) and observer and associated ERA countries such as the United Kingdom. In the DIAMAS project this geographic area was divided into four broad subregions, as described in *Institutional Publishing in the ERA: Results from the DIAMAS survey* ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. 2023](#)) in the following way:

Northern Europe: Northern Europe plays an important role in ERA and is represented in the analysis by Finland, Norway, Estonia, and Ireland. It is an area that is well known for its strong public research systems and advanced digital infrastructures. This subregion represents a mature nonprofit OA model.

Western Europe: This area is the central region of the ERA. Countries of Western Europe have high research capacity and close connections. In ALMASI it will be represented by France, Germany, the Netherlands, and Switzerland.

Southern Europe: This diverse and active area within ERA brings together the Mediterranean and Balkan research communities. It is an area that is well known for its active participation in European projects. Italy, Portugal, Spain, Croatia, and Serbia represent this subregion in the ALMASI project, showing that nonprofit OA publishing can work in multilingual contexts.

Eastern Europe: Poland represents Eastern Europe in the project, acting as a bridge between the Central and Western ERA regions.

The European region could be considered as a set of subregions, as described above, but for the sake of this evaluation, and for the presentation of the results, Europe will be treated as a single corpus, providing an overall view of institutional nonprofit Open Access publishing across the continent rather than reporting results separately by subregion. This is also because the DIAMAS project found that the regional subdivision of Europe was not a useful one to discern trends in institutional nonprofit Open Access publishing.

The situation for institutional nonprofit Open Access publishing varies considerably in each of these countries. Countries such as Croatia, Finland, Spain, Portugal, and France have established National Capacity Centres (NCCs) that provide coordinating services to Diamond OA journals. In other countries, such support structures for nonprofit publishing services and Diamond OA have not yet been established.

The geographical approach described reflects both the diversity of national research systems and the variety of institutional models that characterise nonprofit and Diamond OA publishing across the continent.

Within this broader framework, ALMASI is creating a detailed landscape of fifteen selected countries that together capture different linguistic, cultural, and organisational contexts of Europe, representing a cross-section of the ERA where Diamond OA practices range from highly coordinated, nationally supported ecosystems – such as those of Croatia, France, Finland, Portugal, or Spain – to more institutionally driven or emerging frameworks, as found in countries like Serbia or Switzerland.

Building upon the findings of the DIAMAS project, particularly the *National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe* ([Taşkın, Melinščak Zlodi, Laakso, et al 2024](#)), ALMASI is exploring governance models, funding mechanisms, and professionalisation strategies that reinforce institutional nonprofit OA publishing services. The project will also assess the implementation and alignment of these practices with *The Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)* ([Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2025](#)) developed within the DIAMAS project.

At the European level, ALMASI will take into account the roles of key institutions supporting OA and institutional publishing, including Science Europe, SPARC Europe, cOAlition S, OpenAire, and the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH). These entities provide guidance, coordination, and funding that collectively sustain Europe in its leadership on equitable and community-driven scholarly communication.

Latin America and the Caribbean

For ALMASI and in order to understand the prevailing nonprofit publishing model in Latin America, a functional regional subdivision for the entire region is suggested.

Latin America and the Caribbean represent a cultural division, not a strictly geographical one. The shared cultural identity that unites the region is reflected in a tradition of scholarly communications that spans several decades, and that has resulted in the development of an ecosystem that serves epistemic communities rather than countries or geographical regions.

Therefore, the Latin American and Caribbean region will be addressed through four subregions. This division aligns closely with the Standard Country or Area Codes for Statistical Use (M49) of the United Nations ([United Nations. Statistical Office, 1999](#)).

- Latin America: North
- Latin America: Central
- Caribbean
- Latin America: South

1. Latin America: North

Countries: Mexico.

Regarding Diamond Open Access publishing it is very important to analyze Mexico separately for three major reasons: it is the largest Spanish-speaking country; the National Autonomous University of Mexico is the largest Diamond OA publisher of the Spanish-speaking countries in Latin America; and two of the major publishing initiatives of the region, Latindex and Redalyc, are based in Mexico.

2. Latin America: Central

Central America is usually defined as comprising seven countries: Belize, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Nicaragua, and Panama.

Central America has developed a cohesive community of Diamond OA publishing institutions. These countries also share regional policies for Open Access and Open Science, and share cross-country mechanisms and structural organizations that facilitate collaboration among institutions such as CSUCA (the Higher University Council of Central America).

3. Latin America: Caribbean

Anguilla, Antigua and Barbuda, Aruba, Bahamas, Barbados, Bonaire,, Sint Eustatius, Saba, British Virgin Islands, Cayman Islands, Cuba, Curaçao, Dominica, Dominican Republic, Grenada, Guadeloupe, Haiti, Jamaica, Martinique, Montserrat, Puerto Rico, Saint Barthélemy, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Saint Lucia, Saint Martin (French part), Saint Vincent and the Grenadines, Sint Maarten (Dutch part), Trinidad and Tobago, Turks and Caicos Islands, United States Virgin Islands

In terms of Diamond OA journal publishing, Cuba is one of the strongest countries in this subregion within scope of the ALMASI project. Diamond OA publishing also receives strong support from the government.

4. Latin America: South America

Argentina, Bolivia, Bouvet Island, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Falkland Islands, French Guiana, Guyana, Paraguay, Peru, South Georgia and the South Sandwich Islands, Suriname, Uruguay, Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of).

Language-based Diamond OA initiatives

Examples of Francophone initiatives

In France, a number of platforms publish or disseminate Diamond OA journals. These also host

journals from other French-speaking or other countries. They include OpenEdition,²² a platform that services 656 journals, of which 583 are OA and no-fee, Centre Mersenne,²³ and the overlay journals of Episciences²⁴. There are also institutional platforms such as Numerev,²⁵ Open-U Bordeaux,²⁶ and Prairial (Lyon Saint-Etienne),²⁷ in addition to a journals incubator (17 journals)²⁸.

An important article describing the French landscape is Ancion, Lutz, Mounier et al (2023). Many nonprofit academic publishers in France publish Diamond OA books without explicitly mentioning it. For example, IRD éditions has adopted a Diamond OA policy for its books and works extensively in collaboration with publishers in Africa and South America. These publishers are therefore encouraged by this collaboration to adopt the Diamond OA publication model. There are a lot of Universities publishing journals in the diamond model without labelling them “diamond”.

In Africa, some journals from francophone speaking countries are hosted or referenced in AJOL. Not all African-published journals partners of AJOL are Diamond OA, and those that are Diamond OA and have French as their only or primary publishing language are underrepresented on AJOL compared to journals from African countries that have English as one of their named official languages. AJOL has explicitly planned to recruit (for the first time in 25 years) applications for journal inclusion assessment from both African Diamond and African Francophone journals for potential inclusion to the platform from 2026 onwards, which has been made feasible by increased support to this Pan-African nonprofit, increasingly gaining traction and acknowledgment after 25 years of work for the continent in this sector.

Some publishers such as the Presse Universitaire de Dakar in Senegal have shown interest in the Diamond model. For example, there is the Senegalese Diamond OA journal²⁹ and there are also Diamond OA journals in Togo. In 2023, the Université Gaston Berger de Saint-Louis (UGB) in Senegal launched Global Africa, a multilingual panafrican Diamond OA journal.³⁰

Many scholarly journals in Africa do not disclose their business models or charge very low APCs. A shift towards a Diamond OA model, supported by a programme to strengthen scientific quality according to DOAS criteria, seems feasible.

The French-speaking scientific community is a dynamic area of collaboration, offering international collaborations and support within the French-speaking world. In Quebec the CIRCE network³¹ has a strong policy on Diamond OA journals. The Canadian publishing platform Erudit³² is

²² <https://www.openedition.org/>

²³ <https://www.centre-mersenne.org/>

²⁴ <https://www.episciences.org/>

²⁵ <https://www.numerev.com/>

²⁶ <https://open.u-bordeaux.fr/>

²⁷ <https://www.publications-prairial.fr/>

²⁸ <https://reseau-reperes.fr/>

²⁹ <https://raspa.episciences.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.globalafricasciences.org/fr>

³¹ <https://reseaucirce.org/>

³² <https://apropos.erudit.org/?lang=en>

the leading digital dissemination platform of SSH research in Canada, hosting 240 Diamond OA journals. In Switzerland there is a National Fund for Open Access journals but not dedicated specifically to French-language journals. In Belgium, Reliade³³ is the network for Diamond OA journals, bringing together journals, libraries and university presses. And there is Shared Open Access Publishing Platform created by several university libraries³⁴.

AUF (Agence française pour la francophonie) is also a relevant player: AIFS is the International Academy of Francophone Science³⁵ with a publishing center Pôle 2 - Publication and promotion of research and scientific publishing, but they have no special provisions for Diamond OA publishing.

Examples of Lusophone initiatives

In Portugal, most Open Science initiatives are related to Open Access, primarily through repositories. The Portuguese funding agency FCT (Foundation for Science and Technology) manages the scientific repository of CPLP (Portuguese Speaking Countries) and has collaborated with Brazil since 2009 on several initiatives, including the Lusophone Open Science Conference. More information is available here on the website of Electronic System for Journal Publishing (SEER).³⁶

SciELO³⁷ is the major service provider for electronic journals and includes a large number of lusophone Diamond OA journals. Miguilim³⁸ is a directory of electronic journals in Brazil that contains over 1300 diamond OA titles.³⁹

Core project concepts and their relationships

To summarise the core definitions and concepts for the project, a visualisation of key relationships between them is provided in Figure 1. As represented in the figure, the entire project scope is contained within the outlines of the *geographical scope* and its definition within this chapter. We consider different types of publishers of diamond OA, placing focus on *organisational structures and governance models*, acknowledging the existence and involvement of parent organisations, and the need for methods and interpretations to account for the high number of very small publishers. Published outputs from publishers are made available through various combinations of solutions and services, encompassing technical, production, editorial, and funding aspects. We distinguish between publishing that occurs on shared platforms or elsewhere, e.g. the publisher's own webpages, if that is not the case. For example, a university may

³³ <https://reliade.be/>

³⁴ <https://www.soap2.ch/>

³⁵ <https://aifs.auf.org/>

³⁶

<http://sitehistorico.ibict.br/pesquisa-desenvolvimento-tecnologico-e-inovacao/sistema-eletronico-de-editoracao-de-revistas-seer>

³⁷ <https://www.scielo.org/en/>

³⁸ <http://www.miguilim.ibict.br>

³⁹

https://miguilim.ibict.br/simple-search?query=&sort_by=dc.date.accessioned_dt&order=desc&rpp=10&etal=0&filtername=publicationfees&filterquery=A+revista+não+cobra+qualquer+taxa+de+publicação&filtertype>equals

have different departments which publish and host their journals on different platforms. In this figure, Journal 3 is an example of a journal that is not hosted on a platform but on, e.g. a Wordpress site.

Figure 1 - Connections between core concepts of the publishing environments

3. Mapping

Africa

Africa is a massive continent comprising 56 countries, depending on the political definition of a country. There exist wide cultural, language, economic and geographical differences both between and within African countries. The continent includes the largest number and concentration of Least Developed Countries in the world, so many countries are characterised by resource scarcity and low GDPs. That said, some African countries' governments have committed contributions of nearly 1.5% of GDP to higher education, and a handful have or are developing policies and mechanisms to support the dissemination of research outputs conducted within their countries.

It is extremely difficult to provide a comprehensive summary of scholarly publishing and Diamond OA for an entire continent that is far more varied than the other two regions involved in this project, so some generalisations are in order. There are very few commercial, or nonprofit professional scholarly publishers working from Africa (as distinct from in Europe and Latin America). South Africa, in particular, is an outlier on the continent regarding state policy and funding of scholarly publishing structures, as well as the professionalisation and formalisation of many journals published in that country.

Estimates of the number of journals being published on the African continent vary widely. Many, if not most journals are stand-alone scholar-led journals, with few or no paid staff, run primarily through the volunteer efforts of their founding (or first intake of new) Editorial Board members made up of institutional faculty and subject-specific experts. These journals may or may not have a formal relationship with the institution/s listed by them as their “publisher” or owner-entity of the journals. In many instances, universities on the continent unknowingly provide in-kind support for the functioning of these journals. In other instances, journals are able to obtain allocations for supporting their costs through formal internal institutional budget arrangements.

Financial publication models to support cost-recovery of African research publications have tended to follow time-lagged international publication trends. Open Access was fairly quickly adopted as a publication model by many older journals on the continent as their Editorial Board members became aware of the broader concept as experienced through their own research and publication efforts as individuals. Often, the shift from a subscription-based model to an Open Access model was fairly easy, as subscription incomes were largely very low, and based on printed copies. Familiarity with licensing types for Open Access is often only gained through the process of scholar-led journals applying for inclusion to AJOL, or to DOAJ. During recent preparation efforts in the second half of 2025 to implement a country-wide in-person journal training workshop in Tanzania (which sadly had to be postponed due to national violence in protest of non-democratic election procedures), it was noted that there are still, potentially vitally important research sharing journals publishing in hard-copy print only.

In the past, AJOL used to conduct (when funding was available) in-person training workshops for subject-specific experts on Editorial Boards of scholar-led journals to share the irreplaceable research, and sometimes niche, content in ways that are proven to be of scientific and human and environmental importance to the satisfaction of researchers and librarians globally... Ironically, this is more difficult to prove to some African institutions, than to the rest of the world’s most stringent assessments. Happily, and currently, AJOL is now in the position to be able to conduct in-person training workshops again, throughout the continent (country-level and invitation-only), which are going to be interesting to learn from, given AI, and given the new and most important attention from the regional public sector now fully recognising the importance of relevant research-proven solutions to address the second largest continent in the world’s burden of disease, climate change, growing populace, and potentially fast and unpredictable systemic influences of Artificial Intelligence, and the AI Large Language Models (LLMs) and similar that are based on currently untraceable sources. It might end up that AJOL’s and other ALMASI project partners’ in-person training might become even more useful than in the past.

The number of OA journals beginning to charge small APCs for cost recovery increased in Africa as the giant commercial publishers in the Global North started shifting from subscription to APC-based income. In recent years, awareness of the Diamond model OA has significantly increased across Africa, with corresponding shifts towards the adoption of Diamond by previously APC-funded journals. In a few country publishing traditions, the Diamond model appears to be the dominant model. Journals established within the last few years are very often Diamond OA.

There is a paucity of research on African scholarly communication in general, and Diamond OA journal publishing in particular. In large part, this is because most of the continent is in the early stages of exploring the need for policy and funding support for domestic journal publishing.

Platforms

There are continental publishing platforms hosting Diamond OA journals, such as *African Journals Online (AJOL)* - a South African legal entity, but Pan-African non-for-profit organization that has been operating for over 20 years.

More recent university of Cape Town Library initiative *African Platform for Open Scholarship (APOS)* has been including some Diamond OA books and textbooks, and some Diamond OA journals, and has been operating since 2023.

Regional platforms include *Le Grenier des savoirs* from the Association Science Afrique, registered in Bénin - a collective, collaborative, and decolonial project that serves African Diamond OA journals published in French and in African languages. COPPHA PublishNow is a very recently established public health platform piloted by WACREN, in collaboration with PublicHealthAfrica, Peoples-Praxis, AFREhealth, WAIPH and Somali Health Action Journal, which is not hosting journals directly but supports Diamond OA publishing workflows, overlay journals, and repository integration. National platforms are supporting Diamond OA publishing in Algeria, Ethiopia, Morocco and South Africa. Many African universities run Open Journal Systems (OJS)-based platforms where Diamond OA journals are available.

Pan-African Platforms

African Journals Online (AJOL)

AJOL is an independent Not-for-Profit Organisation, legally based in South Africa since 2005, with pan-African stakeholder oversight through its Board of Directors, comprising representatives from stakeholder groups. AJOL⁴⁰ provides an online platform which hosts 905 scholarly journals (as of 2nd December 2025) published from 41 African countries at no cost to the journals. All research disciplines and languages are included. The journals are required to implement a valid system of peer review and be run primarily by African citizens in African countries, and are subject to a rigorous quality control assessment with supportive feedback before and if they are included on the AJOL platform. A factsheet for the AJOL platform is provided in Table 2.

⁴⁰ www.ajol.info

Name	African Journals Online (AJOL)
URL	https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ajol
Responsible organisation(s)	African Journals Online (AJOL)(RF)
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	905 of which 245 Diamond OA
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	<p>Scholarly content with original research, primarily Open Access, peer reviewed and quality controlled, published within Africa, or in the case of diaspora journals (limited to 2 at the point of writing to limit demand) primarily overseen by African citizens</p> <p>Journals must apply to join, and be assessed by AJOL to ensure they meet Journal Publishing Practices and Standards (JPPS) basic inclusion criteria at least before acceptance.</p>
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free hosting of content ● Free software maintenance and upgrades ● Free hosting of full online publishing workflow for journals who wish to run that via AJOL ● Help in setting up a journal online ● Training for editorial staff ● Free backups ● Free Digital Object Identifiers(DOI) ● Technical support and support on Open Access, copyright, assistance with choosing Creative Commons licensing, digitisation, ORCID application, visibility and other related topics ● Global networking and representation, including addressing research assessment global norms that are under-representing Southern research community needs and norms, ● Current and back issue content uploading to the platform if journals don't have adequate resources do so themselves, ● Feedback on areas for improved publishing policies and procedures after assessment, ● Regional in-person training workshops, periodic Webinars, ● Provision of article download and abstract view statistics on a granular level (by article, by download country, over time) via cryptic links to each journal,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open meta-data harvesting is active
Software	Open Journal Systems v3.3 (Amended by AJOL to function as a platform). Also, various software that underlie OJS in order for it to function.
Year of establishment	1998 as International Network for Advancing Science and Policy (INASP) project, from 2005 with African management under stakeholder oversight as an independent Pan-African Not-for-Profit Organisation
Business model for service provision	Not-for-Profit Organisation legally registered in South Africa, with an emphasis on supporting journals outside of South Africa Financial support from continuous fundraising Free for journals
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Current funding support from: Norwegian International Development Agency (NORAD), Wellcome, University Libraries, and various University Library Consortia via the Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS). Sustainability strategies: Ongoing fundraising, AJOL Supporters model (developed separately and very similar to SCOSS model) ⁴¹
Interface language	English, but journals are published in many different <i>lingua francas</i> including English, French, Arabic, Portuguese and Italian, and also in many indigenous African languages including: KiSwahili, Hausa, Igbo, Amharic, Afrikaans, Zulu, etc.
Links for more information	https://www.journalquality.info

Table 2 - AJOL platform factsheet

All business models are accepted, but AJOL actively encourages OA, and increasingly promotes Diamond OA publishing. The rationale is that subscription model and APC-model journals can

⁴¹ <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ajol/supporters-AJOL>

more easily adopt a Diamond model as a result of the free hosting, software support, persistent identifiers and technical support, and training that AJOL provides. More than a quarter of AJOL's journal partners have adopted the Diamond model (241 titles at the time of writing), with a Flip to No Fee toolkit in development.

AJOL works directly with a wide range of journal types on the platform and does not currently work through institutions on the continent, unless requested to do so. AJOL accepts journals in all languages.

Journals apply to AJOL for inclusion, and are assessed using AJOL's Journal Publishing Practices and Standards Framework (JPPS).⁴² This framework was conceptualised and drafted by AJOL with the input of hundreds of African journals, and further developed in partnership with the International Network for Advancing Science and Policy (INASP). Journals must meet at least the basic inclusion criteria before being included on the AJOL platform. Journals assessed against the 108 JPPS criteria are assigned one of six levels: inactive title; new title; no stars; one star; two stars; and three stars. The assigned JPPS levels serve a dual purpose. For readers and authors, they provide assurance that the journals meet an internationally recognized set of criteria at a particular level. For journal editors, the detailed feedback from the JPPS assessment helps them identify ways to improve their publishing practices and standards with a view to achieving a higher level at the next evaluation. AJOL provides journal-specific mentoring via email, online and in-person training and regular webinars.

With millions of article downloads from AJOL each month by researchers and librarians worldwide, the aggregation of approved partner journals provides massive regional and international visibility for African research.

AJOL technical infrastructure

The AJOL infrastructure is based on Free and Open Source software, notably an customized version of Open Journal Systems (OJS) supported by the Public Knowledge Project (PKP). In addition to free hosting of journal content and optional free full online publishing workflow hosting using OJS, AJOL provides free Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to its partner journals, as well as information about the number and location of article downloads for each journal via encrypted links. The modifications to OJS by AJOL have been fairly extensive, enabling it to run as an aggregator, and featuring a significantly modified front-end (improving the user experience of the website). AJOL has also developed an extensive in-house design back-end to capture data and produce reports for the use of AJOL staff.

In terms of technical infrastructure, the AJOL platform runs on various layers of Free and Open Source Softwares (FOSS). The top level is an OJS installation (version 3.3.0-11) using FOSS PHP 8.2 scripting language on the server-side to query a FOSS MySQL 8.0 database, on top of a FOSS Linux (Ubuntu) server which is hosted at AWS Cloud Services (Amazon) in Western Europe (Ireland), running FOSS Apache 2.4 web server, and backed up on Amazon systems, as well as backed up by

⁴² www.journalquality.info

AJOL’s Software Developer in Montague, South Africa. AJOL’s entire PDF repository of journal content is also stored on Google Drive, from which it is accessible (via two-factor authentication security) to all AJOL’s remote staff across the continent. The repository is backed up by Google as well as onto two physical servers (which have a permanent electricity supply via solar power) in Makhanda, South Africa.

For the purpose of capturing article download numbers, by country and across various timeframes, AJOL uses a combination of Google Analytics and proprietary software called Analytics Canvas, for which AJOL has been granted a permanent, free license.

AJOL does not use the OJS search functionality, but has instead chosen Lucene SOLR search. AJOL ensures that metadata is harvestable from the platform, as OJS is coded to support Open Archives Initiative Protocol on Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

AJOL has an agreement with CrossRef, through which AJOL absorbs the costs of Digital Object Identifier (DOI) assignment to articles, as well as implementing metadata registration on behalf of its partner journals.

Currently AJOL only offers PDFs as full text, as this format is the norm for the vast majority of journal partners. AJOL has requested assistance with including XML as an option in our offerings, but are yet to be in a position to assess the extent of work and processes required cost and implement this properly.

African Platform for Open Scholarship (APOS)

APOS is a project run out of the University of Cape Town (UCT) Library, and provides a platform for hosting African-published journals and books.⁴³ It was initiated with UCT Diamond Open Access books in 2021 and was initially referred to as the “continental platform,” but later expanded to include journals and was renamed APOS in October 2023. APOS works with Universities in 5 African countries, and hosts 24 journals, and 93 books. A factsheet for APOS is provided as Table 3.

Name	African Platform for Open Scholarship (APOS)
URL	https://apos.uct.ac.za/
Responsible organisation(s)	University of Cape Town (UCT) Discussions underway to transfer the platform to a regional network

⁴³ <https://apos.uct.ac.za/>

Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	24 Diamond journals; 93 Diamond books
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Unknown, except model must be Diamond OA
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free hosting of content, • free software maintenance and upgrades, • free hosting of full online publishing workflow for journals and books
Software	Open Journal Systems (OJS) and Open Monograph Systems (OMS)
Year of establishment	2023
Business model for service provision	Free for journals and books
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	UCT libraries funding
Interface language	English
Links for more information	

Table 3 - African Platform for Open Scholarship (APOS) platform factsheet

APOS works via institutions in Africa, and hosts only Diamond Open Access content at no cost to the institutions. APOS uses the multi-tenant model, that enables multiple institutions to publish and disseminate knowledge on one shared instance of the software, where the ICT support is centralised and institutions can focus on creating local scholarship (Raju et al. 2023). There are discussions to transfer it to one of the Regional networks in the immediate future. APOS is based on Free and Open Source Software, namely Open Journal Systems (OJS) and Open Monograph Systems (OMP) both supported by the Public Knowledge Project (PKP).

Le Grenier des savoirs

Le Grenier des savoirs is a collective, collaborative, and decolonial project that serves African journals published in French and in African languages. It aims to give researchers from Africa, Haiti and around the world the opportunity to freely and openly share their research and writings, building a high-quality, visible and accessible pluriversal science for all, with a view to cognitive justice and in the service of the common good and sustainable local development. A factsheet for *Le Grenier des savoirs* is provided as Table 4.

Name	Le Grenier des savoirs
URL	https://www.revues.scienceafrique.org
Responsible organisation(s)	Association Science Afrique, registered in Bénin
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	8
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	OA, open or double-blind peer review, inclusive writing, research integrity and anti-plagiarism policies and guidelines, no fees charged to authors, and cognitive justice: multidisciplinary, epistemological pluralism, multilingualism, combating sexism in science, and social relevance of articles
Services offered for journals (if any)	Setting up a journal online and hosting under a a CC BY-SA licence
Software	Pressbooks
Year of establishment	2015
Business model for service provision	Free for journals
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Florence Piron, who founded and supported the platform in the wake of the SOHA (Open Science in Haiti and Africa) project. The Association science et bien commun (ASBC), a Quebec-based association with a large African membership, has continued to support Grenier des savoirs since her death on 26 April 2021. The platform has been able to count on the voluntary work of its members and grants from the Florence Piron Fund.
Interface language	French
Links for more information	https://www.revues.scienceafrique.org/about/

Table 4 - Le Grenier des savoirs platform factsheet

COPPHA PublishNow

The Coalition for Open Access Publishing of Public Health in Africa (COPPHA) integrates a preprint repository BAOBAB and an open peer review system (The PublishNow Review Platform) tailored to address the challenges faced by researchers and public health professionals across the continent. It is a collaborative effort spearheaded by WACREN in partnership with PublicHealth.Africa, AFREhealth, the West African Institute of Public Health (WAIPH), Peoples-Praxis, and the Somali

Health Action Journal, with the aim to provide a transparent and inclusive environment for scholarly publishing. A factsheet for COPPHA PublishNow is provided as Table 5.

Name	COPPHA PublishNow
URL	https://coppha.vercel.app/
Responsible organisation(s)	WACREN, in collaboration with PublicHealthAfrica (PHA), Peoples-Praxis, AFREhealth, WAIPH, Somali Health Action Journal
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	Not hosting journals directly; instead, supports Diamond OA workflows, overlay journals, and repository integration
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Open to public health-relevant journals committed to Diamond OA principles
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Transparent open peer review, ● curation pathways, ● interoperability with repositories, ● persistent identifiers, ● overlay journal creation
Software	Kotahi (Publish-Review-Curate model)
Year of establishment	2025 (pilot), with full deployment planned Q2 2026
Business model for service provision	Diamond OA (no author or reader fees)
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Regional and global partnerships; grant support; integration with African research infrastructures (e.g. BAOBAB)
Interface language	English (with scope for expansion)
Links for more information	https://libsense.ren.africa/coppha and https://wacren.net/en/establishing-a-diamond-oa-publishing-ecosystem-for-public-health-research-in-africa-the-coalition-for-open-access-publishing-of-public-health-in-africa-coppha/

Table 5 – COPPHA PublishNow platform factsheet

National platforms

This section describes four publishing platforms from Algeria, Ethiopia, Morocco and South Africa.

Algerian Scientific Journals Platform (ASJP)

In 2015, Algeria launched an Algerian Scientific Journals Platform (ASJP)⁴⁴ that currently includes 894 Diamond OA journals and 269,109 articles. The platform is hosted by the Centre de Recherche sur l'Information Scientifique et Technique, and fully supports editorial and publication workflows in Arabic, French, English and Kabyle languages. In addition, it is free to use for Algerian OA journals. A factsheet for ASJP is provided as Table 6.

Name	Algerian Scientific Journals Platform (ASJP)
URL	https://asjp.cerist.dz
Responsible organisation(s)	Centre de Recherche sur l'Information Scientifique et Technique (CERIST) and Direction Générale de la Recherche Scientifique et du Développement Technologique (DGRSDT)
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	894 Diamond OA journals and 269,109 articles
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Only journals listed by the DGRSDT and editors trained on ASJP
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full editorial and publication workflows in Arabic, French, English and Kabyle languages, • search and browse functionality (e.g by the journal scope), • statistics (e.g. ten most downloaded articles per journal, 100 most cited articles and journals)
Year of establishment	2015
Business model for service provision	Free for journals
Funding streams	Public budget, provided by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, with a contribution from DGRSDT. Funding covers the costs of installations, maintenance, premises, human resources management,

⁴⁴ <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/>

	general IT services (e-mail, hardware, internet, etc.), specific IT services such as anti-virus and plagiarism software, and the salaries of permanent staff. Funding is currently very stable and will remain sustainable as long as public funding is provided.
Interface languages	English and French

Table 6 - Algerian Scientific Journals Platform (ASJP) platform factsheet

Ethiopian Journals Online (EJOL)

In 2013, Addis Ababa University Libraries launched EJOL to publish and increase the visibility of Ethiopian Journals using OJS. The EJOL platform is freely available to all locally published OA journals in Ethiopia. A factsheet for EJOL is provided as Table 7.

Name	Ethiopian Journals Online (EJOL)
URL	https://ejol.aau.edu.et
Responsible organisation(s)	Addis Ababa University Libraries
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	Over 20
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Scholarly content with original research, Open Access, peer reviewed and quality controlled, published within Ethiopia
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Free hosting, ● help in setting up a journal online, ● training for editorial staff, backup, ● free Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), ● technical support and support on Open Access, copyright, digitisation, visibility and other related topics, networking
Software	Open Journal Systems v3
Year of establishment	2013
Business model for service provision	Free for journals
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Funded by Addis Ababa University

Interface language	English, but journals are also published in different local languages: Amharic, Geez, Afaan Oromo.
Links for more information	https://ejol.aau.edu.et/index.php/index/about_ejoli

Table 7 - Ethiopian Journals Online (EJOL) platform factsheet

Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal (PRSM)

In Morocco, the Centre National pour la Recherche Scientifique et Technique (CNRST) – via the Institut Marocain de l'Information Scientifique et Technique (IMIST) – maintains the Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal (PRSM)⁴⁵ with over 100 Diamond OA journals playing a key role in national research production. PRSM OA digital publishing platform can be used free of charge to manage the entire editorial process, including article submission, peer review, online publication, and hosting, or just for content indexing. A factsheet for PRSM is provided as Table 8.

Name	Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal (PRSM)
URL	https://revues.imist.ma
Responsible organisation(s)	Centre National pour la Recherche Scientifique et Technique (CNRST) via the Institut Marocain de l'Information Scientifique et Technique (IMIST)
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	Over 100 Diamond OA journals, but also includes hosting of non-Diamond OA journals
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Journals published by public institutions and non-profit scholarly societies
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Journal development and hosting; ● flipping print journals to electronic journals and hosting on CNRST servers; ● support for new journals (platform set up, visual identity design, layout, etc. and hosting on CNRST servers). ● Journal indexing for electronic journals published on other platforms. ● anti-plagiarism software, (iThenticate); implementation of DOIs; ● training sessions on various aspects of the editorial process and indexing.

⁴⁵ <https://revues.imist.ma/>

Software	Open Journal Systems v3
Business model for service provision	Free of charge
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	CNRST
Interface language	French
Links for more information	https://revues.imist.ma/index.php/index/apropos

Table 8 - Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal (PRSM) factsheet

Khulisa Journals

The Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf) operates an OJS-based platform, Khulisa Journals. Khulisa (KH00-lee-sa) is a word from the Nguni languages (Xhosa, Zulu, Ndebele, and Swati) that are indigenous to southern and eastern Africa and means “to grow or foster the development of a person or community”. It began in 2014–2015 as a pilot project with five journals and was officially established in 2016. Khulisa Journals mission is to support good-quality, peer-reviewed, OA South African journals to adhere to best practice and to enhance their reach through optimising accessibility, discoverability, indexability, interoperability and visibility. ASSAf’s vision for the Khulisa Journals platform is to sustain and grow the hosting service in the long term, and maintain and develop the functionality provided on the platform in line with best practice and ASSAf’s mission. A factsheet for PRSM is provided as Table 9.

Name	Khulisa Journals
URL	https://journals.assaf.org.za/index.php
Responsible organisation(s)	Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf)
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	9 out of 17 journals are Diamond OA
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Journals must be included in the SciELO SA Collection ⁴⁶ or have received a recommendation from an ASSAf peer review panel for inclusion on SciELO SA and meet the criteria for inclusion on SciELO SA.
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT support - 1st and 2nd level (business hours). • Full hosting of the journal, combining a website and journal content management system 2-in-1.

⁴⁶ <http://www.scielo.org.za/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Full autonomy over the journal, within the Khulisa Journals framework/policies/vision/mission. ● Regular system and plugin upgrades, as well as back-ups. ● Crossref integration for the depositing of DOIs. ● Automated deposits with Portico (digital preservation). ● Automated export of metadata to DOAJ. ● Citation export. ● ORCIDs integration. ● Social share buttons. ● Altmetric (for non-citation metrics). ● Dimensions (for citation counts). ● iThenticate plagiarism checker. ● Recommendations on best practices, and expert scholarly publishing advice. ● Initial setup of the journal, and upload of one retrospective issue. Upload of further backfiles for the account of the journal owner. ● Registration with Google Search Console, Google Scholar and Google Analytics. ● Article and review reports. ● User training, continuous support, and webinars on new developments. ● Regular e-news communication, staying in touch with the Khulisa Journals community. ● Benefit from a lively and innovative scholarly journal community. ● All Khulisa Journals are indexed by the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ).
Software	Open Journal Systems v 3.4.0.6
Other technical details	Dedicated server (with xneelo) & SLA with a System Admin (outsourced); development work (bug fixes) outsourced; a federated approach (one OJS installation, unlimited number of journals)
Business model for service provision	Journal setup fee (once-off) – ZAR 10,000.00 (\$548) and annual hosting fee – ZAR 15,000.00 (\$822) or ZAR 20,000.00 (\$1096). No increase since 2016. The more journals are hosted, the more affordable the platform becomes
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Journal set up and annual hosting fees are covered by Government departments, institutions or Universities/Higher Education Faculties/Departments, professional body member fees, advertisements, Article Processing Fees (for Non-Diamond OA journals)
Interface language	English
Links for more information	https://journals.assaf.org.za/index.php/index/about

Table 9 - Khulisa Journals platform factsheet

Institutional platforms

Many African universities run OJS-based platforms where Diamond OA journals are available, for example:

- In Ethiopia: Diredawa University - Harla Journals hosting six journals, Jimma university portal with eight journals,⁴⁷ Haramaya University with six journals,⁴⁸ Hawassa University with ten journals,⁴⁹ Mekelle University,⁵⁰ University of Gondar with six journals and Wollo university⁵¹.
- In Ghana: University of Cape Coast⁵² and University of Ghana⁵³
- In Tanzania: University of Dar es Salaam⁵⁴
- In Uganda: Kampala International University⁵⁵

There are also journal platforms outside Africa that have established partnerships and host African journals. Among these are:.

- University of Michigan African e-Journals project⁵⁶
- OpenEdition⁵⁷ is a French platform for scientific journals, mainly in the social sciences and humanities. Among the 658 journals, 13 are in countries tagged in Africa.
- Erudit⁵⁸ is a Canadian journal platform that hosts Etudes Littéraires Africaines journal that is run by an international association.
- Episciences⁵⁹ is a French OA overlay journals platform, based on preprints reviewing, which hosts ARIMA: Revue africaine de recherche en informatique et mathématiques appliquées, and RASPA: Revue africaine de santé et de productions animales

Output types

Journals

A recent study ([Azilan, Lrhoul, Aventurier et al., 2024](#)) using ISSN data, showed that, of 1070 scientific journals online in nine different countries in Africa, all of them are open-access, but

⁴⁷ <https://journals.ju.edu.et>

⁴⁸ <https://www.haramyajournals.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://journals.hu.edu.et/hu-journals/>

⁵⁰ <https://journal.mu.edu.et/>

⁵¹ <https://abjol.org.et/>

⁵² <https://journal.ucc.edu.gh/>

⁵³ <https://journals.ug.edu.gh/>

⁵⁴ <https://journals.udsm.ac.tz/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.kiu.ac.ug/journals>

⁵⁶ <https://d.lib.msu.edu/aejp>

⁵⁷ <https://www.openedition.org/catalogue-journals>

⁵⁸ <https://www.erudit.org/fr/revues/ela/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.episciences.org/journals/#arima-2>

around 30% of journals charge publication fees. These are often set at 50,000 CFA (75 euros) in North Africa (100 to 150). Most of these journals are not identified in international databases (WOS, Scopus, Open Alex, Dimensions, ROAD, and DOAJ) and are not searchable or visible. It is very difficult to identify journals based on the Diamond model because they are not categorised under this model, and fees are not always disclosed. Sometimes, it is only clear that fees are required once the submission process has been started. However, disparities remain between North African countries, which are distinguished by the existence of structured research platforms, and other regions where journals are most often supported by isolated institutions. Thematically, the social sciences dominate, with linguistic diversity centered mainly around French, English, and Arabic. The analysis reveals significant potential for editorial transformation, particularly through the adoption of the Diamond Open Access model. In addition, the study reveals many weaknesses in the data from the International Standard Serial Number (ISSN) for West and Central African countries.

Books

In Africa research budgets are frequently constrained. Diamond OA book publishing has emerged as a promising yet still underdeveloped model ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)). Unlike the now widespread OA models for journals, Diamond OA for books is slowly growing and not yet gaining enough traction. It is largely confined to mission driven, nonprofit and community-led initiatives. These initiatives are explicitly motivated by principles that relate to the public good, including equitable knowledge access, decolonization of scholarly communication, and capacity building of African researchers ([Kuchma and Ševkušić, 2024](#)). Their primary focus lies in the creation of shared infrastructure and community owned publishing ecosystems that facilitate the free production and dissemination of scholarly books. This limited uptake of Diamond OA for books reflects structural barriers such as chronic underfunding of book publishing, the high costs of editorial and production workflows, and the scarcity of long term business models suited to the African research environment ([Bosman, Kramer & Moore, 2021](#)). Furthermore, African countries are at different stages of adoption or transition toward Diamond OA for books with many initiatives still in early development. As a result, there is relatively little peer reviewed scholarship describing their governance or financial models. Much of the available knowledge comes from institutional websites, project documentation and grey/popular literature.

Table 10 provides a snapshot overview of notable Diamond OA book publishing initiatives that are currently active across the continent.

Name	Type	Country/ Owner	Infrastructure / Platform / Software used	Business model/Funding scheme	OA Books Published / Type / Language s	More Info
UCT Press (University of Cape Town)	University library press	South Africa / University of Cape Town & UCT Libraries	Hosted by UCT libraries platform open monograph press. POD via local distributors	Hybrid: Diamond OA model: free PDFs; Institutional/lib rary budget. prints sales, In kind support	Primarily English; African scholarshi p focus	https://lib.uct.ac.za/uct-press more info on catalogue & guidelines there
BookHub / APC-Minna / FUTMinna OA BookHub (Nigeria)	University / APC pilot	Nigeria / Federal University of Technology, Minna (FUTMinna), Academic Publishing Centre (APC)	Uses Ketty(CoKo) and locally hosted Bookhub instance centre) outlet of FUTMinna for hosting and distribution.	Diamond OA pilot; Institutional, National TETFund, local grants	8 OA books by Q1, then 18 more by year end under pilot. Content in English; Focus on Nigerian Academic. Context, focus on locally relevant academic materials.	https://www.bookhub.ng (BookHub OA page)
CODESRIA Books	Pan-African scholarly network publisher	Senegal / Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa (CODESRIA)	Own Book Publication System platform hosted by CODESRIA publication portal	Mixed model: some titles are sold (print), some available for purchase; many unsolicited and solicited manuscripts, institutional	Focus on social sciences & humanities ; multiple African languages / multilingual context	https://codesria.org/codesria-books/

				funding via CODESRIA programmes/ grants	(English, French) given	
AfricArXiv	Pan-African preprint / repository	?	Community preprint repository (OSF/AfricArXiv infrastructure),	Community run, volunteers, hosted partnerships, external funding	For early versions of books thus not a publishing platform. Supports multiple language in translation	https://info.africanarxiv.org/
African Minds	Nonprofit OA publisher	South Africa	Publisher website: books also hosted on OAPEN / DOAB / Science Open. uses standard digital publishing stacks (PDF/EPUB)	Hybrid nonprofit: some titles Diamond (publisher-funded), some with BPCs (book processing charges), print sales, distribution partners	English; focus on African research in social sciences/humanities.	https://www.africanminds.co.za/ (African Minds)
WACREN / LIBSENSE (shared repository / hosting initiatives)	Library / national network	Nigeria	Shared repository services (WEK03, multi-tenant repo infrastructure)	Funded by Regional partners projects and donors. Sustainability strategy via consortia models and National Research and Education Networks	supports OA books & theses if institutions host monographs or chapters; used for national IR & multi-tenant services	https://libsense.ren.africa/ and WACREN websites (LIBSENSE multi-tenant WEK03 / Invenio pilots) (https://libsense.ren.africa/home)

				support		
AISA / HSRC Press (Africa Institute of South Africa / HSRC Press)	National / research institute press	South Africa	Institutional press infrastructure digital publishing & repository integration		AISA titles and HSRC Press titles; HSRC has OA policy for some outputs and OA catalogue. Language Focus: English	https://hsrc.ac.za/hsrc-press/

Table 10 - Diamond OA book initiatives on the African continent

Diamond OA book publishing in Africa is a hybrid ecosystem of outputs that integrate both digital and print formats. These outputs primarily consist of monographs and edited collections with a concentration in the humanities and social sciences. Research councils and think tanks also publish policy reports and working papers. Although open textbooks remain underrepresented, institutional commitment to their production is growing, particularly in South Africa, where open education resources have become a strategic priority. Most publishers adopt fast digital production, generating PDF versions for preservation and free access, and increasingly also e-book formats for mobile-friendly reading. **University-led** initiatives such as UCT Press and nonprofit publishers like African Minds have invested in producing web-native outputs that are readable across devices: books are typically published in HTML or through online reading platforms. This is a key achievement for access given the uneven connectivity infrastructure across the continent. Nonetheless, print on demand (POD) remains vital, as print continues to be the dominant format in several African regions especially where internet access is costly or unreliable. Especially for small book presses, POD facilitates cost-effective small print runs, reducing storage and distribution costs, and sustaining library acquisition channels. Crucially, these outputs are interconnected through metadata and identifier ecosystems. A single book may appear as a PDF in the OAPEN library, an e-book via a library aggregator, and have a POD title through the African Books Collective (ABC), all linked by a common DOI. This interoperability is not merely technical, but strategic as it maximizes visibility and promotes equitable access across media, and enhances sustainability by diversifying dissemination pathways.

African Diamond OA book publishing is characterised by a reliance on open-source technologies and distributed infrastructure. Referring to Table 3 above, a prominent example is the use of Open Monograph Press (OMP) by library-led publishing programmes, notably at the University of Cape

Town (UCT),⁶⁰ where OMP underpins peer review, editorial workflow, and metadata dissemination. In parallel, newer experimental platforms, such as BookHub⁶¹ at Federal University of Technology Minna (FUTMinna), leverage Coko Foundation's Ketty framework to produce web-native monographs with EPUB and PDF outputs.

Complementary infrastructures include AfricArXiv, which provides a preprint and repository layer for African scholarship and African Books Collective (ABC),⁶² which offers pan-African distribution and print-on-demand (POD) services (ABC, n.d.). Integration with global discovery tools, such as DOAB⁶³ and Crossref, is essential for visibility and citation of African OA books.

Integration flows: how African OA book platforms connect to discovery, identifiers, and distribution.

Integration between production platforms, metadata intermediaries, identifier services, repositories and distribution partners is a critical enabler for Diamond OA book publishing in Africa. Publishers typically adopt a workflow in which manuscripts are processed through editorial production platforms, such as OMP, COKO etc, each producing final outputs as mentioned in Section 1 above (PDF, Epub). These provide metadata which are then passed on to metadata intermediaries and aggregators for example, DOAB, THOTH, and OAPEN. The intermediaries normalize metadata by exposing machine-readable versions (KBART, ONIX) that library discovery services and other aggregators can harvest. For small and mission-driven African publishers especially, this reduces the technical and administrative burden of registration and indexing thereby enabling their titles to appear in library catalogues and global discovery sources.

Preprints

Preprinting practices are still limited in Africa. Although subject-based preprint servers and institutional or generalist repositories like AfricArxiv and BAOBAB operated by WACREN allow African researchers to post preprints at no cost and also support multilingual posting, broadening accessibility beyond dominant languages, structural barriers include minimal recognition from institutions and funders, and the continued dominance of traditional publishers in shaping what is considered legitimate scholarly publishing. Non-structural challenges include low awareness of the benefits of preprints among researchers, as well as limited awareness of local preprint platforms.

A survey run by Aneth Bella David, Lamis Yahia Mohamed Elkheir, Roseline Dzekem Dine, Emmanuel Adamolekun and Jonny Coates "revealed widespread unawareness regarding preprints and reliance on traditional publishers among African researchers. Of 182 respondents from Nigeria, South Africa, and Tanzania, 41.9% posted preprints, yet 77% were unaware of Africa-specific repositories. While non-posters read preprints, fewer cited or shared them. Social media served as the primary platform for preprint sharing, with concerns over sharing before peer review. Although recognized for accessibility and career enhancement, concerns persisted

⁶⁰ <https://lib.uct.ac.za/services/publishing>

⁶¹ <https://www.bookhub.ng/>

⁶² <https://www.africanbookscollective.com>

⁶³ <https://www.doabooks.org>

regarding recognition and co-author unfamiliarity.” ([David, Elkheir, Dine, et al. 2024](#)) Recommendations include increasing awareness of preprints and further work to dispel common and persistent myths through the use of tailored outreach initiatives; improving institutional recognition by encouraging the development of policy frameworks that utilizes preprints as part of promotion and recruitment practices in addition to graduation requirements; and engaging with funders.

Addis Ababa University demonstrates leadership by encouraging post-graduate students to post preprints. Development and support for preprint platforms in partnerships with universities, research institutions, industry, civil society, and international organizations is included in the Uganda National Council of Science and Technology Open Science Policy.

Organisational structures & Governance models

African Diamond OA journals are published by institutions: universities, research institutes, faculties and schools, research centers and research laboratories, academies of sciences, national and regional associations and other types of scholarly societies (e.g. multidisciplinary Associação Multidisciplinar de Investigação Científica e Universidade Rainha Njinga a Mbande in Angola and professional associations such as Ghana Library Association, East African Association of Neurological Surgeons (EAANS), The Kenya Association of Physicians, The National Association for Clean Air in South Africa) and other types of nonprofits (e.g. The African Centre for the Constructive Resolution of Disputes (ACCORD) and Affirmative action on Gender Equality Network (AGEN)) including library consortia (e.g. Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium (KLISC)).

The ‘Landscape of No-fee Open Access Publishing in Africa’ study found that about one-third of Diamond OA journals surveyed have a dedicated institutional unit responsible for publishing with personnel fully or partially employed to work for the journal ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)). This study is based on survey responses from 199 journals, 21 institutional, national and continental platforms that host Diamond OA journals, and 25 country reports with information about current funding and financial sustainability approaches and challenges, institutional in-kind support, incentives and collaborations among Diamond OA journals, needs and strategies to advance Diamond OA publishing.

Figure 2 - Dedicated institutional units or the lack of them

Journal editors often perform co-publishing roles, for example from the 'About' page of The Journal of Student Affairs in Africa (JSAA): "JSAA is published twice a year by the JSAA Editors in collaboration with the University of Pretoria and the open access, non-profit, public benefit academic publisher African Minds⁶⁴."

The governance structures of Diamond OA journals in Africa include the following types: Editorial Board/Editorial Committee/Comité scientifique/Scientific Board and in some cases Advisory Board. The 'Landscape of No-fee Open Access Publishing in Africa' study found that most Diamond OA journals surveyed (159; 79.9%) have up to 20 members in their editorial boards or other editorial bodies, with almost equal shares of those having up to ten board members (80; 40.2%) and those with 11-20 members (79; 39.7%) (Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024). The fact that less than 10% of the respondents have editorial boards with more than 30 members confirms that the vast majority of the surveyed journals has manageable editorial boards. Approximately one quarter of the respondents (19; 24.6%) have more than 50% of their editorial board members from outside the journal's country, and the share of those with less than 10% international members is almost the same (51; 25.6%). At the same time, nearly half (97; 48.7%) of the respondents report having more than half of the editorial board members from outside their institutions.

Governance in African Diamond OA book publishing largely mirrors that of academic journal publishing, but is contextualized by the longer production cycles and curatorial demands of monographs. Library-led presses are typically managed through library administrative structures, with input from faculty editorial boards. For example, the UCT libraries' publishing program relies on faculty editorial boards to guide editorial decisions, while independent nonprofit publishers such as African Minds maintain small in-house teams of editors and project managers, contracting freelancers for specialized tasks, including typesetting and translation. Similarly,

⁶⁴ <https://www.africanminds.co.za/>

scholarly networks like CODESRIA operate under nonprofit boards of trustees, combining financial and strategic oversight.

Funding mechanisms

The ‘Landscape of No-fee Open Access Publishing in Africa’ study found that about 60% of Diamond OA journals surveyed rely on volunteer work fully or partially (Kuchma and Ševkušić 2024). About a half of the Diamond OA journals surveyed receive some institutional funding, and types of funding are described in the Table 11 below.

Types of funding	# journals using this funding source
Fixed and permanent subsidy from a journal's primary institution's base	49
Periodically negotiated subsidy from a journal's primary institution's base	42
Time-limited grants or subsidies, either private or public from outside a journal's primary institution's base	20
Permanent public/government funding (international, national, local)	12
Collective funding (e.g. crowdfunding, membership fees, etc.)	23
Print sales	22
Other	45

Table 11 - Types of funding for Diamond OA journals in Africa

Almost equal numbers of respondents saw their funding sources as stable or very stable (40.1%) and unstable or very unstable (39.2%). Most journals (71.4%) do not have an annual approved budget. The majority of the respondents (56.8%) have a journal sustainability plan.” (Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024)

Most African Diamond OA journals surveyed rely on institutional in-kind support, where general IT services support is the most common, followed by service-specific IT services – publishing platforms, websites and other tools, facilities and premises. The majority of journals (57.8%) rely on multiple forms of support provided by the host organization, while 7% report receiving no support.” (Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024)

Almost a quarter of the responding journals reported that their institutions provided incentives for journal personnel, e.g. additional points during evaluation/promotion, allowances, bonuses and honoraria, and reduction in regular work and working hours (including teaching load and institutional administrative work). (Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024)

Financial constraints are by far the most pressing challenge affecting three-quarters of the respondents, while nearly half are struggling with a lack of human resources.

Infrastructure-related and administrative challenges affect more than one third of the respondents. ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#))

Funding mechanisms for Diamond OA books

Diamond OA book publishers in Africa rely on a variety of funding sources to sustain their operations. These include:

- Institutional support - University libraries subsidise staff time, infrastructure, and overhead costs
- Grant funding - for example Open Book Collective, UNESCO, Arcadia fund
- Capacity building and infrastructure partnerships in lieu of funding - DOAB, THOTH, OMP, Invest in Open Infrastructure.
- Governments or Research Council funding - some presses receive public funding tied to National Research priorities for example, HSRC press in South Africa
- Sales of print on demand copies- for example African Minds covering distribution costs without charging authors relying on pod sale
- Consortium membership and institutional contributions- regional networks pool membership fees to sustain publications for example, CODESRIA, WACREN, Libsense

Most of these models are subsidy-based and designed to remove author and book processing charges, thus keeping books freely accessible in line with Diamond OA principles. However, ensuring predictable long-term funding remains a significant challenge, often reducing scalability and continuity. To address this, models combining free digital access with revenue from print sales are emerging, for example in East Africa as innovative business models (for commercial publishers as part of their OA initiative) that diversify funding sources, essential for maintaining operations while keeping books free for both authors and readers.

Solutions and services

There is a notable lack of studies specifically focused on the solutions and services used in Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing in Africa. Available information is largely fragmented and typically embedded in case studies that describe individual publishing platforms. However, such information often becomes outdated quickly, as platforms undergo regular updates, functional changes, or may even be discontinued. The insights presented in this section primarily draw on the 2024 landscape analysis conducted by EIFL ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)), which included a survey of 199 Diamond OA journals and expert-authored country reports, evidence provided on journal websites and publishing platforms, and the dataset containing a summary of information about known public installations of Open Journal Systems, Open Monograph Press, and Open Preprint Systems provided by the Public Knowledge Project (PKP).

Infrastructure for Diamond OA publishing and dissemination

Software

African Diamond OA journals rely on diverse types of publishing infrastructure, including primarily single-journal websites and multi-journal platforms (continental, regional, national or institutional).

Different setups are possible within those two main types, depending on the software, additional services used, and provision and usage types. Also, some journals are hosted.

As far as software is concerned, single-journal websites can be based on:

- Free and open-source (FOSS) journal management system software (most commonly OJS, but also Kotahi);
- Widely used free and open source content management system (CMS) software (e.g. Wordpress, Drupal, Joomla, etc.) that typically supports only content display, but can be combined with custom-made modules or commercial tools (e.g. Scholar One) to support submissions, review and production workflows.

According to Khanna et al. 2024, there are 2351 OJS installations in Africa.

The survey conducted by [Kuchma & Ševkušić \(2024\)](#) reveals a strong preference for publishing platforms based on free and open-source software. Specifically, 68.3% of the surveyed journals use OJS, and CMSs such as WordPress, Drupal, and Joomla are also quite popular.

The same survey shows that the infrastructure is usually provided by institutions (nearly half of the surveyed journals) and is often maintained by editors, volunteers, or academic staff. One-third outsource infrastructure and maintenance services.

In journals operating without an integrated editorial management system, submission and editorial processes are usually managed manually, via email. Some journals use commercial services such as ScholarOne or Manuscript Central. It is noteworthy that some journals using OJS handle submission and editorial processes manually primarily due to a lack of staff and skills to manage these workflows online.

Multi-journal platforms reveal an even greater diversity of solutions. In terms of software, they can be based on widely used FOSS (most commonly OJS, but also Kotahi,⁶⁵ or custom-made proprietary solutions (AOSIS)⁶⁶.

The infrastructure for journal websites is also be provided on a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) basis by external providers, either free of charge (e.g. in national platforms, or Europe-based platforms

⁶⁵ <https://kotahi.community/>

⁶⁶ <https://aosis.co.za/about-journals/>

Episciences⁶⁷ and OpenEdition⁶⁸), or for a fee (e.g. PKP Publishing Services⁶⁹). Some journals use proprietary journal management systems (e.g. Scholastica,⁷⁰ AOSIS), typically provided on a SaaS basis.

Platforms have different functions: content display and dissemination, support for the entire publishing process, evaluation (rating), content aggregation, ensuring visibility). However, classifying platforms strictly by function is challenging, as most fulfill multiple roles, and their perceived purpose can vary depending on the context.

The most common platform type is institutional (The University of Zambia Journals,⁷¹ University of Ghana uses Open Journal Systems,⁷² etc.) or national (e.g. Ethiopian Journals Online - EJOL,⁷³ Khulissa Journals⁷⁴). These platforms designed primarily to support publishing workflows and content dissemination are prevalingly based on FOSS, usually OJS and operate on a SaaS model where a journal is assigned a fully independent software instance (single-tenant) or multiple journals are hosted on the same installation (multi-tenant). Presumably, the scope of services offered may vary, but it is not possible to provide a more accurate breakdown of various options, as key details (e.g. inclusion criteria, availability of editorial services such as plagiarism detection tools, whether journals are charged for services, etc.) are frequently missing from platform pages. Along with providing hosting for journals, platforms may also reference externally hosted journals, e.g. the Moroccan national platform Le portail des revues scientifiques marocaines - PRSM.⁷⁵

In case of commercial providers, membership with a platform may affect journal policies, e.g. AOSIS has a default APC policy, where an APC is defined. Some journals include waiver statements to indicate that they are not charging fees, which may raise confusion regarding the journal's Diamond OA status.

Another key type of platform is non-commercial custom-made systems managed by non-profit entities seeking to support, monitor, evaluate and preserve (OA) journals in country, region or the continent, offering their services to journals free of charge under the condition that they meet certain quality criteria (AJOL, Scielo SA). It is noteworthy that platforms usually accept both Diamond OA and APC-based journals, and subscription-based journals can still be found on AJOL. Also, it is not uncommon for OA journals to have their content closed on commercial platforms like Sabinet.

AJOL and Scielo SA are not hosting primary journal websites and are usually referred to as aggregators, suggesting that content is harvested. However, content provision is not automated

⁶⁷ <https://www.episciences.org/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.openedition.org/>

⁶⁹ <https://pkp.sfu.ca/hosting-services/>

⁷⁰ <https://scholasticahq.com/>

⁷¹ <https://journals.unza.zm/>

⁷² <https://journals.uq.edu.gh/>

⁷³ <https://ejol.aau.edu.et/>

⁷⁴ <https://journals.assaf.org.za/>

⁷⁵ <https://revues.imist.ma/index.php/index/Revues-references>

and it involves manual workflows. Although not primary journal websites, for many journals these platforms remain the most reliable and the most complete source of information.

The relationship between single-journal websites and platforms is complex. Notably, a significant number of journals have both independent websites and disseminate their content via one or more platforms. The content found on those different venues is not always the same – e.g. the content in AJOL may be up-to-date, while the content on the website is outdated and vice-versa. Although this is confusing for users and may affect the reputation of journals, there are several possible reasons for this practice, including uninterrupted access and preservation in case of website failure, and a desire to improve chances for indexing.

Support for indexing, PIDs, and metadata standards

The technical features of the publishing infrastructure directly impact a journal's ability to maintain visibility and interoperability. Websites and platforms based on FOSS journal management systems have the potential to ensure better discoverability and facilitate indexing, as support for the delivery of machine-readable metadata to search engines and aggregators is a native software feature.

The results of the 2024 survey ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)) demonstrate that AJOL plays a major role when it comes to indexing: more than half of the surveyed journals (53.3%) indicated that their journals are indexed in AJOL, while for about 40% of journals AJOL was the only service where they were indexed. Other indexing services were also highlighted: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), where almost one-third of the surveyed journals were included, as well as Google Scholar, Web of Science and Scopus. Journals are particularly interested in getting accepted for indexing in the last two services, believing that this would attract high-quality submissions and more citations.

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are widely recognized as essential for ensuring research integrity, visibility, and interoperability. According to the 2024 survey ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)), Crossref DOI is the most commonly used PID (nearly 60% of the surveyed journals). The ability to implement and sustain PID registration varies. Some journals rely on intermediaries such as AJOL for DOI assignment (where the landing pages associated with DOIs are on AJOL's domain), while others struggle to maintain subscriptions due to currency regulations or institutional limitations on paying international fees. PID waivers are offered through Crossref's Global Equitable Membership (GEM).⁷⁶ African journals can also apply for grants through the DataCite's Global Access⁷⁷ to support the adoption and implementation of DOIs for their articles.

According to the survey, the use of ORCID identifiers is less widespread (reported by only 25.6% of journals). Platforms usually support ORCID, but this option is not used by all journals. Other PIDs

⁷⁶ <https://www.crossref.org/gem/>

⁷⁷

<https://datacite.org/event/introducing-datacites-global-access-program-in-africa-what-is-in-it-for-the-continent/>

like ROR, Handle, and ARK are used only occasionally, although WACREN provides support for the implementation of ARKs⁷⁸ free of charge.

Digital preservation

Accurate data about digital preservation options is not available. Based on information from journal websites, African Diamond OA journals are using PKP Preservation Network, offered free of charge to OJS-based journals, LOCKSS, CLOCKSS, Portico. The actual coverage by these services is impossible to establish based on available data. It seems that a significant number of OJS-based journals are still not using the PKP Preservation Network.

Editorial services

As already mentioned, some journals do not use journal management systems despite having access to them, and instead manage editorial workflows via email.

The information about editorial services is scarce. The 2024 survey suggests that journals show the greatest interest in tools for detecting plagiarism and AI-generated content ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)). The most commonly used plagiarism detection tools appear to be iThenticate and Turnitin, which can be provided by parent institutions or purchased directly by journals. There is no clear data on how many journals actually have access to these tools. It is also unclear whether these tools are primarily used via integrations within publishing platforms or accessed directly. Anecdotal evidence suggests that some journals screen all submissions before peer review, while others only scan manuscripts that are accepted for publication. It seems that many journals seem unaware of the discounted rates available through Crossref Similarity Check.

Capacity building and training

Support for capacity building, training programmes and workshops aimed at enhancing the skills of editors, reviewers, authors, and journal managers in scholarly publishing practices, including ethical standards, peer review processes, and editorial management is highlighted as a priority both by survey participants and experts involved in the study 'Landscape of no-fee open access publishing in Africa' ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)).

Capacity building for Diamond Open Access (OA) journals is actively supported by various actors. AJOL has long provided training, advice and support for journal editors, especially small and regional journals, in areas like online publishing workflows, editorial practices, and visibility.⁷⁹

West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)⁸⁰ is involved in capacity building for Diamond OA publishing through multiple initiatives, such as LIBSENSE (Library Support for Embedded NREN Services and E-infrastructure),⁸¹ which focuses on libraries, and the Coalition for Open Access Publishing of Public Health in Africa (COPPHA),⁸² which aims to enhance

⁷⁸ <https://pidslink.wacren.net/faq>

⁷⁹ <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ajol>

⁸⁰ <https://wacren.net/en/>

⁸¹ <https://libsense.ren.africa/home>

⁸² <https://wacren.net/en/coppha/>

the sustainability and quality of Diamond OA publishing across the continent by providing training, fostering peer review practices, and building a community for journal editors and publishers.

In collaboration with EIFL (Electronic Information for Libraries), AJOL and WACREN, launched Diamond Open Access Publishing Community of Practice (CoP) for Africa⁸³ within the project 'Collaboration for Sustainable OA Publishing in Africa'.⁸⁴ It connects over 100 African no-fee journals, providing a space for sharing resources, discussing challenges, and collaborating on capacity-building initiatives. Furthermore, many journal and platform support projects funded through this project include training and capacity-building actions.

On the national and institutional level, a variety of capacity-building and training initiatives support Diamond OA journals across Africa. In Algeria, collaboration between journals is fostered through joint platforms, exchanges between editorial teams, and regular workshops on open access and scholarly publishing, coordinated by CERIST in partnership with the Directorate-General for Scientific Research and Technological Development. In Mozambique, editors, reviewers, and authors have relied on training provided by international publishers such as Elsevier and Springer as well as initiatives like Research4Life, which is not tailored to the needs of Diamond OA publishing. However, training has recently been provided by Brazilian and Portuguese partners via the Lusophone Open Science Conference (ConfOA). The University of Namibia (UNAM) assists local editors with compliance for DOAJ indexing and provides guidance on ethics, copyright, licensing, indexing, DOI assignment, and broader capacity-building. At the University of Cape Town, training extends to hosted institutions, journal editors, and reviewers, combined with technical and software support (e.g. OJS upgrades and migration). South Africa's Academy of Science (ASSAf) plays a leading role in training and capacity-building for editors, reviewers, authors, and other stakeholders in South Africa through its Scholarly Publishing Programme. It offers workshops, webinars, and resources to advance editorial quality and best practices in open access publishing ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)).

Production services

Production services may be provided internally, outsourced to commercial or non-profit providers, or coordinated through regional consortia or freelance networks. This information has high practical value but is in many cases not available or incomplete.

The majority of journals provide full-text content only in PDF, and conversion to JATS XML is a significant challenge for most journals ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)).

Accessibility compliance is an emerging topic and most journal websites and platforms are not aligned with accessibility standards ([Kuchma & Ševkušić, 2024](#)).

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<https://wacren.net/en/news/community-of-practice-for-diamond-open-access-publishing-in-africa-opens-for-application/>

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<https://wacren.net/en/news/community-of-practice-for-diamond-open-access-publishing-in-africa-opens-for-application/>

Latin America

Open Access in Latin America has been implemented primarily through scientific journals -whose sustainability model is Diamond Open Access- and through institutional repositories, which are led by the academic and scientific community and financed with public funds.

Historically, and largely due to various circumstances, including the lack of financial resources to access commercial scientific publications, the region has developed public, non-commercial infrastructures, upholding knowledge as a common good that should be accessible without economic or profit-driven barriers for both authors and readers ([Becerril-García, 2024](#)).

The movement toward Diamond OA journals in Latin America is characterized by strong institutional support, with universities and scientific organizations managing editorial processes based on quality and rigor. The academic sector plays a fundamental role as owner and publisher of scientific journals.

Nowadays, this region is widely recognized as one of the most consolidated in open access, given the presence of multiple journal portals, open access repositories, and information systems that few continents possess, as well as organizations that advance openness and many other initiatives that can be found on the web ([Becerril-García & Córdoba González, 2021](#)).

Several platforms and infrastructures have emerged in the region as key digital components in the communication of science. Latindex, Redalyc, SciELO, CLACSO, AmeliCA, LaReferencia, as well as hundreds of journal portals at institutional and country levels, disciplinary and institutional repositories, and repository networks, are part of the regional infrastructure.

The Latin American ecosystem encompasses slightly more than 14,000 online journals (of which 3,569 have met the criteria of the Latindex 2.0 Catalog). Furthermore, of the nearly 6,000 repositories registered in OpenDOAR, 1,765 are affiliated with countries in the Latin American region ([Becerril-García, 2024](#)).

Latin America features more than 650 journal portals (i.e. platforms where the content is made available in its primary instance), which are generally managed by the journals themselves. Among the most relevant are those from the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM) and the University of São Paulo (USP). Both portals employ OJS technology and adhere to the philosophy of open access. Moreover, both platforms ensure content quality through the implementation of rigorous academic criteria. Furthermore, they possess interoperability with various systems and provide diverse services to their respective communities, in addition to content availability.

Most of these journal portals are built with free software developed by the Public Knowledge Project (OJS), and most of the journals focus on rural development, local histories, and indigenous cultures ([Alperin, 2022](#)). Diamond Open Access is the prevailing model among scientific journals, as shown by DOAJ: 13,905 journals charge no APCs, representing more than 60% of those indexed.

In addition to journals portals, the open access ecosystem in Latin America also includes books and other academic publications, primarily hosted on platforms and other academic publications aggregated through institutional and thematic repositories. CLACSO brings together 2,358 open access publications from the CLACSO Centers, and its virtual library offers 200,000 full-text open access resources, primarily books. AmeliCA Libros, for its part, has 1,389 publications.

Additionally, LA Referencia comprises 12 national nodes: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador, El Salvador, Spain, Mexico, Panama, Peru, and Uruguay, with a total of 5,327,299 documents, including articles, books, book chapters, reports, doctoral and master's theses, technical reports, and datasets.

This landscape is also aligned with international recommendations for assessing scientific output through criteria that value openness and the potential social impact of research. A case in point is the Latin American Forum on Scientific Evaluation (FOLEC), which demonstrates how open science must be a central component of current academic policies and evaluations. This promotes the quality and accessibility of the publication network in Latin America.

Platforms

Scientific Information System Redalyc

Redalyc, based in Mexico and supported by the Autonomous University of the State of Mexico (UAEM), began in 2003 as an Open Access (OA) journal index and hosting platform for both scientific journals published in Latin America, the Caribbean, Spain and Portugal. However, in 2018 Redalyc decided not to limit the geographic scope to Latin America but to extend its services to any journal as long as it meets the criteria, which include the condition of Diamond Open Access (non-APC).

Currently, the infrastructure offers services, including automatic editorial workflow technology, to more than 1,700 Diamond OA Journals published by 817 institutions from 36 countries. A factsheet for Redalyc is provided in Table 12

URL	https://www.redalyc.org/
Responsible organisation(s)	Autonomous University of the State of Mexico Consolidated Academic Body "Diffusion and Dissemination of Science" "UAEM-CA-77"

Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	1727 Diamond OA journals
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Immediate Open Access Policy, No article processing charges (APC), The publishing institution is a non-profit scholarly, research, scientific university or organization, Scholarly peer review, the journal has its articles tagged in XML JATS format, the journal provides users with more than one electronic format to read the published articles: PDF, ePUB, HTML, XML, XML JATS, continuous quality assurance.
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● journal quality assessment and certification, full-text indexing (Index of Certified Journals Redalyc), ● scholarly content discovery services, ● open publishing tools, ● an AI-based tool to automate the XML JATS markup process, automatically generating various formats like PDF, ePUB, HTML, and interactive article readers, training is also provided to ensure effective use of the tool.; ● OJS journal content integration; ● interoperability services as OAI-PMH, RDF and semantics, Linked Open Data; ● metrics based on co-authorship, usage and internationalization; ● OJS community of users and developers; ● the registry of journal Open Access archiving policies (Aura) ● journal editors training, ● Redalyc-ORCID integration.
Year of establishment	2003
Business model for service provision	<p>Non-profit scholarly project.</p> <p>All Redalyc services are provided to academic institutions, countries, authors and journals at no cost.</p> <p>The materials are cost-free for the end user.</p> <p>Users can read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles and use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself.</p>

	<p>Material in Redalyc.org may be used for educational, informative and cultural purposes as long as the source is cited and not for commercial purposes.</p> <p>Redalyc has the permission of editors and/or those responsible in journals included in its collection to unrestrictedly disseminate their full-text contents and connect with directories, databases and other systems to link the information to the files contained in its collection.</p> <p>Licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0)</p>
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	<p>Redalyc has been sustained with public resources. The main funding source has been the Autonomous University of the State of Mexico.</p> <p>Different mechanisms have been used for funding, varying from institutional budget, government project grants, research project grants or academic agreements.</p>
Interface language	<p>Spanish and English. Journals are published in a total of 27 languages.</p>
Links for more information	<p>https://www.redalyc.org/home.oa</p> <p>https://www.redalyc.org/redalyc/acerca-de/mision.html</p>

Table 12 - Redalyc platform factsheet

LA Referencia, Red Latinoamericana y de España para la Ciencia Abierta

LA Referencia is a regional network composed of science and technology organizations from the governments of Latin America and Spain, or national initiatives designated by those governments. Its main objective is to promote cooperation agreements on Open Science, understood as a public good, among the member countries of LA Referencia and between LA Referencia and the rest of the countries.

Member countries, Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Spain, Panama, Peru, and Uruguay are currently part of LA Referencia.

The mission is to coordinate national policies and actions in open science, with an emphasis on open access to research results, to consolidate an equitable, multilingual, and sustainable public ecosystem of scientific information based on infrastructure and services as regional public goods..

With more than 12 years of continuous development, LA Referencia has built a harvester platform that applies interoperability standards to collect, share, and give visibility to the scientific output of higher education and research institutions across its member countries. While the Network is responsible for maintaining and improving the core software, each partner must keep its national installation up to date. LA Referencia also develops new features and project-specific updates that can be deployed locally. In addition, the platform offers a statistics module based on harvested data, which repositories may install at their own responsibility. Building on this infrastructure, the Network is advancing several strategic projects, some of which are presented below as examples.

- **dARK.** a decentralized service for affordable unique identifiers (similar to DOIs). Its objective is to provide technology so that institutions have persistent identifiers without any payment to third parties. Once released, it will likely operate on shared infrastructure, and each country will need to fund part of the process to manage identifiers.
- **Collaboration with Lyrisis.** A project launched in 2025 to support the adoption of new versions of DSpace in Latin America: DSpace is one of the most widely used repository softwares in the region, and LA Referencia has just begun a project for 2025 that includes the development of some software features and the creation of free training materials.
- **Collaboration with the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and Research Software Alliance (ReSA).** In January 2025, an agreement was negotiated with RDA to create and translate training materials on research data management for Latin America. This project is funded by the Research Data Alliance. A platform factsheet for LA Referencia is provided in Table 13.

URL	https://www.lareferencia.info/es/
Responsible organisation(s)	LA Referencia Responsible organisation(s): Public science and technology agencies (Ministries and National Science and Technology Organizations) of the member countries, together with RedCLARA.

Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	It does not host journals directly, but rather records from institutional and national repositories. LA Referencia does not have an official count of "Diamond OA journals" because its organizational unit is the repositories and metadata of publications.
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	All articles must comply with the standard metadata guidelines distributed by LA Referencia.
Services offered for journals (if any)	<p>Open-source, transferable technology development that allows for savings in development, upgrades, and support for each partner. Also, common roadmaps are identified that facilitate collaborative development tailored to the needs of the countries.</p> <p>Prioritizing non-proprietary standards and development architecture that avoids dependence on proprietary or unique solutions (e.g., at the level of persistent identifiers or technology components).</p> <p>Services that represent economies of scale and can be transferred (e.g., value-added services, distributed statistics, joint proof of concept to determine the viability of a product).</p> <p>Visibility by indexing each country's production collaboratively in other search engines and information retrieval systems.</p>
Software	Software: LA Referencia, through its Technical Team, has developed a free software platform (GPL 3) for data collection that, in addition to supporting the regional network's central node, functions as an aggregator service and national portal for member countries. Its components include LRHarvester, LRProvider, and a service search engine/portal (based on the free software Vufind (http://vufind.org)).
Year of establishment	2012
Business model for service provision	Each public university pays an annual fee of \$14000.

Governance	LA Referencia is composed of a board composed of members appointed by each science and technology organization of the member governments or by initiatives authorized by those governments. The board of members includes a president, a vice president, and four administrative officers.
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Some grants for different initiatives like SCOSS, LYRASIL, OpenAIRE, Research Data Alliance, RESA are contributing with LA Referencia.
Interface language	Spanish
Links for more information	https://www.lareferencia.info/es/institucional/quienes-somos

Table 13 - LA Referencia platform factsheet

Latindex

LATINDEX is an information system and directory of academic publications covering Latin America, the Caribbean, Spain, and Portugal, aimed at promoting the dissemination and access to the region's scientific output. The system was created to provide a reliable tool for researchers, scholars, institutions, and students to locate, consult, and evaluate the quality of scientific publications produced in the region, thereby increasing the visibility of regional research on the international stage.

Among its services, LATINDEX offers a comprehensive and up-to-date catalog of scientific publications, allowing users to access detailed information about journals, articles, and publishers. The system also promotes the evaluation of editorial quality through specific criteria, helping to identify publications with high academic and scientific standards. One of the key benefits of LATINDEX is its capacity to facilitate the indexing of journals in national and international databases, thereby increasing the visibility and reach of regional scientific output. It also provides technical support and guidance to editors and authors to improve their publications' standards, including aspects such as structure, peer review process, and transparency in information dissemination.

The benefits of LATINDEX for Latin America and the world are extensive. It helps strengthen the quality and recognition of regional scientific journals, promoting a greater impact of research produced in Latin American countries. This supports the internationalization of regional science, allowing researchers to access more knowledge and collaborate on joint projects. Additionally, it

helps democratize access to knowledge, as many of the publications are open access, making scientific findings more accessible to the academic community and the public. Finally, LATINDEX encourages regional cooperation among Spanish- and Portuguese-speaking countries, fostering the integration of the scientific community in a concerted effort to improve the quality and dissemination of knowledge in Spanish and Portuguese. A platform factsheet for LATINDEX is provided in Table 14.

URL	https://www.latindex.org/latindex/inicio
Responsible organisation(s)	National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM)
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	3,882 active journals in its Catalog 2.0, of which 1,983 are Diamond Open Access.
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	To be included in the Catalog, a journal must meet the seven mandatory basic features and at least 23 of the remaining features, for a minimum of 30, which represents around 80% compliance.
Services offered for journals (if any)	Directory, Catalog 2.0 and articles search (new service).
Software	Own development + VuFind
Year of establishment	1995
Business model for service provision	Regional cooperation network
Governance	Each institution's members support personal and technological infrastructures to develop the initiative. On the other hand, some grants for different initiatives like SCOSS are contributing with LATINDEX.
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Institutional members

Interface language	Spanish
Links for more information	https://www.latindex.org/latindex/postulacion/postulacionCatalogo

Table 14 - LATINDEX platform factsheet

AmeliCA Open Science for the Common Good

AmeliCA is a collaborative initiative intended to promote and strengthen the development of Open Science from the paradigm of the commons focused on a scientific communication model of a non-profit scholarly nature.

AmeliCA emerged in 2018 with the support of UNESCO, CLACSO, and Redalyc as AmeliCA Open Knowledge in the Latin American region with dozens of member institutions. In 2023, it advances and defines its action spectrum toward Open Science with a broader geographic scope to include other regions from the Global South, such as Africa and Asia. In this new stage, Latin American alliances are consolidated and diversified. Open Science AmeliCA members are non-profit scholarly institutions, government entities, infrastructures, and organizations.⁸⁵

A platform factsheet for AmeliCA is provided in Table 15.

URL	https://amelica.org/
Responsible organisation(s)	UNESCO, CLACSO and Redalyc
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	804 Diamond OA journals
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	The journals adhere to a non-APC Open Access communication model, publishing academic peer-reviewed content. They share the vision of moving beyond the current evaluation of science based on metrics such as the Impact Factor, while promoting the inclusion of local science and linguistic diversity for the common good. They are committed to shifting to digital publishing (tagging of scientific content in AmeliCA XML, supplied with material to that end and regular training).

⁸⁵ <https://amelica.org/index.php/en/about/>

	Each journal is published by a non-profit scholarly, research, scientific university, or organization.
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● journal quality assessment and certification, ● full-text indexing (In Consolidation Journals AmeliCA Index), ● scholarly content discovery services, ● open publishing tools, ● AI-based XML JATS markup software to automate journal production workflow and get automatically different formats like PDF, ePUB, HTML and interactive article readers; ● OJS journal content integration; ● interoperability services as OAI-PMH; RDF and semantics; ● Linked Open Data; ● metrics based on co-authorship, usage and internationalization; ● OJS community of users and developers; ● the registry of journal Open Access archiving policies (Aura) ● journal editors training.
Software	
Year of establishment	2018
Business model for service provision	<p>Non-profit civil association.</p> <p>Collaborative initiative intended to promote and strengthen the development of Open Science from the paradigm of the commons focused on a scientific communication model of a non-profit scholarly nature.</p> <p>All AmeliCA services are provided to academic institutions, countries, authors and journals at no cost.</p> <p>The materials are cost-free for the end user.</p> <p>Users can read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles and use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or</p>

	<p>technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself.</p> <p>Material in AmeliCA may be used for educational, informative and cultural purposes as long as the source is cited and not for commercial purposes.</p> <p>AmeliCA has the permission of editors and/or those responsible in journals included in its collection to unrestrictedly disseminate their full-text contents and connect with directories, databases and other systems to link the information to the files contained in its collection.</p>
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	<p>AmeliCA's sustainability model consists of the cooperation between scholarly, government, and social sectors by means of a membership model along with projects financed by scholarly instances, exemplified by partners such as SCOSS and by strategic grants such as those from the Arcadia Fund.</p>
Interface language	<p>Spanish and English</p>
Links for more information	<p>https://portal.amelica.org/</p> <p>https://amelica.org/index.php/voces/</p> <p>https://amelica.org/index.php/acerca-de/</p> <p>https://aura.amelica.org/</p>

Table 15 - AmeliCA platform factsheet

Portal of Scientific and Academic Journals of the CSUCA Universities

The Central American Higher University Council (CSUCA) is the highest governing authority within the Central American University Confederation. This confederation comprises the public university systems of Central America, the Dominican Republic, and Cuba, along with their respective academic communities. Acting as a collegial body, the CSUCA coordinates and represents the main public higher education institutions in this vast region ([Declaratoria de Ciencia Abierta Del CSUCA, 2022](#)). The portal of Scientific and Academic Journals of the CSUCA Universities is a space for the visibility of the production of our Central American countries. A platform factsheet for CSUCA is provided in Table 16.

URL	https://revistas.csuca.org/
Responsible organisation(s)	Consejo Superior Universitario Centroamericano (CSUCA)
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	216 journals hosted
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Journal portals must allow harvesting via the OAI-PMH protocol.
Services offered for journals (if any)	Space for highlighting the work of Central American countries.
Software	It's Vufind with some settings to the original code.
Year of establishment	2022
Business model for service provision	Hosting and maintenance is provided by the National University of Nicaragua with CSUCA servers.
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Hosting and maintenance is provided by the Universidad Nacional de Nicaragua with CSUCA servers.
Interface language	Spanish and English
Links for more information	https://csuca.org/es/download/declaracion-de-ciencia-a-bierta-del-csuca/

Table 16 - CSUCA platform factsheet

In the Plan for the Regional Integration of Higher Education in Central America and the Dominican Republic (PIRESC), CSUCA has established strategic objective 2.4:

Promote and facilitate access to information and research results and to the knowledge produced by the region's universities, promoting principles, concepts, and methods of open science, giving

it international visibility, and proactively transferring them to society to contribute to the sustainable development of the region's countries (Central American University Council, 2016, pp. 73-74). Among the initiatives it has promoted is the development of the Scientific Journals Portal, a platform built by Universidad Nacional, Nicaragua, using CSUCA servers, which compiles journals from the 28 public universities in the nine Central American and Caribbean countries that make up CSUCA.

This platform gives visibility to all journals that, to date, have been published entirely under the Diamond model. This is consistent with the CSUCA Open Science Declaration, signed by all university rectors, which states in its sixth commitment (p. 6):

"Promote among university communities that their scientific and academic production be published in open access without publishing or reading costs (Diamond model) and that their final version be deposited in the institutional repository (Green model) to implement non-commercial open access. In the case of restrictions on dissemination or distribution, the metadata of said production must be made available and publicly accessible."

Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO)

SciELO (Scientific Electronic Library Online) was founded in Brazil in 1998 as a result of a collaboration between the Latin American and Caribbean Center on Health Sciences Information (BIREME) of the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) and the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP). It is an initiative aimed at promoting electronic publishing, primarily from Latin America, the Caribbean, Spain, and Portugal. SciELO's original objectives were to increase the visibility of journals in the region, improve their quality, and provide access to the full text of their articles ([González & Melero, 2023](#)).

The SciELO Network is the application of the SciELO Program, originally launched by the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP). Its common objectives, methodologies, and technologies are adapted in each country according to its policies, priorities, and conditions to advance research and scientific communication. The collections are developed under the management of national organizations, representative of the research and scientific communication in their respective countries (Cetto, Gamboa, Packer, et al., 2015).

SciELO operates 19 collections, most of which are country-specific, although there is also a thematic collection (Public Health) and the Science and Culture collection. The largest collections are SciELO Brazil, with approximately 45% of all publications. This is followed by SciELO Colombia (9%), and SciELO Mexico and SciELO Chile, which each contribute 8% of the publications. The remaining 30% corresponds to all other collections ([Maricato, Mazoni, Mugnaini, et al., 2023](#)). From 1997 to 2023, over one million articles were published by the journals that make up the network, whereas the SciELO Brazil collection recorded nearly 373,000 ([Garcia, Rode, Packe, et al., 2024](#)). In recent years, SciELO Brazil has incorporated the SciELO Preprints, SciELO Data, and SciELO Books collections.

A platform factsheet for SciELO is provided in Table 17.

Name	SciELO
URL	https://www.scielo.org/en
Responsible organisation(s)	National collections are governed, maintained, managed, and operated autonomously. Each country has only one national coordination and one collection.
Journals hosted (number), of which Diamond OA	1654 journals hosted, with the vast majority being Diamond OA
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Open access to article texts and other types of documents, update their editorial policies and management in accordance with the open science modus operandi including: Expressing alignment with the goals of open science in the public display of the journal's mission, objectives, and scope, specifying alignment with open science practices in the author guidelines; implementing a continuous publication model for articles as soon as they are approved and edited, introducing a checklist for compliance with open science practices during manuscript submission, providing training for the editorial team and reviewers, developing the role of data editors for research data; where feasible, designate an editor responsible for data.
Services offered for journals (if any)	Recognition, promotion, and enhancement of journals published by universities, scientific societies, and professional associations, primarily operated in non-profit contexts.
Software	Based on the SciELO publishing schema, which uses XML (JATS/SGML) to structure journal articles and enable automated conversion into multiple formats (HTML, PDF, EPUB). This system supports the management, publication, indexing and long term preservation of scientific content.

Year of establishment	1998
Business model for service provision	SciELO (Scientific Electronic Library Online) is a program to support open access research communication. International Cooperation Program for Open Access Scientific Communication.
Funding streams and sustainability strategies	Sustained by public institutional funding from national research agencies, universities, and scientific societies, complemented by in-kind contributions for technical and editorial operations. Also implements Contributions to the Cost of Publications (CCPs) to partially recover publications costs and support long-term sustainability as non-profit open science infrastructure.
Interface language	Portuguese, English and Spanish
Links for more information	https://www.scielo.org/en/about-scielo/program-publication-model-and-scielo-network/

Table 17 - SciELO platform factsheet

In 2023, it celebrated its 25th anniversary and reaffirmed its communication model through a declaration of support for Open Science with IDEA ([SciELO Network, 2023a](#)). It also signed the "Declaration on the use of Contributions to the Cost of Publications (CCPs) in the SciELO Network", which proposed a specific charge to cover partial or total publication costs ([SciELO Network, 2023b](#)). The network's collection coordinators agreed align with UNESCO's recommendation on open science, contribute to the progress of global open access in its various forms, and maximize the impact of open science, among other considerations ([SciELO Network, 2023a](#)). SciELO's internationalization strategy has been primarily based on the systematic adoption of English or Spanish in most of its journals and the evaluation of scientific performance based on citation and the Impact Factor.

The SciELO Brazil collection's leadership established an expected proportion of articles in English, the international affiliation of authors, and foreign researchers in the editorial management bodies according to thematic areas; the option to publish simultaneously in two or more languages was suggested ([Packer, 2024](#)).

Since 2014, the collections in the SciELO Network are indexed in the SciELO Citation Index, a regional collection restricted only to users or institutions with a paid subscription model of the company Clarivate Analytics ([González & Melero, 2023](#)). SciELO Brazil manages all the metadata

sources that are used to supply this index, which currently covers 1,466 journals and contains over 1 million (1m+) records. The objective is to aim for greater visibility and better access to research, and to operate the indexing of SciELO journals, particularly the citation count in the SciELO Network and on Clarivate’s platform ([Packer, 2014](#)). Another key aspect of the SCIELO CI’s importance is its future as an evaluation tool, provided its utility is contrasted and any potential biases are eliminated ([Repiso, Jiménez-Contreras & Aguaded, 2017](#)). It is important to note that the decision regarding the inclusion and permanence of journals in the SciELO Network is made by national scientific committees and not by citation indicators.

SciELO has made significant progress in improving the quality and reach of academic publications in the region. This is achieved by enhancing the professionalism of its output, ensuring the quality and speed of manuscript evaluation, managing more affordable publication costs, and, crucially, increasing its international presence and visibility (Cetto, Gamboa, Packer, et al., 2015).

Output types

Journal articles

DOAJ

In 2021, a study of production in DOAJ analyzed the trends of the Gold and Diamond models over the 2014–2019 period. The study defined Gold as the model with an Article Processing Charge (APC), and Diamond as the model free of charges for both authors and readers ([Aguado López, 2021](#)).

Analyzing only Diamond-level publishing, Latin America scientific output accounts for 25.9% of total production. In contrast, its share of Gold OA publishing is significantly lower, reaching only 3.4% of total production (Figure 3). According to the data analyzed in DOAJ, the APC publication model is not its main publication route which emphasizes the region’s strength in Diamond OA publishing.

Figure 3- Distribution of scholarly articles in DOAJ-indexed journals 2014-2019: Diamond OA and Gold-APC. Source: Adapted from [Aquado López, E. \(2021\)](#).

Latindex

Latindex lists 15,188 online journals, of which 3,983 are in the 2.0 catalog, which refers to online journals with information visible and searchable on the official website of each journal, making this resource a reliable reference for high-quality journals. Latindex is an essential tool for identifying the diversity and quality of the region's publishing output.

Latindex offers three information products ([Sistema Latindex, 2025a](#)):

DIRECTORY. This database records the existence of print and online academic journals published in Ibero-American countries. It currently contains a total of 28,574 print and online journals.

CATALOGUE 2.0. A compilation of journals that meet quality standards according to the Latindex methodology.⁸⁶ It currently contains 3,988 journals.

CATALOGUE 2.0 ITEMS. This allows access to full-text articles and documents published in journals included in the Latindex Catalog 2.0. A basic search is offered, displaying the document title, abstract, and journal title. It currently contains 636,460 articles.

The number of journals per country that have been added to their 2.0 catalog is shown in Table 18 ([Sistema Latindex, 2025b](#)):

Country	Journals
Argentina	554
Bolivia	17
Brazil	384
Chile	221
Colombia	147
Costa Rica	105
Cuba	83
Dominican Republic	15
Ecuador	371

⁸⁶ <https://www.latindex.org/latindex/postulacion/postulacionCatalogo>

El Salvador	14
Guatemala	21
Honduras	11
Iberoamericanists - North America	28
Iberoamericanists - Asia	2
Iberoamericanists - Eurasia	1
Iberoamericanists - Europe	64
Iberoamericanists - Africa	1
Mexico	410
Nicaragua	23
International Organizations	6
Panama	40
Paraguay	22
Peru	270
Portugal	68
Puerto Rico	10
Spain	1008
Uruguay	59
Venezuela	33

Table 18 - Distribution of Scientific Journals in the Latindex 2.0 Catalog (2025). Source: Adapted from Indicators Catalog 2.0, by [Sistema Latindex \(2025b\)](#).

Redalyc

Redalyc currently hosts 1,784 journals from 36 countries (from 828 institutions), totaling 750,155 articles.

A study conducted in 2024 analyzed 692,173 articles from 1,581 journals (1,327 of which are from Latin America), identifying 1,788,539 author forms and 40,764 institutional affiliations from 182 countries ([Becerril-García, 2024](#)).

The journals indexed in Redalyc demonstrate a significant global reach. The collection of 1,581 journals, published in 31 countries, received articles written by authors from 182 different countries, who benefit from publishing without APCs. The following map shows this interaction between authors (red dots) and countries of publication (blue dots). (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Map of countries of authors (red dots) and countries of publication (blue dots) in Diamond OA journals indexed by Redalyc (2023). Source: Adapted from [Becerril-García \(2024\)](#).

A closer analysis of the flow of articles from countries of authors to countries of publication reveals a strong concentration of scientific production: Brazil concentrates 33.48% out of the total, i.e., 598,838; Mexico 14.65% (262,018); Colombia 10.54% (188,513) and Spain 9.87% (176,586).

The weight of countries in terms of journal publication is also shown in the right column of Figure 5. The journals published in Brazil concentrate 30.53% of the total number of papers of the study (211,322), Mexican journals publish 16.34% (113,087 papers) and the Colombian ones 14.54% (100,658 papers).

Figure 5 - Flow of articles between article affiliation countries and countries of journal publishers (2023). Source: Adapted from [Becerril-García \(2024\)](#).

OLIVA 1.0

The Latin American Observatory of Evaluation Indicators (OLIVA) operates within the Center for Knowledge Circulation Studies of the Faculty of Political and Social Sciences at the National University of Cuyo, Argentina. It is home to projects led by researchers from CONICET, fellows, professors and students of the University, and participants from other Latin American countries and the rest of the world.

The Observatory is a regional, collaborative, and interdisciplinary undertaking that seeks to reverse the difficulties that exist in making visible and valuing the production published in Latin America and the Caribbean ([Fernández & Pascual, 2022](#)).

In 2022, the OLIVA 1.0 project was launched in collaboration with CLACSO, Redalyc, and SciELO. This project presented a consolidated, non-overlapping database containing various types of data from journals indexed in Redalyc and SciELO, with a total of 1,720 journals, 908,982 documents, and 2,802,295 authors, published between 1909 and 2019 ([Beigel, Packer, Gallardo, et al., 2024](#)).

The basic data of the database are shown in Table 19.

Publisher's country	Journals	Documents	Documents authors	Articles	Articles authors
Brazil	506	444.332	1.579011	396.293	1.476.492
Colombia	291	102.762	241.335	90.530	224.630
Mexico	283	120.475	299.471	100.355	273.002
Argentina	167	46.237	121.052	35.919	104.093
Chile	144	69.095	199.308	57.032	178.521
Venezuela	97	34.939	92.097	30.161	85.814
Cuba	82	46.052	160.371	41.621	149.736
Costa Rica	48	16.313	35.322	14.816	33.199
Peru	37	13.902	40.558	11.773	37.066
Uruguay	25	4.756	14.914	3.680	12.866
Bolivia	22	4.491	10.080	3.629	8.767
Ecuador	11	3.440	5.631	2.877	5.002
Puerto Rico	5	1.253	1841	816	1.382
Panama	1	408	427	333	341
Dominican Republic	1	527	877	469	793
Total	1.720	908.982	2.802.295	790.304	2.591.704

Table 19. Scientific Output Indicators by Publisher's Country: Data from the OLIVA Project (1995-2018). Source: Adapted from [Beigel, Packer, Gallardo, et al. \(2024\)](#).

The authors of the OLIVA corpus identified two key aspects of scientific communication in the in the main findings: its diversity (thematic and linguistic) and collaboration (international and inter-institutional/national), which challenges the traditional separation between "mainstream or global" and "regional or local" circuits.

Repositories

In the Latin American context, university repositories primarily offer open access to full-text publications and journal collections, and have recently begun the process of offering open access to research data, moving towards the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) as a guide. University digital repositories represent the institutions' response to policies and legislation mandating open access to publications and data derived from publicly funded research.

LA Referencia

These repositories are part of national science systems and are instrumental to the network of repositories in Ibero-American countries known as LA Referencia. They have been the university response to the policies and legislations, serving as the key instrument to guarantee compliance with mandates of transparency and access to scientific output along with research data ([Rovelli, Babini & Vommaro, 2021](#)).

Its addition of documents from multiple countries demonstrates regional cooperation and metadata standardization, facilitating interoperability and global visibility. This network, as a representation of the repository system, is the source with the highest number of open access records available in the region ([Lautaro, Mora-Campos, Barrere, et al., 2023](#)).

In 2023, representatives from its country nodes were consulted, as well as leaders of Open Science in non-member countries and in National Science and Technology Organizations or other government bodies, to ascertain the possibilities for repositories' geographical coverage extending beyond the LA Referencia network. The results show the repositories by country and type (Table 20). Peru leads with 192 repositories of scientific literature, followed by Mexico (135), Colombia (130), and Brazil (119). Brazil stands out with 14 data repositories, followed by Mexico (5) and Colombia (4). Argentina has 12 mixed repositories, as does the Dominican Republic, while Mexico (4) and Brazil (3) show lower figures ([Lautaro, Mora-Campos, Barrere, et al., 2023](#)).

Country	Scientific literature repositories	Data repositories	Mixed repositories
Peru	192	0	0
Mexico	135	5	4

Colombia	130	4	#
Brazil	119	14	3
Spain	113	2	37
Argentina	77	1	12
Ecuador	56	1	0
Cuba	16	0	0
Nicaragua	15	0	0
El Salvador	11	0	0
Uruguay	9	0	0
Costa Rica	8	0	1
Panama	8	0	0
Dominican Republic	0	0	12
Guatemala	1	0	1
Honduras	1	0	0
Puerto Rico	1	0	0

Table 20 - Institutional repositories by type and country in Ibero-America (2023). Source: Adapted from [Lautaro, Mora-Campos, Barrere, et al. \(2023\)](#).

Data sourced from LA Referencia (as of July 2023) reveals over 4.5 million metadata records of scientific output (articles, reports, doctoral and master's theses, books, book chapters, and datasets) harvested by the regional aggregator from its 12 national nodes (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Spain, El Salvador, Mexico, Panama, Peru, and Uruguay).

Figure CD shows the evolution of the collected metadata over time, segmented by document type. This reflects the maturity of the regional repository infrastructure and a growing commitment to the visibility of scientific output.

Figure CD - Evolution of Collected Metadata by Document Type in LA Referencia (2023). Source: Adapted from [Lautaro, Mora-Campos, Barrere, et al. \(2023\)](#).

In terms of content, it is important to note that scientific articles predominate, while theses (doctoral and master's) and book chapters appear in small but consistent proportions. Books and datasets are minimal, which reflects a low integration of research data and monographs into the repositories.

Books

A 2024 study examined the production of academic books in 16 Spanish-speaking Latin American countries between 2013 and 2019, using ISBN databases provided to CERLALC, to characterize the academic publishing sector ([Giraldo-González, Giménez-Toledo & Córdoba-Restrepo, et al., 2024](#)). All results displayed here are sourced from this study.

The main findings highlight the significant output from Mexico, Argentina, and Colombia. In addition to geographic and thematic distribution, the research detailed editorial characteristics of the output, such as format (physical or digital), commercial offerings, average page count, print run, and the number of translations.

The book production landscape, based on ISBN applications, is presented in Figure CW. Key results highlight a sustained publishing production in the region, a notable increase in self-published authors—from 11,651 in 2013 to 16,180 in 2019 (an approximate 39% rise)—and a trend toward greater publishing autonomy.

Figure CW - Landscape of Book Production by ISBN Applications in Latin America (2013-2019). Source: Adapted from [Giraldo-González, Giménez-Toledo & Córdoba-Restrepo, et al. \(2024\)](#).

Over the seven-year period, 747,537 ISBNs were registered in the region (Table 21). The vast majority, 87% (651,539), were requested by publishers, while 13% (95,998) came from author-publishers.

Agent	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2013-2019	%
Publishers	93.561	92.595	92.608	92.462	92.488	96.780	91.045	651.539	87%
Self-published authors	11.651	12.063	13.636	13.687	14.057	14.724	16.180	95.998	13%
Total	105.212	104.658	106.244	106.149	106.545	111.504	107.225	747.537	100%

Table 21 - ISBN Registrations in Latin America by Requesting Agent (2013-2019). Source: Adapted from [Giraldo-González, Giménez-Toledo & Córdoba-Restrepo, et al. \(2024\)](#).

The individual country analyses (Table 22) identify stable publishing production in countries such as Mexico, Argentina and Colombia, contrasting with significant declines in Venezuela, Panama and Honduras.

Mexico and Argentina hold a commanding position in the region's book production, accounting for more than 50% of the total output. Regarding author-publishers, Mexico registers a low participation rate (5%), significantly lower than Argentina's (16%). Colombia is the third country with the highest number of ISBNs issued, where 13% of registrations come from author-publishers.

Adding the registrations from these three main countries (Mexico, Argentina, and Colombia), they represent 69% of all ISBNs issued in the study. If Peru and Chile are included, this proportion rises significantly to 84%. The publishing systems of these countries could serve as a benchmark for other regions to strengthen their book publishing output.

Country	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Mexico	29464	29525	29895	27943	26418	27635	25653
Argentina	27754	27643	28803	27702	28352	27754	27668
Colombia	16046	15900	17621	17836	18485	20867	19922
Chile	5946	5700	6267	7232	8015	8152	7204
Peru	6756	6152	6093	6463	6742	7111	8157
Ecuador	3401	3854	3992	4727	4596	4744	4768
Venezuela	3579	3199	3334	3118	2729	2275	1853
Uruguay	2049	2054	2080	2097	2230	3231	2336
Costa Rica	1826	1596	1449	1951	1876	2158	1807
Dominican Republic	1372	1652	1646	1487	1568	1866	1502
Guatemala	1172	1197	1248	959	1045	1137	1421
Paraguay	842	698	863	867	869	1007	1188
Bolivia	1140	1275	1304	1403	1474	1578	1643
Panama	2867	2974	972	1229	882	940	974
El Salvador	651	734	677	667	727	661	703
Honduras	347	505	468	537	387	384	62

Table 22 - Distribution of Total ISBN Registrations, by Country (2013–2019). Source: Adapted from [Giraldo-González, Giménez-Toledo & Córdoba-Restrepo, et al. \(2024\)](#).

Almost half (46%) of the ISBNs registered in the region correspond to academic publications (Table 23). The countries with the highest proportion of academic publications are Mexico (60%), Colombia (58%), the Dominican Republic (53%), Guatemala (53%), and Paraguay (51%).

Country	Total	Academic	Percentage
Mexico	196.533	117.929	60%
Colombia	126.677	73.772	58%

Argentina	195.676	61.102	31%
Peru	47.474	19.740	42%
Chile	48.516	17.764	37%
Ecuador	30.082	13.595	45%
Venezuela	20.087	8.439	42%
Uruguay	16.077	6.258	39%
Costa Rica	12.663	6.130	48%
Dominican Republic	11.093	5.910	53%
Guatemala	8.179	4.316	53%
Paraguay	6.334	3.223	51%
Bolivia	9.817	3.183	32%
Panama	10.838	2.531	23%
El Salvador	4.820	2.074	43%
Honduras	2.671	919	34%
Total	747.537	346.885	46%

Table 23 - Academic Book Production as a Percentage of Total ISBNs, by Country (2013–2019).
Source: Adapted from [Giraldo-González, Giménez-Toledo & Córdoba-Restrepo, et al. \(2024\)](#).

Of the 346,885 academic ISBNs issued, 62% (214,142) correspond to commercially available works, while the remaining 116,999 (38%) are non-commercial works. Additionally, a significant percentage drop was observed in the production of marketable books in the region, falling from 71% in 2015 to only 53% in 2019. Figure 5 provides a visualisation of this development.

Figure 5 - Academic ISBNs issued (2013-2019). Source: Adapted from [Giraldo-González, Giménez-Toledo & Córdoba-Restrepo, et al. \(2024\)](#).

However, open access initiatives demonstrate a commitment to knowledge sharing in the region, since their creation:

- CLACSO brings together 2,358 open access publications from the CLACSO Centers,⁸⁷ and its virtual library⁸⁸ offers 200,000 full-text open access resources, primarily books.
- AmeliCA Libros,⁸⁹ for its part, has 1,389 publications.
- And SciELO Books⁹⁰ contributes with 1,468 open access titles and 19,603 open access chapters.

CLACSO Books

CLACSO Books is a platform belonging to the Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO), an institutional network that promotes open access to academic production in the social sciences and humanities in Latin America and the Caribbean. The platform offers a virtual library and a digital bookstore with free, open, and unrestricted access to thousands of books, documents, and academic publications, promoting the democratization of knowledge and countering the monetization of publicly funded scientific production. Only a small percentage of books are available in print, and the majority are published and downloaded in open digital format.

Amelica Book collection

⁸⁷ <https://libreriacentros.clacso.org/>

⁸⁸ <https://biblioteca-repositorio.clacso.edu.ar/>

⁸⁹ <https://portal.amelica.org/coleccionLibros.oa>

⁹⁰ <https://books.scielo.org>

The Amelica Book collection is part of AmeliCA, a cooperative infrastructure for scholarly communication and open science focused on non-profit publishing models and seeking to preserve the open and scholarly nature of scientific knowledge. This initiative is led by UNESCO, CLACSO, Redalyc, and universities. AmeliCA promotes open access to books and journals, encouraging the dissemination of scientific knowledge, especially in Latin America and the Global South, with a focus on sustainability, equity, and the protection of knowledge as a common good.

AmeliCA acts as a non-profit centralized harvesting and visibility platform and ensures collections must meet the technical and editorial standards to be included. The books are published by the participating academic institutions and university presses. Specifically, books must be academic in nature, have an open license, and their metadata must be housed in a publicly accessible repository that implements the OAI-PMH protocol. The automated harvesting done by AmeliCA Books inclusion will be limited solely to the book records, excluding any other type of academic production. As a Diamond Open Access initiative, it ensures content is free for both readers and authors.

SciELO Books

The SciELO Books Portal publishes national and thematic collections of academic books online with the objective of maximizing the visibility, accessibility, use and impact of the research results, essays and studies that are published in them. The SciELO Books Network interoperates and shares goals, resources, methodologies and technologies with the SciELO Journals Network. SciELO Books is part of the SciELO Program of FAPESP. The methodology and the technological platform of SciELO Books was developed with the technical cooperation of BIREME/PAHO/WHO and its execution is supported by the Fundação de Apoio à Universidade Federal de São Paulo ([SciELO, 2017](#)).

Preprints

SciELO Preprints is a platform that allows authors to publish complete preliminary versions of their scientific manuscripts prior to peer review. These manuscripts contain comprehensive information, data, and methodologies, and are therefore quickly published in open access to facilitate the rapid and complete dissemination of the analysis and findings regarding the results ([Trujillo, 2023](#)). SciELO Preprints is part of the SciELO Network. The platform makes use of the Public Knowledge Project's Open Preprint Systems (OPS) and focuses on maintaining integration with other international servers while addressing the specificities of Latin America, such as multilingualism and the local relevance of research. In this region, SciELO Preprints also helps avoid the fragmentation of scholarly communication and facilitates cooperation between journals and institutions ([Packer, Santos & Meneghini, 2017](#)).

Between 2020 and 2024, SciELO Preprints accepted 3,683 manuscripts with an acceptance rate of 65%, which means a rate of 735 preprints annually. The majority of these preprints originated in Brazil (79%) and were written in Portuguese (67%), followed by Spanish (17%) and English (16%). In

terms of accesses, Life Sciences had the highest number per preprint (2,250), surpassing Humanities (1,225) and Physical Sciences (835) ([Packer, 2025](#)).

Organisational structures & Governance models

In 2020, Redalyc and AmeliCA, as part of the activities of the CLACSO Working Group “Open Knowledge as a Common Good” and the “Invest in Open Infrastructure” group, coordinated a survey of open access journals, which was answered by 1109 journals (85% from Latin America). The publishing institutions of the participating journals were classified into the following groups: universities, academic associations/societies, educational institutions, private organizations, research institutions, governmental organizations, foundations, international bodies, and hospitals. The main results ([Becerril-Garcia, 2021](#)) regarding the organisation of publishing show that:

- 70.3% of the journals are published by universities, in contrast to 3.7% by private organizations and 2.4% by governmental organizations.
- The academic sector stands out as the driving force and support for regional academic publication, representing 92.4% of publishers (including academic associations/societies).
- Both private initiatives (5%) and the government (2.6%) play a marginal role as journal publishers.
- 76.9% of the 1,145 journals that participated in the survey define themselves as institutional projects.
- Other classifications include non-profit foundations (8%), civil associations (6.9%), and other organisations (8.2%).
- Decision-making processes involve and are distributed among different parties, such as the publishing institution, the editorial board, and the journal's directors.
- The publishing institution plays a notable role in decisions regarding economic matters: 49.5% of the responding journals (556 journals) indicated that their publishing institution participates in these types of decisions.
- 78.2% of the journals that answered this question included the editorial board as a participant in editorial decisions.

The full breakdown of these results are provided in Table 23 and Figure 6.

Publishing institution category	Percentage
Universities	70.3%
Academic associations or societies	11.6%
Educational institutions	6.6%
Private organizations	3.7%
Research institutions	3.2%

Governmental organizations	2.4%
Foundations	1.3%
International organizations	0.3%
Hospitals	0.2%
Other	0.2%
Anonymous	0.1%
No institution listed	0.1%

Table 23 - Types of publishing institutions of participating journals. *Source:* Adapted from [Becerril-Garcia\(2021\)](#).

Figure 6 - Decision-making among parties. *Source:* Adapted from [Becerril-Garcia\(2021\)](#).

The dominant role of the academic sector as owner and publisher of scientific journals is highlighted. In addition, publication governance places both economic and editorial decisions in the hands of the publishing institution. These findings demonstrate that academia controls and defines scientific publishing: its present and future are in the hands of the academic community.

To complement this analysis, the results of a 2024 study of Latin American journals indexed in Redalyc are presented in Figures 6, 7, 8 and 9 ([Becerril-García, 2024](#)). This study finds that

publications not only function as public goods—due to their non-excludable and non-rivalrous nature—but also reinforce academic control over their financial and editorial management.

- 93% of all journals are published by academic institutions, followed by government organizations (4.1%). The private sector (2.1%) comprises foundations, commercial publishers, non-profit publishers, and businesses or other companies.
- Within the academic sector, universities are the strongest player, publishing 993 journals (74.8%).
- They are followed by academic associations with 182 journals (13.7%), research centers (2.5%) and colleges (2%).
- The majority of journals (68.3% or 907 journals) are published by public institutions, while private organizations, including all private academic institutions and organizations with private legal status, publish 31%.
- In Chile, Peru, and Colombia, the strong participation of private higher education and research institutions stands out.
- In Uruguay, Argentina, Brazil, Peru, and Mexico, the participation of academic associations as publishers is notable.
- Cuba presents a more diversified participation from different sectors, with a significant contribution from the government and health sectors.

Figure 7 - Proportional chart of publisher institutions of Diamond OA journals indexed in Redalyc (2023). Source: Adapted from [Becerril-García \(2024\)](#).

Figure 8 - Diamond OA journals' publisher institutions by legal status of journals indexed in Redalyc (2023). Source: Adapted from [Becerril-García \(2024\)](#).

Figure 9 - Sectoral classification of Diamond OA journal publishers indexed by Redalyc. Breakdown by country (2023). Source: Adapted from [Becerril-García \(2024\)](#).

Figure 10 - Nature of Diamond OA journal publishers. Breakdown by country (2023). Source: Adapted from [Becerril-García \(2024\)](#).

Funding mechanisms

Latin America maintains academic control over scientific publishing, championing a model of publication that is free for both readers and authors, primarily funded by public institutions. Funding mechanisms focus mainly on integrating costs into existing structures, utilizing public funds, and employing competitive calls for proposals, all within a framework of strong

inter-institutional cooperation. Crucially, the sustainability of this model relies on the consolidation and use of open infrastructures.

The primary source of funding is public universities, which serve as the core of the model. These institutions typically cover the costs of technological infrastructure (such as servers, OJS support, and DOI registration), editing, and digital preservation using their institutional resources or academic budgets, as seen in countries like Colombia, Ecuador, Costa Rica, Nicaragua, Panama, and Mexico. A crucial strategy is integrating publishing costs directly into budgets allocated to research and university outreach.

Additionally, Science and Technology Agencies play a key role through various mechanisms. In Argentina, CONICET and universities allocate human and technical resources through their Science and Technology departments.

Agencies such as ANID in Chile and SENACYT in Panama provide support through competitive calls for proposals, although this funding is often sporadic. In Brazil, CAPES allocates financial resources to the SciELO Brasil program to enhance its international visibility, while in Chile, and manages the SciELO Chile platform. Other countries, such as Cuba, utilize the National System of Science and Technology Programs and Projects or the Annual Science and Technology Plan to obtain financial support for quality assurance processes and to cover publication costs.

Finally, cooperation and the use of regional networks serve as a mechanism for sustainability and technical support. Participation in academic infrastructures such as SciELO, Latindex, Redalyc, and AmeliCA allows for the sharing of technological infrastructure, access to technical support, and increased visibility. The creation of inter-university consortia facilitates the exchange of human and technical resources.

International cooperation and multilateral funds are also crucial for the sustainability of organizations such as UNESCO and CSUCA. To address the lack of a permanent funding mechanism, future trends include efforts to establish permanent and exclusive competitive national funds for Diamond Open Access journals, as is being pursued in Peru, Nicaragua, and Paraguay, for example.

The Latin American context exemplifies the preponderance of public funding in the dynamics of Research and Development (R&D). Specifically, the public sector is the main source of capital, representing 56% of total R&D investment in the region. In contrast, the private sector's participation is lower, accounting for only 36% of total funding. This structure is a distinctive characteristic of Latin American countries, as it differs from the model prevalent in more developed nations, where investment from the private sector exceeds that of the government. Regarding the resource allocation sector, academia plays a dominant role. Higher education institutions manage the largest percentage of spending, accounting for 42% of R&D funds. This is then distributed among businesses, which use 31%, and the public sector itself, with 26% ([Becerril-García, 2024](#)).

The main results from the survey of open access journals ([Becerril-Garcia, 2021](#)), which received responses from 1,145 journals, show that:

- 70.2% of journals receive funding from the academic sector (54.6% from public universities and 15.6% from private universities).
- An analysis of the contribution of funding sources to journal sustainability shows that funding from public universities accounts on average for 93.1% of the journal's total budget.
- 7.7% of journals reported receiving contributions from government organizations, and these contributions represent, on average, 70.2% of their income.
- A small percentage of journals (2.2%) report receiving funding from private companies; however, this contribution represents, on average, 77.3% of the budget for the journals in this category.
- Almost a quarter of the journals surveyed (23.8%) mentioned receiving funding from other sources, mainly academic associations, trade organizations or the editors' own resources, in which case the income corresponds to 88.5% of the journals' budgets.

The financial resources available to the scientific journals that participated in this analysis allow most of them to cover tasks such as editorial management and electronic publishing:

- 49.3% of journals indicate that their budget allows them to acquire DOI identifiers;
- 34.7% include XML markup within their budget.
- Other activities include: copyediting, translations, costs related to the journal's website, anti-plagiarism software, distribution of the print version, and legal matters.
- Among the activities that journals cannot cover with their budgets are: resources for academic events, publication of articles in formats other than PDF, visibility, dissemination, training of the editorial team, improvement of websites and activities related to indexing in databases

Regarding the outsourcing of services by journals, it was found that from the 1,145 journals surveyed, a total of 712 journals (62.% of the total) outsource at least one process. Using these 712 journals as the 100% base:

- Half of these journals outsource subcontract article layout.
- 38.8% journals outsource translation tasks.
- 35.3% outsource XML markup.
- 33% journals allocate 50% or more of their budget to cover this outsourcing.

The journals' policy regarding the adoption of APC shows that:

- The surveyed journals are self-sustaining, with only 4.2% mentioning charging this fee.
- These journals charge an average of USD 196.
- 77.6% charge for publishing the article once it is accepted, 2% for submitting the article for review, and 20.4% for other tasks such as translation, document formatting, DOI acquisition, or IT services.
- The adoption of this business model is recent; 77% of the journals that charge APCs adopted this sustainability model in the last decade.

Solutions and services

Within the Open Science landscape, a sample of robust infrastructures was selected from the following types: infrastructures for open access publications (scientific journals and books), infrastructures for repositories, research infrastructures, CRIS infrastructures, and open data infrastructures. The selected infrastructures are listed in Table 24, a summary table of the observed aspects, in accordance with the considerations outlined in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, is included ([Becerril-Garcia, 2021](#)).

Infrastructure	Type	Use of PIDs	Open & Standardized Services	Interoperability	Content Reusable by People and Machines	Non-profit	Permanent Access ⁹¹	Unrestricted Access ⁹²
DOAJ	Open Access Journal Directory	DOI for articles	✓	✓	Full-text content of articles is not hosted in DOAJ, only metadata.	✓	✓	✓
OpenEdition	Open Access Journals, Books, and other outputs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Redalyc	Open Access Journals	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

⁹¹ The commitment to the long-term preservation and durability of scientific outputs.

⁹² Providing access to scientific outputs that is free of charge to the user (no paywalls) and accompanied by minimal legal and technical barriers.

D.1.1 Scoping Report on Non-for-Profit Publishing Ecosystems

Erudit	Open Access Journals, Books, and other outputs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
SciELO	Open Access Journals, Books, and other outputs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Latindex	Open Access Journal Directory	No full-text content of articles, as it is a directory	✓	✓	No full-text content of articles, as it is a directory	✓	✓	✓

D.1.1 Scoping Report on Non-for-Profit Publishing Ecosystems

DOAB	Open Access Books	✓	✓	✓	No full-text content of books, only at the metadata level	✓	✓	✓
OAPEN	Open Access Books	✓	✓	✓	Files are requested in PDF and ePUB	✓	✓	✓
African Open Science Platform (AOSP)	Research Support	A federated infrastructure with diverse services	✓	A federated infrastructure with diverse services	A federated infrastructure with diverse services	✓	✓	✓
LA Referencia	Repository Network	✓	✓	✓	Full-text content is found in the repositories it aggregates	✓	✓	✓
OpenAIRE	Repository Network	✓	✓	✓	Full-text content is found at the original sources	✓	✓	✓
OPERAS	Research	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

D.1.1 Scoping Report on Non-for-Profit Publishing Ecosystems

	Support							
EuroCRIS	CRIS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
EOSC	Research Support and Open Data				Federated environment, diverse information sources	Tripartite Governance: European Commission, EOSC Association, EOSC Steering Board		
OpenCitations	Open Data	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
AmeliCA	Research Support and Open Science	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 24 - Open Science infrastructures. Source: Table elaborated based on [Becerril García \(2023\)](#).

This analysis shows a picture of significant progress in the region, marked by the consolidation of the following services:

- The vast majority of infrastructures already adopt persistent identifiers for their content (articles, books, etc.).
- Almost all infrastructures use structured language for their content, such as XML.
- The services they offer are open and in many infrastructures are standardized (at the internal level of each infrastructure).
- Interoperability is a common practice among infrastructures.
- The vast majority of organizations define themselves as non-profit.
- They offer permanent and unrestricted access to their services.
- They have consolidated their position on the international stage, growing in innovative, stable and long-range services.

Additionally, the following areas of opportunity are identified:

- It is not yet common practice to use PIDs as identifiers for institutions, funders, authors.
- Very few infrastructures offer structured language formats (such as XML) available for download on their platforms.
- Although interoperability is common, standardization is not cross-cutting across all infrastructures.
- Despite using formats such as XML, TEI, and JSON, there is a lack of shared vocabularies, standards, and community norms to enable inter-infrastructure cooperation and optimize machine readability.
- There is fragmentation in the ecosystem: the infrastructures interoperate with some similar ones, but there is no connected ecosystem that maximizes the efficiency and benefit of the services.
- Differences in legal constitutions (academic, governmental, independent) may impact the course of infrastructures and permanent access to their services in the future.

To complement this overview, the findings of the survey of journals mentioned in the previous section ([Becerril-Garcia, 2021](#)). Regarding the services provided by journal portals, platforms, directories, and databases (such as Latindex, Redalyc, SciELO, AmeliCA, and Aura), the following was found:

- The visibility of the content published by the journals, search engine ranking, and prestige are the three main benefits that publishers receive from the services.
- The number of journals that report using indicators and other metrics, XML markup, interoperability, and editorial training is worthy of note.
- The technical administration, as well as the costs generated by the journal's website, its maintenance and operation, are largely borne by the publishing institution (Figure 10).
- In many cases, a combination of tools and systems is used for editorial management, including free software, open source software, commercial software, or internally developed software, among others (Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Origin of Funding for Journal Website Hardware and Communication Services. *Source:* Adapted from [Becerril-Garcia \(2021\)](#).

Figure 12 - Type of software used for editorial management. *Source:* Adapted from [Becerril-Garcia \(2021\)](#).

Finally, it is worth noting that some open academic platforms can offer a comprehensive solution for Diamond Open Access, based on the integration of their services. Their function goes beyond simply hosting content, as these structures effectively integrate a range of technological, editorial, and visibility services. A prime example is Redalyc, whose infrastructure offers an

ecosystem that includes Link Open Data, which links semantic collections and ontologies to represent knowledge; Metrics, which offers indicators on scientific quality, collaboration, use, and bibliodiversity; Interoperability and Visibility, which ensures integration with repositories and directories through protocols such as OAI-PMH; Full-Text Retrieval, which enables advanced searches, thematic filters, and geographic navigation; Editorial Workflow, which automates digital production with formats such as PDF, HTML, and EPUB, XML markup systems, and AI-based tools; and Quality Criteria, which establishes standards, certifications, and continuing education. The detailed Redalyc architecture can be consulted in [AmeliCA\(2022\)](#).

Europe

Introduction

European Diamond OA has a long and distinguished history that is obscured by its fragmentation: as the digital revolution rolled along, each country in Europe developed their own institutional nonprofit Open Access publishing solutions and infrastructures without much coordination at the supranational level. The French services of OpenEdition, for example, find their origin in Revues.org, a French portal for online academic journals in the humanities and social sciences that was founded in 1999. In Spain, one of the first electronic scientific journals was the *Revista Complutense de Historia de la Medicina* (1991), which was published both in paper and digital format. In Finland, the transition from accessing journal contents in digital form rather than in print was guided by the establishment of a national consortium consisting of Finnish universities, research institutions and public libraries (FinELib) in 1997.

The interest in a more systematic approach to understanding the Diamond Open Access landscape was sparked by the OA Diamond Journals Study (OADJS) from 2021 ([Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al., 2021](#)). One of the main recommendations from the OADJS was that there should be more alignment, coordination, and improvement of sustainability of Diamond OA journals. This idea was taken up in 2022 by the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access ([Ancion, Borrell-Damián, & Mounier, 2022](#)) – an initiative of Science Europe, cOAlition S, OPERAS, and the French National Research Agency (ANR) – which proposed to align and develop common resources for the entire Diamond OA ecosystem, including journals and platforms. The year 2022 also saw the start of the EC-funded DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects to develop the building blocks of the European Diamond Capacity Hub, which was launched in January 2025. In 2023, Diamond OA also received political support from the European Council in its Conclusions on ‘high quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing’ ([Council of the European Union, General Secretariat of the Council, 2023](#)), which called for immediate and unrestricted open access in publishing research involving public funds.

The first systematic overview of institutional nonprofit Open Access publishing efforts in Europe was provided by the DIAMAS project (2022-2025) in [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#). A synthetic overview of the main findings of these results can be found in [Arasteh, & Blake \(2024\)](#).

A systematic country-by-country overview of institutional nonprofit Open Access publishing was published in [Agnoloni, Bargheer, Bosman, et al. \(2024\)](#). These country reports draw on the 685 valid responses to the DIAMAS survey conducted between March and May 2023, representing data from 43 countries in the ERA. The country reports describe a snapshot of the landscape of institutional publishing in Europe based on analysis of the data collected in the survey sample.

Another output from the DIAMAS project ([Taşkın, Melinščak Zlodi, Laakso, et al., 2024](#)), shows how national contexts in Europe differ and present unique conditions for Diamond OA publishing in each country. Diamond OA thrives in countries with strong community leadership and public funding. In some countries, national journal publishing is financially supported via public financing and thus facilitates a scholarly communication environment in national languages, often realised through Diamond OA publishing. In countries where institutional publishers are coordinated at the national level, more public funding may be available for Diamond OA, although this does not appear to be a condition for national infrastructures that support Diamond publishing.

One of the main insights from the DIAMAS project was that countries with a national infrastructure for institutional nonprofit Open Access Publishing - including Croatia, Finland, France, Spain and Portugal - have thriving communities of well-aligned Diamond OA journals. One of the recommendations of the DIAMAS project was that Capacity Centres for institutional nonprofit OA publishing should be established at the national level in ERA countries that currently lack national coordination to provide tools, guidelines, governance, and funding ([Rooryck, & Mounier, 2023](#)). This effort is now in full swing, with a total of 20 National Capacity Centers currently (October 2025) being established or in preparation, coordinated by the European Diamond Capacity Hub.

Platforms

Europe has a diverse landscape of different platforms that are catering to Diamond OA publishing, many of them working on a broad national level (as opposed to an institutional or international level). To provide insight into the characteristics of platforms active in Europe this section contains selection of platforms from different parts of the ERA. There is also momentum for further organisation into nationally-oriented platforms with relatively recently launched platforms in Sweden⁹³) and the Netherlands⁹⁴.

OpenEdition

The origins of OpenEdition stem from Revues.org which was renamed to OpenEdition in 2017, now including both journals and books. The platform provides hosting services for publishers and focusing specifically on the social sciences and humanities disciplines in its content.

A platform factsheet for OpenEdition is provided in Table 25.

⁹³ <https://publicera.kb.se/>

⁹⁴ <https://openjournals.nl/>

Name	OpenEdition
URL	https://www.openedition.org/
Responsible organisation(s)	UAR 2504 of the CNRS, Aix-Marseille Université, EHESS, and Avignon Université.
Journals hosted	666 journals hosted, of which around 80% Diamond OA
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Application form, see https://www.openedition.org/10824
Services offered for journals (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● electronic publishing software: Lodel. ● helps editorial teams learn how to use various publishing tools and manage their own digital publishing process. ● editorial advice and technical support ● semantic structuring of metadata (using the XML TEI OpenEdition schema) ● data persistence and citability (DOI allocation) ● interoperability with other systems (OAI repository) ● automatic generation of portable formats (PDF and EPUB)
Year of establishment	2017
Business model for service provision	
Funding streams	Public funding via CNRS, Freemium models.
Interface languages	French
Links for more information	https://www.openedition.org/

Table 25 - OpenEdition platform factsheet

HRČAK

Launched in 2006, HRČAK is the central portal of Croatian scientific and professional journals. The portal is free for publishers to use, and getting accepted to use the platform requires some connection to Croatia but also requirements concerning licensing and publication processes and their transparency. A recent case study of the HRČAK platform is provided within a report stemming from the CRAFT-OA project (Laakso, van Edig, Fenner et al 2025). A platform factsheet for HRČAK is provided in Table 26.

Name	HRČAK
URL	https://hrcak.srce.hr/en
Responsible organisation(s)	University of Zagreb Computing Centre (SRCE)
Journals hosted	422 active OA journals of which approximately 93% Diamond OA
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	Journals can be admitted to HRČAK if they are open-access, have a connection to Croatia (through publisher, institution, or language), and meet specific quality and editorial criteria, including a transparent peer-review process
Services offered for journals (if any)	OJS
Year of establishment	2006
Business model for service provision	
Funding streams	Ministry of Science and Education (MSES), Croatia, which covers the portal's development and maintenance costs. HRČAK is an integral part of the University of Zagreb Computing Centre (SRCE), and receives additional funding from international grants
Interface languages	Croatian, English
Links for more information	https://hrcak-srce-hr-index-php-enid-89lang-cas-apis.com/policies/

Table 26 - HRČAK platform factsheet

TIB Open Publishing

Based in Germany, TIB (Technische Informationsbibliothek) Open Publishing is a diamond OA publisher of journals and conference proceedings. While open to all disciplines, focus is in particular on TIB's central subjects: natural sciences and technology. TIB Open Publishing is able to offer services to editors of any institution. A platform factsheet for TIB Open Publishing is provided in Table 27.

Name	TIB Open Publishing
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URL	https://tib-op.org
Responsible organisation	TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Hanover
Journals/books hosted	10+ OA journals & conference series (growing)
Joining requirements	Quality standards are based on the technical implementation guidelines of Plan S), but also on the DOAJ Seal), the OASPA membership criteria, and the COPE guidelines)
Services offered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Journal hosting, ● metadata, ● DOIs, ● long-term archiving
Year established	2021
Business model	Cost for journals/conference series dependent on publication volume, with an additional one-time setup cost for the first year.
Funding streams	TIB, Leibniz Association, BMBF
Interface languages	English, German
More info	https://www.tib-op.org/ojs/index.php/index/tibop/aboutus

Table 27 - TIB Open Publishing platform factsheet

Journal.fi

Journal.fi is a national-level OA publishing platform launched in 2017 provided by the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV). The platform is free for learned societies in Finland to use and is based on a central OJS installation. Non-learned society publishers can also make use of the service for a fee. Technical support is provided for journals, but content-related work is up for each journal to take care of and resource themselves.

As of 2025 the platform hosts 125 active peer-reviewed scholarly journals. 104 of these are Diamond OA, with the rest being available OA after a maximum 12 month embargo. A recent case study of the journal.fi platform is provided within a report stemming from the CRAFT-OA project ([Laakso, van Edig, Fenner, et al., 2025](#)). A platform factsheet for journal.fi is provided in Table 28.

Name	Journal.fi
URL	https://journal.fi
Responsible organisation	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV)
Journals/books hosted	125 active scholarly journals, of which 104 Diamond OA and the rest OA with an embargo of 12 months.
Joining requirements	<p>TSV member society journals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles must be openly available with a maximum delay of one year from the date of publication. Journals based on subscription models from member societies can also use the service for manuscript reception and editorial work. <p>Journal is not required to be peer-reviewed</p> <p>Other than TSV member society journals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Journal must be immediately and completely open. It must be published regularly, at least once a year. Journal must present scientific research results and be peer-reviewed. The publisher of the journal must be Finnish, or it must be a joint publication with at least one Finnish entity as a publisher.
Services offered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OJS hosting, submission & publication workflow, DOIs, indexing
Year established	2017
Business model	Publicly funded service, non-society publishers pay a usage fee
Funding streams	TSV, Ministry of Education & Culture, non-society publishers

Interface languages	Finnish, English, Swedish (varies by journal)
More info	https://tsv.fi/palvelut/avoimen-julkaisemisen-palvelut/journal.fi

Table 28 – Journal.fi platform factsheet

Tidsskrift.dk

Tidsskrift.dk is a national-level journal portal in Denmark launched in 2008 and maintained by the local national library, Det Kongelige Bibliotek. In the beginning the portal primarily functioned as a digitized archive for content for a handful of journals, but has over time become OJS-driven to support editorial workflows and is now home to content from over 190 journals. The platform is free for journals to use. A platform factsheet for Tidsskrift.dk is provided in Table 29.

Name	Tidsskrift.dk
URL	https://tidsskrift.dk
Responsible organisation	Royal Danish Library
Journals/books hosted	200 immediate OA journals (majority Diamond OA), 14 delayed OA journals
Joining requirements	Danish scholarly journals (cultural & academic)
Services offered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OJS hosting, ● editorial workflow, ● archiving
Year established	2008 (OJS relaunch 2016)
Business model	Public library service
Funding streams	Royal Danish Library

Interface languages	Danish, English
More info	https://tidsskrift.dk/index/om_tidsskriftdk

Table 29 - Tidsskrift.dk platform factsheet

EKT ePublishing

EKT ePublishing is the Greek national-level portal for hosting OA journals, monographs, and conference proceedings. The service is operated by the National Documentation Centre (EKT) in Greece. The system is based on OJS.

A platform factsheet for EKT ePublishing is provided in Table 30.

Name	EKT ePublishing
URL	https://epublishing.ekt.gr
Responsible organisation	National Documentation Centre (EKT), Greece
Journals/books hosted	87 journals, 63 monographs, 23 conference proceedings. All publications are Diamond OA
Joining requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Editorial Board, ● Publicly available description of the peer review/editorial processes, focus and scope, etc. ● Publication of original content ● Peer-review ● Content available in open access ● Regular publication periodicity ● Compliance with internationally acknowledged publication ethics
Services offered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OJS/OMP-based hosting, ● metadata, ● training, ● preservation
Year established	2007

Business model	Public research infrastructure
Funding streams	Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance, EU projects
Interface languages	Greek, English
More info	https://epublishing.ekt.gr/en/5695

Table 30 - EKT ePublishing platform factsheet

RACO

RACO is a platform for serving OA publishing for Catalan journals. The system is based on OJS.

A platform factsheet for RACO is provided in Table 31.

Name	RACO – Revistes Catalanes amb Accés Obert
URL	https://www.raco.cat
Responsible organisation	Biblioteca de Catalunya, Consorci de Serveis Universitaris de Catalunya (CSUC)
Journals/books hosted	593 OA journals, most immediate OA but also some with delayed OA to content
Joining requirements	Catalan academic journals with OA policy
Services offered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hosting, ● metadata, ● visibility services
Year established	2006
Business model	Cooperative OA infrastructure. Basic archiving features are free for publishers, management and editing tools are paid premium services.

Funding streams	Generalitat de Catalunya, member institutions
Interface languages	Catalan, Spanish, English
More info	https://raco.cat/raco/index.php/en/about/

Table 31 - RACO platform factsheet

Septentrio Academic Publishing

Septentrio Academic Publishing is a publishing service provided by The University Library at UiT The Arctic University of Norway. The platform is running on OJS and caters to publications where staff from UiT are involved in editorial roles, or for publications in subjects that are important for UiT.

A platform factsheet for Septentrio Academic Publishing is provided in Table 32.

Name	Septentrio Academic Publishing
URL	https://septentrio.uit.no
Responsible organisation	UiT The Arctic University of Norway (University Library)
Journals/books hosted	11 journals, and several peer-reviewed publication series, all Diamond OA
Joining requirements	OA journals, typically linked to UiT or Norwegian institutions
Services offered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hosting, ● DOI, ● indexing, ● copyediting support, ● preservation
Year established	2014
Business model	Diamond OA (no fees)

Funding streams	UiT, Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research
Interface languages	English, Norwegian
More info	https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/index/etablering

Table 32 - Septentrio Academic Publishing platform factsheet

Output types

When it comes to European Diamond OA publishing activity and research on different aspects of European Diamond OA publishing, the focus has been largely on scholarly journals. However, other outputs of Diamond OA publishing, such as books and preprints also deserve attention.

The DIAMAS project conducted an Europe-wide web survey that reached out to institutional publishers active in the region to map among other things their organisational circumstances, activities, and resourcing ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al., 2023](#)). One of the sections of the survey concerned what type of outputs the publishers were producing, with Figure 12 displaying the distribution of the responses among the 685 organisations that responded. When interpreting the results it is worthwhile to note that 1) not all respondents produce Diamond OA outputs, either in full or partially, so immediate conclusions can not be drawn concerning that aspect, 2) the emphasis of the DIAMAS project was on scholarly journals so respondents that are active in that area of publishing, either in part or completely, might have been more inclined to respond. Nevertheless, from the results one can see that it is not uncommon for European institutional publishers to engage in journal publishing, academic book publishing, as well as publication of conference outputs. Over half of the respondents that published an academic journal also published academic books and conference outputs.

Figure 13 - Publication types among European institutional publishers ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al., 2023](#): 52)

Table 33 goes further in depth on the degree of OA publishing that the respondents reported for each output type that they engage with publishing, showing quite a stark difference between journals (90%) and books (58%). With regards to degree of full Diamond OA publishing slightly over 25% of institutional publishers publish their journals and books in OA without charging APCs or BPCs (BPC).

	n	mean	median
Academic journals	496	90.1	100
Academic books	319	58.2	60
Conference outputs	280	75.5	100
Grey literature	105	62.6	95
Non-standard research outputs	117	63.2	99
Non-academic outputs	118	51.1	50
Other outputs (datasets, software ...)	89	54.0	67

Table 33 - Mean and median of the proportion of OA content per output type ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al., 2023](#): 64)

Diamond OA journals

Based on the contents of the Directory of Open Access Journals at the start of the year 2025, of the 13,083 active Diamond OA journals that were part of the directory, 5,840 (45%) were published in a European country ([Crawford, 2025](#)). The share was also similar if considering what volume of

Diamond OA journals articles were published by these journals, which was 48% (204,969 out of a total 425,391). The numbers suggest that Europe together with Latin America are the two most active areas globally for Diamond OA publishing for journals. It warrants reminding that the DOAJ nor any other single international data source is exhaustive or completely comprehensive covering Diamond OA journals. For a broader scan of Diamond OA journals in Europe please see the dedicated bibliometric mapping section towards the end of this report.

Diamond OA books

Open access to scholarly books has a long tradition in Europe, but it is far from being the mainstream approach and its results are not on a par with the achievements in the journal publishing space. This particularly concerns Diamond OA book publishing, since a lot of the existing practices revolve around payment of book processing charges or self-archiving of partial or full book contents rather than funding for the publication activities coming from elsewhere.

The OAPEN Foundation is a key actor in the European context of open access books, operating three key services: The OAPEN Library, OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit, and The Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB). The OAPEN Library is a central repository for hosting and disseminating OA books which in July 2025 provides access to 40,642 titles. OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit is a collection of resources aimed to guide and support different actors in their actions and choices related to OA book publishing. DOAB is a discovery service providing indexing of over 96,000 OA books, provided in partnership with OpenEdition, CNRS, and Aix Marseille Université from France. It should be noted that not all of these OA books are Diamond OA.

As practices and policies for OA books have been very diverse in the European area the EU-funded PALOMERA project which ran from 2023 to the end of 2024 was set up to map the present status across the European Research Area ([PALOMERA Project, n.d.](#)). Through analysis of hundreds of OA policies, national contextual documents, interviews, a broad web survey, and bibliometric data the project produced recommendations for different actors for facilitating OA book publishing practices (Bandura- Morgan, Bazeliuk, Davidson et al 2024). Although they are very recent, these recommendations have already been integrated into new OA policies, suggesting that the project served to bring both clarity and alignment to the emergent space of OA books.

In addition to PALOMERA, notable European projects researching and facilitating the OA book publishing are the UK-based Copim (2019-2023) and Open Book Futures (2023-2026) projects, which have produced both new knowledge and business models particularly for smaller publishers. One of these models is the Open Book Collective (OBC) that gathers together publishers, publishing service providers, libraries and other research institutions on a platform that matches together providers services with those with any actor that wants to financially support them.

Preprints

In a longitudinal bibliometric study on preprinting patterns across countries and disciplines [Rzayeva, Pinfield, & Waltman \(2025\)](#) observed that European uptake of preprinting has largely

followed the global patterns for the group of 15 European countries included in the study. The highest share of preprinting was found within physics and mathematics, and in many European countries about half the published articles in these disciplines have been made available as preprints. Chemistry, engineering, technology, biology, and psychology followed after in terms of preprint prevalence, with many countries having between 10% and 15% of outputs available in preprint form. The study found in general lower degrees of preprinting among Southern European countries, while Western European and Northern European countries had higher ones.

On the national levels, there has not yet been a development towards launching preprint publication portals, with the focus rather being on portals for Diamond OA journals. The vast majority of Diamond OA journals in Europe are within the Social Sciences and Humanities ([Crawford, 2025](#)) and preprinting initiatives are currently not strongly represented in these disciplines ([Melero, Boté-Vericad & López-Borrull, 2023](#); [Rzayeva, Pinfield, & Waltman 2025](#)). This suggests that preprint publications are not a significant activity for European Diamond OA journal publishers.

Preprint practices do not just make non-peer reviewed materials available on subject repositories while being relatively disconnected from peer-review and publication processes being advanced elsewhere. The principles of making manuscripts publicly available upon submission followed by peer-review (the Publish-Review-Curate model) is something that European publishing platforms set up by major funders have embraced, including the EC's Open Research Europe and Wellcome Open Research, which are publication options for research that has been funded through these funders. Peer Community In⁹⁵ and SciPost also represent this novel model that integrates preprints into a deconstructed peer review process that may then lead to a final publication outlet selection. Together with Overlay journals, these models are strongly represented by European Diamond OA publishers ([Rousi, & Laakso, 2022](#)). Another European initiative enabling integration of repository-archived preprints into peer-review and publication processes is the Notify project by the Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)⁹⁶.

A platform factsheet for Peer Community In is provided in Table 34.

Name	Peer Community In
URL	https://www.peercommunityin.org/
Responsible organisation(s)	Association « Peer Community In » (PCI), 11 route de Bellet, Nice, France
Journals hosted	One own journal for peer-reviewed preprints accepted by thematic PCIs (Peer Community Journal. Twenty-one thematic PCIs (e.g. PCI Ecology, PCI Archaeology, etc ...) that conduct peer-review of preprints in their thematic

⁹⁵ <https://peercommunityin.org/>

⁹⁶ <https://coar-repositories.org/what-we-do/notify/>

	areas and have collaborations with hundreds of journals that take peer-reviews managed by the thematic PCIs as input into editorial processes.
Requirements for journals joining (if any)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New thematic PCIs created if a small group of founders is willing to invest time and energy and if they adhere to the status, interior rules and code of conduct of PCI • They must adhere to open science and transparency and integrity in science • Their PCI has a clear scientific scope, not overlapping with the other 21 scopes of the 21 thematic PCIs • They recruit a solid group of recommenders (associate editors) • They secure a large number of commitments to submit to the PCIs
Services offered for journals (if any)	<p>For new thematic PCIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website of publication, including an in-house preprint submission system with a back-office specifically designed for the evaluation workflow performed by the thematic PCIs. • Help of editorial teams to learn how to use various publishing tools and manage their own digital publishing process. • Editorial and technical support. • Preservation (CLOCKKS) and DOIs (CROSSREF) • Interoperability with preprint servers and institutional repositories (via COAR notify, hypothes.is) and aggregators (Society.org, Europe PMC) • Communication and communication funds • Direct acceptance and publication at no cost and in open access, if authors choose, of their recommended preprints in Peer Community Journal, already running and indexed.
Year of establishment	2017
Business model for service provision	Supported by Peer Community In
Funding streams	Public funding via many universities, libraries and national research organisations.
Interface languages	English
Links for more information	https://www.peercommunityin.org/

Table 34 – Peer Community In factsheet

Organisational structures & governance models

The information compiled from the existing literature reveals a diverse landscape of Diamond OA publishing in Europe, shaped by different legal forms, institutional affiliation, staffing, and operational practices.

The OADJS findings ([Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al., 2021](#)) as well as several DIAMAS outputs found that resourcing of these journals largely depends on volunteers, universities, and government, confirming the significance of institutional and community-led models. A uniform classification of governance structures is not provided across all sources, but we have organised the observations into four broad categories that also function as the structure for this section.

From the analysed documents, the following governance types and associated operational characteristics can be identified:

1. Legal part of parent organisation (e.g., Research Institution, University, Library)

These publishing entities are often small-scale compared to commercial publishers, and organisation structures tend to be more flat, collaborative, and flexible. Many such organisations publish a mix of academic books, monographs, edited volumes, conference proceedings, and journals. Staff often consists of personnel from the organisation who take on publishing responsibilities alongside potential primary roles, with few fully dedicated hires. However, institutions, particularly universities, have multiple missions that are not dedicated to publishing, which can pose challenges for restructuring or development. Host institutions provide continuity, technical support, and access to resources, enhancing stability. Operations depend on institutional technical infrastructure such as publication management software, repositories, and other digital services. This also extends to leveraging other in-house support services such as legal, human resources, and marketing. Frictions can arise when the institutional partner's priorities (e.g., standardisation) clash with the journal's specific needs.

When there are larger teams, these have specialised and well-defined roles, supporting professionalisation and task distribution. Smaller teams often rely on volunteers or in-kind contributions from the institution, overlapping roles and flexible responsibilities. The hybrid nature of staffing (volunteers and in-kind support) can affect long-term stability and make strategic development difficult.

A large majority of Diamond OA journals in Germany are published by research institutions, including universities and non-university research institutions ([Taubert, Sterzik, & Bruns, 2024](#)). New University Presses (NUPs) emerging in the UK are often library-based, suggesting they are part of the larger university structure ([Adema, & Stone, 2017](#)). For example EKT Open Book Press

highlights initiatives developed by specific institutions, such as the National Documentation Centre (EKT), which was described earlier as within the platforms section.

2. Stand-alone legal entity (e.g., Learned Society, Foundation):

Some Diamond OA journals and presses operate as independent legal entities, such as learned societies, non-profit foundations, or scholarly publishers. These entities often assume full independent responsibility for editorial operations and academic quality. Organisational size and structure vary, with some journals having large teams with defined roles, while others rely on small and committed groups. Funding can come from donations, grants, or a combination of public and private sources.

Larger or well-funded entities can achieve high professionalization, with dedicated staff and formalised processes (for editorial, technical, and administrative operations). Smaller independent initiatives often depend on volunteer contributions and in-kind work, making them flexible and with the risk of unbalanced workloads and dependence on some individuals. "Subscribe-to-Open" and similar models also exist, often realised in partnership with a commercial publisher, that differ from typical Diamond OA organisational principles and structures ([Taubert, Sterzik, & Bruns, 2024](#)).

3. Ad hoc and acephal communities of practice (e.g. academic-led):

A notable number of academics and researchers have set up their own publishing initiatives, often demonstrating innovative approaches. These are sometimes referred to as academic-led presses (ALPs). Operationally, these initiatives often correspond to models heavily reliant on gift-based completion of tasks, especially when team sizes are small. In this model, individual contributions tend to be large due to limited team size. There can be limitations as donors decide *whether* and *how* to contribute, potentially creating friction if this doesn't align with journal requirements. Shortage of resources (time and money) is a prominent issue, leading to prioritisation of day-to-day tasks over long-term development. Workload can be transferred to highly committed members, risking overburdening them, and high personalisation can make the journal dependent on indispensable individuals. In some cases, a "miracle of the crowd" model can prosper with a large volunteer team and primarily gift-based contributions, enabled by specific organisational and technical preconditions, and a pragmatic orientation that minimises workload. This requires mutual trust and fair work distribution.

4. Shared Service Providers and Hybrid Models

Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) and similar collaborative frameworks are increasingly common in Europe. These entities provide infrastructure, technical services, or editorial support for multiple journals or presses, not always with legal responsibility for content. Hybrid organisational models combine volunteer work, in-kind institutional contributions, and limited dedicated staff. Shared infrastructures (platforms, preservation systems, metadata management) improve efficiency and allow small journals to benefit from these resources.

Centralised services allow small initiatives to operate sustainably, reduce administrative burden, and maintain standards across publications. Voluntary contributions, institutional support, and dedicated staff can affect governance, task allocation, and scalability. Organisational structures remain flexible, with small hierarchies and overlapping responsibilities.

In summary, while specific legal governance structures are not exhaustively listed in the sources, the data strongly points to research institutions (universities, libraries, research centres) as major players, alongside learned societies and individual/academic-led initiatives heavily reliant on voluntary contributions. These different entities operate with varying degrees of monetisation and team sizes, which significantly impact their stability, professionalisation, and capacity for development. The dependence on time-limited funding and the challenges of relying heavily on indispensable volunteers are significant factors affecting the long-term stability of some models.

While the sources do not categorise organisational structures, several patterns emerge across European Diamond OA journals and institutional publishing initiatives:

1. Institutional embedding (universities, libraries, research centers) is the dominant model, providing stability, infrastructure, and some funding, but limiting flexibility.
2. Independent legal entities (learned societies, foundations, non-profits) balance autonomy and responsibility, with operational stability dependent on funding and team size.
3. Scholar-led or community-based models improve flexibility and innovation but rely heavily on volunteer labor and key individuals.
4. Shared service providers and hybrid approaches support operational sustainability, scalability, and professionalisation, particularly for small-scale journals

Team size, funding sources, volunteer contributions, and institutional support determine the professionalisation, workload distribution, and long-term viability of each model. Across all models, reliance on institutional infrastructure, digital platforms, and collaborative networks is essential for continuity and quality of scholarly output.

Funding mechanisms

Diamond OA is an ecosystem made up of institutional publishers and service providers of different shapes and sizes, with diverse missions, services and tasks. These factors also influence the sustainability options and choices available. For this reason, no one size fits all, and there is no one source of funding that serves all types of publishers ([Brun, Pontille, & Torny, 2024](#)).

A mapping study of journals published by small and mid-sized publishers in Europe and the existing public funding mechanisms found that the funding mechanisms available to journals differed significantly across countries in Europe. Some countries, such as Finland, have inclusive subsidies available for all peer-reviewed journals published in the country, while many other countries rely on competitive grant funding for distributing resources. Publishing OA was often found to be a requirement to be eligible for funding. It would also seem that many journals do not

receive public funding directly but rather are supported through their institutions ([Laakso, & Multas 2023](#)).

The funding mechanisms behind Diamond OA publishers are indeed various and can be split into two top-level categories: 1) Non-monetary, including people, infrastructure, services, and time, and 2) Financial ([Bargheer, Bosman, Drahomira, et al., 2023](#)). In Germany, a bibliometric mapping of Diamond OA journals found significant diversity of funding mechanisms used. The study does not provide itemised funding mechanism information but rather maps the journals on a 2x2 matrix in relation to the size of the journals (in terms of article volume), and in relation to the degree of voluntary/gift-based delivery of tasks versus monetization of task completion. There are journals in all quadrants which speaks for the diversity of circumstances for different diamond OA journals in Germany. Most crowded it is in the smaller scale of publication volume where moderate to high task monetization is in place ([Taubert, Sterzik, & Bruns, 2024](#)). Across Europe, the funding mechanisms available for Diamond OA publishing differ from country to country.

Non-monetary support

The two most common funding mechanisms found in the survey distributed by the Diamond OA Study were in-kind support by home institutions and voluntary labor (excl. scientific) ([Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al., 2021](#)). Parent institutions provide non-monetary support to Diamond OA publishing operations in the form of the workforce, resources such as office space, and hosting services. The workforce, which is delivered via voluntary, in-kind or paid work, is just as central if not more central to revenue streams ([Brun, Pontille, & Torny, 2024](#)).

For example, most RPOs in the UK operating university presses are supported by the institution, or by making use of existing staff and resources within the library. In another survey, only one reported to be self-sustaining, and one having some other type of funding (e.g. external funding). Most of the institutional support came in the form of staffing, with infrastructural and technical support following closely after ([Adema, & Stone, 2017](#)).

Funding available for Diamond OA in Europe

Financial support for Diamond OA in Europe usually comes from institutional, local, national, and international funding sources and takes the form of subsidies, grants, and paid salary costs. The Diamond OA Study found that grant funding, collectively organised funding, and donations or gifts were less common funding mechanisms than non-monetary forms of support (Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer et al 2021), but these funding mechanisms still are relied upon to help cover costs. Most publishers and service providers substantially rely on only one or two funding forms, even for the majority of those with less than 2 or 6 FTEs ([Brun, Pontille, & Torny, 2024](#)). Where financial support is not available, publishers seek other sources of funding.

Local, regional or national funders are the main funders in Europe. Types of funders that fund Diamond OA include institutions such as universities, research centres, departments, as well as publishers, national dissemination platforms, governmental bodies, local communities, learned societies, private sponsors and authors. Funders largely fund institutional publishers and service

providers of their own country, although some do outside of them: from publishers to infrastructure. Those who fund outside of the local country in Europe are predominantly European institutions/initiatives such as the European Social Fund, the Council of Europe or the European Commission or service providers such as large publishers or dissemination services and certain foundations.

DIAMAS concluded that universities and/or libraries and public national or regional funders seem to be the most committed to sustaining Diamond publishing. IPSPs can remain sustainable without direct funding if full costs are covered by the parent organisation or if the necessary tasks are handled by dedicated personnel. For most publishers that are fully Diamond, the role of the parent organisation is paramount for their basic support particularly in personnel and services through in-kind support. Support can be fixed or periodically negotiated (less frequently but still significant). DIAMAS found that 66% of institutional publishers and service providers receive funding from their parent organisation ([Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al., 2021](#)). For example, among the editors of 168 Diamond OA journals in Switzerland surveyed in 2023, the most common funding mechanisms were direct financial support by affiliated institutions, and paid salary costs by affiliated institutions, with all other options having substantially lower representation among the answers. Donations and endowments, grants, membership fees, and 'other' were roughly tied ([Hahn, Hehn, Hopp, et al., 2023](#)).

Government or other sources of funding outside the organisation provide time-limited grants or subsidies; DIAMAS research found that 48% of institutional publishers and service providers surveyed benefit from these. "Research funding organisations and international funders, however, currently marginally support non-commercial Diamond OA publishing needs, in contrast to the significant support that they provide to commercial publishing through APCs and BPCs" ([Brun, Pontille, & Torny, 2024](#)).

Subsidies or grants are one of the cornerstones for the sustainability of institutional publishing. Although some are permanent and some periodically negotiated or time-limited, subsidies are considered by Diamond OA publishers to be the most stable funding source, although this is by no means an available option to all. European institutional publishers responded to the DIAMAS survey in 2023 that they have relied on *Fixed and permanent subsidies from a parent organisation* most in the last three years, with many relying on them highly or very highly. Publishers and their service providers also frequently depend on *Periodically negotiated subsidies from the parent organisation, Time-limited grants or subsidies, either private or public from outside the organisation and Permanent public government funding (international, national, local)* ([Brun, Pontille, & Torny, 2024](#)).

An example of a European country where public subsidies are important to funding OA journals is Croatia, for which [Horvat, & Velagić \(2020\)](#) provide a comprehensive overview of funding information coupled with bibliometrics in terms of outputs enabled by the funding. 234 journals received such subsidies between 2012 and 2018, where a criterion for funding was that they should be available OA through the national HRČAK, the central portal of Croatian scholarly journals. The average journal subsidy for 2018 was around 8500 euro. Subsidies for the publication of books did not have an OA requirement at this point in time. Another country is Serbia, where the ministry

responsible for science (or culture) distributes subsidies to a sizeable share of journals active in the country, and other types of public funds distributed through the publishing institutions or local communities ([Ševkušić, Janković, & Kužet, 2017](#)). The majority of OA journals that responded to the survey distributed by [Ševkušić, Janković, & Kužet \(2017\)](#) depended in one form or another on public funding.

In European countries where there is limited support from institutional, local, and national funders, Diamond OA publishers must seek other sources of funding. In Italy, Diamond OA is situated in a strained environment where a lot of funds in the sector are funnelled to enabling OA through international commercial publishers. Many university presses in the country are Diamond OA but there still is not a national-level funding mechanism for supporting Diamond OA journals. Instead, they rely on a fragmented palette of funding sources to keep publishing activities running ([Peruginelli, & Faro 2024](#)).

While parent organisations and public or governmental bodies are often the primary sources of funding, some seek additional revenue, whether through their content and services or from external funders. Sources of funding like *Author Processing Charges (APCs)/publication fees*, *Voluntary Author Contributions*, *Collective funding* (e.g. *crowdfunding*, *S20*, *SCOSS*, *subscription fees* or *membership fees*) or *any other income* (event organisation, commercial revenue or loans) are far less prevalent and relevant for the majority. While not all institutional OA publishing follows the Diamond model, institutional OA publishers are more likely to adopt Diamond than to charge APCs. However, some do pursue revenue from content and print sales and Voluntary Author Contributions (VACs) to fund their activities. Fewer rely on income streams such as events, advertising, commercial revenue and loans ([Brun, Pontille, & Tornø, 2024](#)).

The use of advertising among OA journals to raise revenue is not a common practice. In 2009 Frantsvåg (2010) conducted a web survey directed towards a sample of journals (1332 journals invited, 474 responded) from the DOAJ, and with a particular focus on journals from the Nordic countries, on the topic of use of advertising as an income source among journals. The results show that 21% of the responding journals accepted advertising in their journal or on their webpages, with larger publishers more commonly accepting advertising compared to smaller publishers. Advertising is generally perceived as inappropriate for scholarly journals. 26% of the journals surveyed noted that they had not considered using advertising as a source of income. More than two-thirds of those that chose to pursue revenues from advertising did so directly with firms interested in advertising in the journal, rather than by making agreements with brokers for serving dynamic advertisements. Similar results were also gained in the survey to Serbian journals conducted by [Ševkušić, Janković, & Kužet \(2017\)](#) where 82% of respondents reported that they do not publish advertisements.

Sustainability

Limited duration of funds and limited access to funds challenge the sustainability of Diamond OA publishing in Europe. In the last 3 years, funding streams mainly stem from local, regional or national sources rather than funders with international scope, which are in a tiny minority. Securing long-term structural or project-based funding from public and institutional sources at

both national and European levels is essential for Diamond OA publishers ([Brun, Pontille, & Torny, 2024](#)).

High reliance on funding from the parent organisation can place an extra burden on publishers, for instance from administrative reporting. However, some parent organisations highly value the work of these publishers and are willing to support them regardless of whether other funding streams are also available ([Brun, Pontille, & Torny, 2024](#)).

The most critical challenges reported from journal editors of Swiss diamond OA journals were managing journal operations largely based on volunteer effort, and the lack of sustainable funding and fundraising ([Hahn, Hehn, Hopp, et al., 2023](#)).

Among institutional publishers and service providers surveyed by DIAMAS that know their costs, most operate on under €50k, though expenses vary greatly depending on the host country, the range of services offered, and the volume of journal output ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al., 2023](#)).

[Dufour, Pontille, & Torny \(2023\)](#) note that: “To make fully diamond OA IPs more sustainable, there is the need for new funding schemes that would stimulate and enable RFOs and universities to become their funders independent of their nationality or location”.

Diamond OA particularly flourishes in countries with strong OA community leadership and public funding ([Taşkın, Melinščak Zlodi, Laakso, et al., 2024](#)). When institutional publishers are co-ordinated at the national level, more public funding can also be available for Diamond OA. In some countries, publishers can largely operate as non-profits, and Diamond OA journals predominate here. In Norway a consortium of national journals receive public funding, where a criterion for eligibility is that they are Diamond OA. In Finland, a robust national umbrella organisation distributes public subsidies to support journal publishing, which is utilised mainly by learned societies publishing Diamond OA on the national journal.fi⁹⁷ platform. In Croatia, community-led infrastructures are largely publicly funded, as is a system of national infrastructures for OA in France, but these infrastructures are still underfunded. In Poland, institutional publishers are primarily institutionally funded, while government funds are available to those striving to increase their impact or quality rather than those publishing OA. Some fund Diamond OA, but more dedicated public funding is still needed to extend the reach of Diamond publishers and service providers across Europe.

The Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) was developed in the DIAMAS project to help institutional publishers and service providers operate with good practices. DOAS presents a number of required and desired attributes for Diamond OA journals that want to be aligned with the standard. DOAS is organised into seven sections, of which one is “Funding” ([Consortium of the DIAMAS project, 2025](#)). That section contains three sub-sections:

⁹⁷ <http://journal.fi>

- Diamond OA model - Journals are required to have no paywalls for either authors or readers, and provide this information transparently on their webpages, as well as if there are any other types of fees involved
- Sustainability
 - Financial support. “The publisher is directly or indirectly funded by public funds or other revenue streams to enable free access to the author and reader, ideally covering all costs. (REQUIRED)”
 - “Costs. Costs are identified year-on-year. Publishers are able to plan their annual costs and to balance them with expected incomes and in-kind contributions using a tracking system, such as a budget. (DESIRED)”
 - Sustainability plan. “The publisher considers the medium-term economic viability of its Diamond OA model. It has a clear overview of available funding sources and other relevant external and internal (in-kind) resources, aligned with set expectations of future maintenance and developmental costs. In achieving its goals, a publisher preferably deploys collaborative strategies and uses common open infrastructures, to cut costs and raise efficiency. (DESIRED)”
- Editorial Independence - Editorial operations related to content and peer review are required to be completely detached from influence of any bodies that are providing funding to the publisher. A desired practice is that the origin of the revenue streams are in line with the values, expectations, and traditions in the disciplines that the publisher is serving, and do not have an impact on editorial independence. Any conflicts of interests between revenue streams and authors, reviewers, or editors should be clearly indicated.

Another tool developed in Europe to support good practices is *Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access* overview, which maps out over ten funding or revenue streams compatible with Diamond OA, including the pros and cons of each ([Melinščak Zlodi, 2025](#)). It was designed to support publishers and service providers in deciding the model most suitable to their field, business model, and size. See Table 35 below for insights on the models described and who they best serve, with examples.

Funding stream or model	Most appropriate for	Examples
Collective pledging model	Diamond OA publishers, publishing service providers, and infrastructures that provide a valuable service to a dedicated community of users who need additional funding to consolidate and develop their operations.	The Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services(SCOSS) ⁹⁸ KOALA Consortium ⁹⁹ service at the TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology University Library
Collective supporter programmes	Particularly relevant for Diamond OA publishers with contacts with other publishers and service providers with similar audiences and publishing profiles in terms of size, language or topics. This type of consortium is typically established as an informal group of members with a shared background and focus, organisation type, or place of origin.	Open Book Collective ¹⁰⁰ ScholarLed Consortium ¹⁰¹
Cooperative centralised funding	Particularly suited to scholarly fields with strong international collaborations and significant financial revenues, where researchers form well-connected global communities.	SCOAP3 - Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics.
Donations and grants from private funders or charities	Journals, publishers and platforms aligned with the charity's mission and eligible according to its criteria.	Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa (funded by Wellcome) OA grants by Arcadia Fund

⁹⁸ <https://scoss.org/>

⁹⁹ <https://www.tib.eu/en/services/koala/participate>

¹⁰⁰ <https://openbookcollective.org/>

¹⁰¹ <https://scholarled.org/>

<p>Individual membership fees</p>	<p>Particularly suited to organisations (primarily societies or associations) with a strong membership base that forms a dedicated community, either at a national or international level. It can be used to convert an existing non-Diamond journal to the Diamond OA model or to establish a new journal, as well as for other types of publishing outlets or services.</p>	<p><i>European Societies</i> - a journal published by MIT Press, owned and supported by the umbrella membership organisation</p> <p>the European Sociological Association; <i>Revija za sociologiju</i> - a journal published by the Croatian Sociological Association (a national association and a member of the European Sociological Association)</p>
<p>Library membership programmes</p>	<p>Diamond OA publishers or service providers with a dedicated community of libraries, publishers who know the groups of libraries interested in their collections, and publishers who have staff and resources for supporting and maintaining the community of library members and reaching new ones. It is easier to gain support from libraries whose users are also active users or whose authors publish with the publisher or service provider.</p>	<p>Open Book Publishers;</p> <p>the consortial library model of the Open Library of Humanities</p>
<p>Sales of additional digital content or services (Freemium)</p>	<p>Suitable for publishers with publishing platforms and technical capabilities for offering additional services that can be charged for in addition to the availability of content in basic formats. This type of income is also more appropriate for publishers with a more diverse and substantial catalogue of book or journal collections and less for small publishers such as single journal publishers.</p>	<p>OpenEdition Freemium for Books and OpenEdition Freemium for Journals</p>

<p>Sales of print copies</p>	<p>This type of funding can serve as a source of income for publishers who continue to have an audience for print editions (especially audiences that are outside of academia and without access to collective subscriptions). Those are often publishers of books in humanities and social sciences or journals with readers among professionals and practitioners, for instance, in law, healthcare, etc.</p>	<p>Bern Open Publishing, BMGN - Low Countries Historical Review</p>
<p>Subscribe to Open (S2O)</p>	<p>Works best for established subscription journals with stable subscriber bases. In most cases, it would not be as well-suited to new subscription journals with growing subscriber bases, journals that experience significant variations in the price of subscription from year-to-year, existing OA journals, and journals that depend on significant non-subscription revenue (from licensing, advertising, etc.).</p>	<p>Annual Reviews Project Muse De Gruyter</p>
<p>Subscriptions to print copies</p>	<p>Most suited to publishers that still have a traditional audience for print editions (especially audiences that are outside of academia and without access to collective subscriptions), such as publishers of book series in humanities and social sciences or journals that have readers among professionals and practitioners, for instance in law, healthcare, etc.</p>	<p>Almost all Diamond OA journals that are not born digital and have not yet abandoned the print version, sell subscriptions to print copies.</p>

<p>Subsidies and grants from public bodies</p>	<p>Journals, publishers and platforms that are eligible according to the proposed criteria. Except for the French National Open Science Fund, most other current subsidy schemes are nationally bounded, meaning only entities based in a certain country are eligible. That means journals, publishers or platforms based in countries without established and available subsidy schemes cannot rely on this funding source.</p>	<p>Governmental public funding subsidy for non-profit journals that is distributed by TSV in Finland; the Belgian Fund for Scientific Research, which provides annual calls for journal publishers, granting subsidies for up to three-year periods, the Norwegian NÅHST model, and the French National Open Science Fund.</p>
<p>Voluntary author contributions (VACs)</p>	<p>All publishers who publish at least a proportion of articles/chapters resulting from funded research projects or whose authors have dedicated institutional OA funds.</p>	<p>Publications of the Open Library of Humanities and the journal <i>Glossa Psycholinguistics</i> at eScholarship.</p>

Table 35 – Examples of key funding / revenue streams for Diamond OA including who they may be most appropriate for with examples.

Solutions and services

Infrastructure for Diamond OA publishing and dissemination

There are several challenges in analysing literature on the technical aspects of publishing. First of all, software evolves quickly and the literature data about publishing platforms published just a few years ago may already be outdated. Secondly, available information is mainly collected through surveys, which sometimes reflect the perspective of respondents rather than the actual state-of-the-art. In a number of surveys, participants showed poor familiarity with important details about their publishing infrastructure (e.g. which software is used, who provides hosting, etc.). Thirdly, the two main studies on Diamond OA publishing (Bosman et al. 2021)(Armengou et al. 2023) differ in the geographical coverage and targeted respondents. In both cases, there are gaps in coverage – for example, in the OA Diamond Study many respondents came from France, while the DIAMAS survey received proportionally more responses from southern Europe, which affects the regional balance of the data. For these reasons, our analysis will emphasize broad trends rather than accurate figures.

Software platforms

Diamond OA journals in Europe rely on a variety of publishing infrastructures. In this section too, we focus on software solutions for single-journal websites and multi-journal platforms.

Single-journal websites are most commonly built on:

- Free and open-source (FOSS) journal management systems, such as Open Journal Systems (OJS).
- Free and open-source content management systems (CMSs), such as WordPress or Drupal.
- Custom-made solutions.
- Commercial solutions offered by publishers such as Sciendo, Scholastica, De Gruyter, Springer, but also university presses in the UK (Adderley et al. 2011; Adema and Stone 2017).

According to [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#), publishers and service providers rely mainly on open-source software, with Open Journal Systems (OJS), developed by the Public Knowledge Project for managing peer-reviewed academic journals, as the dominant system – about 60% of the respondents in [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al. \(2021\)](#). According to [Khanna, Raoni, Smecher, et al. \(2024\)](#), there are 9499 known public installations of OJS in ERA (European Research Area), ERAC (European Research Area and Innovation Committee), observer and other countries associated with Horizon Europe, excluding Morocco and Tunisia, which are already covered in this report under Africa.

CMS-based applications are widely used as publishing venues, accounting for 14.07% according to [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#) and 8.5% according to [Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al. \(2021\)](#). Among these, WordPress is the most frequent solution – 11.2% according to [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#).¹⁰² Custom-made solutions account for 12.2% and are more common in Southern Europe (Armengou et al. 2023). Some examples suggest that platforms tailored to the needs of specific journals can streamline publishing ([Taubert, Sterzik, & Bruns, 2024](#)). However, such systems are usually more difficult and sometimes more expensive to maintain and upgrade.

Multi-journal platforms reveal a great diversity of solutions. The majority of journal publishing platforms in Europe are based on free and open-source software. The most commonly used software is Open Journal Systems. Examples of OJS-based platforms include national (e.g. Openjournals.nl¹⁰³ in the Netherlands, Tidsskrift.dk in Denmark, Journal.fi in Finland, SOAP2¹⁰⁴ in Switzerland, RECYT¹⁰⁵ in Spain, etc.) and institutional platforms (e.g. Revistes científiques de la Universitat de Barcelona (RCUB),¹⁰⁶ University of Ljubljana Press Journals,¹⁰⁷ etc.). It is followed by Janeway, an open-source publishing platform developed by the Centre for Technology and Publishing at Birkbeck, University of London, designed to manage the entire scholarly publishing workflow from submission to publication. Janeway is used by Open Library of Humanities,¹⁰⁸ as well as by a number of university platforms, mostly based in the United Kingdom (e.g. University of Huddersfield Press,¹⁰⁹ UCL Press Journals,¹¹⁰ etc.). Another software solution with significant

¹⁰² Repository software is also used to support publishing operations, presumably in book publishing. Reported examples include DSpace (7.6%), Dataverse (1.7%), Opus, Omeka, and DiVA ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. 2023](#)).

¹⁰³ <http://Openjournals.nl>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.soap2.ch/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://recyt.fecyt.es/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://revistes.ub.edu/>

¹⁰⁷ <https://journals.uni-lj.si/>

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.openlibhums.org/journals/>

¹⁰⁹ <https://unipress.hud.ac.uk/>

¹¹⁰ <https://journals.uclpress.co.uk/>

usage, though limited to one country, is Lodel,¹¹¹ developed by OpenEdition to enable the management of digital journals, books, and other scholarly publications, with a focus on the humanities and social sciences. Lodel is used to power OpenEdition Journals,¹¹² hosting more than 650 journals in September 2025. Another FOSS solution that is currently used by only one platform – Episciences,¹¹³ is Episciences,¹¹⁴ developed by the Centre pour la Communication Scientifique Directe to support overlay journals.

Custom-made solutions can also be found (e.g. Hrčak – Portal of Croatian scientific and professional journals in Croatia, SCIndeks¹¹⁵ in Serbia). Proprietary software is less frequently used for platforms hosting Diamond OA journals and is most commonly used by commercial publishers.

Platforms often operate on the SaaS model, where a journal is assigned a fully independent software instance (single-tenant) or multiple journals are hosted on the same installation (multi-tenant), offered to publishers free of charge (e.g. ePublishing, by the National Documentation Centre – EKT, in Greece, HRČAK OJS¹¹⁶ in Croatia) or for a fee (e.g. SCIndeks Asistent¹¹⁷ in Serbia).

The migration of Open Library of Humanities from OJS to Janeway, completed in 2022, is interesting as it shows how the need to make the publishing process more efficient and accommodate innovative approaches such as open peer review or overlay workflows can drive the development of a new software solution. Unlike OJS, which is based on PHP, Janeway is built in Python/Django, which is more flexible and easier to maintain, thanks to a wider developer community ([Eve, & Byers 2018](#)).

The information about motivation to use a particular software for the publishing platform is scarce and mostly anecdotal. The report by the PublishOA project, funded by the National Open Research Forum (NORF)¹¹⁸ in Ireland shows that the process of selecting software is sometimes guided by clearly defined criteria – in this particular case, derived from the Diamond Open Access Standard ([Publish OA, 2025](#)).

The most common type of multi-journal platforms are institutional platforms (40%), hosted by universities and other academic institutions ([Bosman, Frantsovåg, Kramer, et al., 2021](#)). National platforms developed with different aims and backgrounds. Some were created specifically to support Diamond OA journals (e.g., Openjournals.nl, SOAP2), while others aim for broad national coverage regardless of business model (e.g., RECYT, Hrčak). As running such platforms requires stable funding and strong coordination, many countries still lack a national journal platform.

The functions of publishing platforms vary in complexity. Some serve as primary publishing venues for journals (e.g. the Swedish national platform Publicera, Milano University Press

¹¹¹ <https://lodel.hypotheses.org/>

¹¹² <https://journals.openedition.org/?lang=en>

¹¹³ <https://www.episciences.org/>

¹¹⁴ <https://github.com/CCSDForge/episciences/>

¹¹⁵ <https://scindeks.ceon.rs/>

¹¹⁶ <https://ojs.srce.hr/>

¹¹⁷ <https://aseestant.ceon.rs/>

¹¹⁸ <https://dri.ie/norf/>

Journals¹¹⁹), while others also aggregate content from existing journal websites or platforms (e.g. Hrčak). Platform owners may operate as service providers (a common model for national platforms) or claim publisher rights, which is more typical of commercial publishers.

Different approaches to website and platform development can be observed. Some publishers (e.g. Masaryk University Press) have developed highly customised platforms based on FOSS solutions to accommodate their specific workflows and content display preferences ([EIFL, 2025](#)), while others rely on native features and widely used plugins. In the former case, software updates and upgrades are difficult and sometimes impossible.

Implementations of open-source platforms vary. CMS-based solutions, which usually do not support submission and review workflows, are sometimes combined with custom-made applications (e.g. Comet,¹²⁰ developed by SDEWES Centre, used by more than 20 journals in Croatia) or proprietary tools such as ScholarOne or Editorial Manager. Furthermore, a significant number of journals using OJS do not use all of its features ([Bosman, Frantsovåg, Kramer, et al., 2021](#)). It is often used only for content display, while submissions, peer review and production are managed via email, spreadsheets, Google Drive or even custom-made applications. These arrangements are diverse and insufficiently documented.

Despite the widespread use of standardised software solutions, interoperability remains a challenge because not all journals and platforms use available metadata exchange functionalities (e.g. OAI-PMH or metadata export) ([Laakso, Edig, Fenner, et al., 2025](#)). Only 37.2% of the participants in the DIAMAS survey licensed metadata under Creative Commons licenses ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al., 2023](#)).

According to ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al., 2023](#)), website and platform hosting is usually in-house (68.5%), managed by IT departments, publishing units or libraries. Many institutional publishers use outsourced services (52%), either free of charge (e.g. with NRENs) or for a fee (typically with commercial providers), or hybrid models (34.2%). In the SaaS model, hosting is usually part of the service package.

According to the same source, about 73.5% of institutional publishers and service providers have backup or disaster recovery policies and the likelihood of formal procedures increases with a larger budget. Maintenance is mostly in-house (70%). Outsourcing is common (47%), especially for infrastructure. Hybrid approaches, combining in-house and outsourced services, are widespread, and budget size affects internal maintenance capacity ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al., 2023](#)).

Support for indexing, PIDs, and metadata standards

According to [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#), most institutional publishers and service providers assign persistent identifiers (PIDs) such as DOIs, ISSNs, ORCID iDs, and RORs, with DOIs being the most common (94.7%). Registration is usually managed through Crossref and, less frequently, through DataCite. Despite broad adoption of PIDs, key challenges include limited skilled personnel and technical resources for metadata management and PID registration. PID

¹¹⁹ <https://milanoup.unimi.it/eng/journals.html>

¹²⁰ <https://comet.sdewes.org/info/>

usage seems to be consistent in Western Europe ([Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#)) and DOAJ journals use DOI more frequently than those not in DOAJ ([Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al., 2021](#)). In some countries, DOIs are assigned through local brokers, platforms or libraries. In Croatia, a publicly funded national service helps journals get DOIs, but DOIs are assigned only to original research articles. In Serbia, the landscape is more diverse, with publicly funded agencies offering DOIs free of charge to selected journals, non-profit agencies associated with universities and RPOs charging modest fees, and private for-profit agencies.

Many publishers struggle to get indexed in major databases such as DOAJ, Scopus, and Web of Science. According to [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#), around 60% of institutional publishers report difficulties meeting both technical and non-technical requirements. Financial barriers, including membership and recurring fees, are common, as well as technical challenges, particularly with metadata.

Digital preservation

Digital preservation is a critical challenge for many journals. [Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#) underline the reliance on national libraries and infrastructures as the most common preservation option (over 70% of respondents in both surveys). Dark archives like the PKP Preservation Network (PKP PN), CLOCKSS, Portico, and LOCKSS are used far less frequently, often due to technical limitations, costs, or complex joining procedures. The adoption of PKP PN remains surprisingly low given the high usage of OJS. In biomedical and life sciences, some journals use Pubmed as an archive. [Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al. \(2021\)](#) highlight that about 75% of respondents had no archiving policy in place. The situation is especially concerning given past evidence of journal content loss due to lack of preservation ([Laakso, Matthias & Jahn, et al., 2021](#)).

Editorial services

A significant number of journals still lack integrated editorial systems and they manage submission and peer review manually, often via email. Notably, some journals using OJS and similar journal management systems rely on manual submission and peer review procedures due to limited staffing or technical expertise.

Based on DOAJ's public data dump ([DOAJ, n.d.](#)), in September 2025, nearly half of Diamond OA journals from the EU and Associated Countries indexed in DOAJ have a plagiarism screening policy. The provision of plagiarism detection tools is costly, which poses a barrier for smaller journals. The most commonly used tools are presumably iThenticate and Turnitin, but there is no clear data on how many journals actually have access to them. Some journals use iThenticate through its integration with OJS. Turnitin's iThenticate plagiarism-checking system is available at reduced rates for Crossref members, but it is unclear how many Diamond OA journals take advantage of this option.

Little is known about how journals handle plagiarism screening, except that some journals screen all submissions before peer review, while others only scan manuscripts that are accepted for publication. According to the PLATO study conducted in Switzerland ([Hahn, Hehn, Hopp, et al.,](#)

[2023](#)), the majority of Swiss journals do not check submissions for plagiarism, while less than one-quarter of analysed journals systematically scan all submissions for plagiarism.

Capacity building and training

According to (Armengou et al. 2023), nearly half of the organisations are active in providing training, support, and advice, while 45% expressed interest in collaboration in these areas. Training and capacity-building activities are offered by a variety of actors, including libraries, communities of practice, and publishers' associations. For example, in Ireland, the Irish Open Access Publishers (IOAP)¹²¹ community of practice has been instrumental in bringing institutional publishers together. In Croatia, the Croatian Association of Scholarly Communication (ZNAK)¹²² plays a central role in capacity building and sharing best practices, alongside the Croatian chapter of the European Association of Science Editors (EASE). In France, universities have established journal incubators to support the growth of scholarly journals ([Taşkın, Melinščak Zlodi, Laakso, et al. 2024](#)). Libraries also frequently contribute to capacity building for Diamond OA (e.g. the Serbian library consortium, in collaboration with EIFL) (Armengou et al. 2023). In some cases, libraries and institutional publishers provide training modules for OA books, such as the University of Lancaster Library,¹²³ University of London Press,¹²⁴ and Copim Compass¹²⁵ in the U.K..

The European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)¹²⁶ launched in January 2025, designed to strengthen the Diamond Open Access (OA) community across Europe, provides resources such as guidelines and training modules. A key component of the EDCH's strategy is the establishment and support of national Diamond Capacity Centres OA, which play a crucial role in building local capacity by offering tailored services, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, and addressing the specific needs of their communities ([Mounier, & Rooryck, 2025](#)).

For OA books, international networks exist to exchange knowledge and resources. Based at OPERAS in Europe (although with a global reach), the Open Access Books Special Interest Group convenes several networks for stakeholders with an interest in OA book publishing. They provide networking and training events, collect resources online, create a platform for members to share expertise and local knowledge, and collaborate with publishers, publishing associations, libraries, funders, authors, and other stakeholders to ensure programming and resources respond to their needs.

Production services

Based on literature data, it can be concluded that diamond journals would prefer, if they had sufficient resources to do so, delegating or outsourcing design, production and copyediting tasks,

¹²¹ <https://ioap.ie/>

¹²² <https://www.znak.hr/>

¹²³

<https://portal.lancaster.ac.uk/ask/study/library/open-research/open-access/open-access-monographs-books-and-book-chapters/>

¹²⁴ <https://uolpress.co.uk/information/our-training-hub/>

¹²⁵ <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/>

¹²⁶ <https://diamas.org/>

in order to focus on editorial and scholarly activities ([Dufour, Pontille, & Torny 2023](#)). According to [Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al. \(2021\)](#), nearly 30% of the respondents outsource typesetting and copy-editing, very often to volunteers. In some disciplines, such as mathematics, typesetting is less costly and time consuming. Journals using TeX or LaTeX usually provide templates and have less work in the production stage ([Taubert, Sterzik, & Bruns, 2024](#)).

In non-English-speaking countries, providing high-quality copyediting for English-language content is cited as a significant challenge ([Taubert, Sterzik, & Bruns, 2024](#)). Apart from anecdotal evidence, it is not known to what extent journals are using AI-based tools for language editing.

According to [Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#), full text is usually available as PDF (97.3%) and less frequently in machine-readable formats: HTML (40.8%), XML (20.2%), and JSON (2.4%). This is consistent with the findings presented in [Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer, et al. \(2021\)](#). Many journals face difficulties producing JATS XML full text because the process is slow, resource-intensive, and free tools are scarce. To address this, the University of Zagreb Computing Centre developed the free JATS XML Converter Service, available via eduGAIN ([Wnuk, 2024](#)). In parallel, platforms such as OpenEdition use XML TEI, and work is underway to ensure smooth conversion between the two formats ([Martins, Ranasinghe, Souplet, et al., 2025](#)). The free tool Métopes¹²⁷ supports this conversion, but it remains little known among Diamond OA publishers.

[Armengou, Aschehoug, Ball, et al. \(2023\)](#) indicate a low level of compliance with accessibility standards: 87% of the respondents in the DIAMAS survey said they did not meet any of the accessibility standards – WCAG, OpenAIRE, DINI, UAAG, ATG – mentioned in the questionnaire. A large number of respondents (44–49%) are unaware of their platform’s compliance.

Although most publishing platforms could support continuous publishing, where articles are published as soon as they are accepted, a significant number of journals have retained traditional division into volumes and issues. Some journals make articles available as soon as accepted in the “ahead of print” regime and assign them to volumes and issues later. In some cases, the reasons for the adherence to the traditional practice are technical (e.g. limited availability of technical support ([Taubert, Sterzik & Bruns, 2024](#)).

For books, OAPEN Library provides a global infrastructure. The Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) indexes and provides discovery services for books.

4. Bibliometric mapping based on existing data on Diamond OA journals in the three regions

¹²⁷ <https://metopes.unicaen.fr/circeui/>

Introduction

The objective is to perform a bibliometric mapping of Diamond OA journals in Europe, Africa, and Latin America. To achieve this, the study integrates multiple open bibliometric and statistical resources, along with curated datasets from earlier initiatives and project partners. The resulting overview serves as a foundation for an understanding of what the current level of bibliometric data can provide us in terms of identification of Diamond OA journals in the three regions, and to consider what measures could be taken to improve the available knowledge about such journals in the scholarly publishing landscape. It should be highlighted that currently there does not exist any comprehensive international index of Diamond OA journals, and the mapping performed in this section is reliant on the quality of publication metadata from the bibliometric sources it uses to create an initial integrated list. Bibliometric sources are not always kept up to date on aspects such as changing publication models of journals, implementation of APCs, or the activity status of journals but this analysis does what is possible with the data that is available. Further investigations or refinements should conduct manual verification of each journal against specific criteria to assess their status and attributes, for that the dataset created here is a good starting point.

Methodology

To build a comprehensive dataset of Diamond OA journals, we adopted a multi-step integration process that combines global, regional, and project-specific data sources. The goal was to create a harmonized list that captures the diversity of OA publishing ecosystems across and within Africa, Europe, and Latin America. Figure 12 illustrates the overall process.

Figure 13 – Overall process of building the Diamond OA list

Creating the base list

We began by constructing a base list of OA journals using two large-scale public datasets. The first source was ROAD,¹²⁸ which includes 63,892 OA journals indexed by the ISSN International Centre. From this source, we collected key bibliographic and geographic attributes such as ISSN, title, publisher, country, and continent, along with publication start and end dates.

The second major source was OpenAlex,¹²⁹ from which we retrieved 43,570 journal records from the three continents. This dataset provided standardized identifiers, OA status, and publisher information that complemented ROAD's metadata. Combining these two sources of data allowed us to establish a broad and structured foundation for further filtering and validation.

Removing APC-based Journals

The primary aim was to only analyse Diamond OA journals (those that are free for both readers and authors), so we then identified and excluded journals that have metadata records indicating that they charge Article Processing Charges (APCs). To achieve this, we cross-referenced the combined dataset with three complementary sources:

- OpenAPC,¹³⁰ which records journals known to charge APCs.
- DOAJ,¹³¹ which provides metadata on both APC- and non-APC-based OA journals.
- OpenAlex API,¹³² which includes information on the APC status/amount when available.

This multi-source cross-checking process leveraged openly available metadata in order to remove as many APC journals as possible from the ALMASI Diamond OA journal list.

Integrating Diamond OA Sources

We incorporated and cross-validated several trusted Diamond OA datasets identified from the literature and shared by project partners to improve the accuracy of the dataset and represent regional diversity in Diamond OA publishing. The following datasets and national portals contents were included, among others:

- OA Diamond Journals Study datasets by [Bosman, Frantsvåg, & Kramer \(2021\)](#) and [Kramer, & Bosman \(2021\)](#), which provide the most comprehensive early mapping of Diamond OA journals globally.
- IPSP Dataset ([Agnoloni, Bosman, Frantsvåg, et al., 2023](#)), which expands on the OA Diamond study by integrating institutional and policy perspectives from the DIAMAS project.
- PKP dataset ([Khanna, Raoni, Smecher, et al., 2024](#)), which documents journals using the Open Journal Systems (OJS) platform, an essential infrastructure for Diamond OA publishing.
- Regional and national Diamond OA lists:
 - Latin American portals such as AmeliCA and Redalyc

¹²⁸ <https://road.issn.org/>

¹²⁹ <https://openalex.org/sources>

¹³⁰ <https://www.openapc.net/>

¹³¹ <https://doaj.org/csv>

¹³² <https://openalex.org/>

- African national and regional portals such as African Journals Online (AJOL), ASJP (Algeria), and IMIST (Morocco)
- European national portals such as JUF0 portal (Finland),¹³³ the Dutch curated list ([Livio, & Kramer, 2025](#)), DergiPark (Turkey)¹³⁴

These datasets were used both for validation and enrichment to identify journals potentially missing from ROAD or OpenAlex and to confirm the Diamond OA status of ambiguous cases.

In addition to integrating these recognized datasets, a manual quality assurance check was conducted for a small number of individual countries. This was necessary to address data inconsistencies and metadata limitations. This targeted review focused on specific countries, such as Egypt, Nigeria and South Africa. The manual validation involved removing journals confirmed to be non-Diamond OA, as well as correcting for duplications and discontinued journals identified during the review. A key methodological principle was established for this process: where explicit information on publication fees was missing or not mentioned, the journal was assumed to be Diamond OA and retained in the dataset.

Building the Curated Diamond OA Journal List

Finally, all sources were merged and harmonized to construct a curated, de-duplicated list of Diamond OA journals. Each journal was required to meet three strict inclusion criteria:

- The journal is open access, according to ROAD or OpenAlex.
- The journal does not have information about charging APCs, confirmed through OpenAPC, DOAJ, or OpenAlex metadata.
- The journal appears in at least one recognized Diamond OA dataset, or has been validated through regional portals or partner contributions.

Following the harmonization process, the final dataset comprised 20,355 Diamond OA journals across Africa, Europe, and Latin America. Journals without a valid or verifiable ISSN could not be reliably matched across sources and were therefore excluded from the consolidated dataset. The dataset is openly available and available on Zenodo (Taskin & Laakso 2025).

The resulting dataset, covering Africa, Europe, and Latin America, serves as the foundation for further analyses and potential extension in the ALMASI project. It represents one of the most comprehensive cross-continental efforts to map the structure of Diamond OA publishing ecosystems, with all journal-level data openly stored in the project's shared repository for subsequent comparative studies.

Collecting Other Metadata Elements and Standardization

To enhance the analytical scope of the dataset, several additional metadata dimensions were collected and standardized. These include publisher information, language of publication, database coverage, and preservation service coverage. Each of these elements provides a

¹³³ <https://jfp.csc.fi/jufoportaal>

¹³⁴ <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/>

complementary perspective on the sustainability, visibility, and infrastructural robustness of Diamond OA journals.

Publisher identification and classification: Publisher information was primarily obtained through the CrossRef API, which allows reliable ISSN-based metadata retrieval at scale. Each journal's ISSN was matched with CrossRef records to extract publisher names. For cases where CrossRef data were unavailable or incomplete, supplementary metadata were sourced from ULRICHSWEB and DOAJ. This multi-source approach ensured comprehensive coverage and reduced the risk of missing or outdated publisher data.

After collecting publisher names, we standardized and classified them according to the taxonomy established by [Taşkın, Pölänen, Kulczycki, et al. \(2025\)](#). This method, also applied in previous studies of nonprofit and national publishing ecosystems, categorizes publishers into four groups based on naming conventions, organizational descriptors, and external list cross-checks.

- **Publishing houses:** Organisations dedicated to running publishing operations. Entities whose names contain identifiers such as Inc., Ltd., or Press, or that appear on recognized lists of commercial publishing organizations.
- **Society publishers:** Journals maintained by associations, foundations, or learned societies, including multilingual variations of such terms (e.g., Gesellschaft, asociación).
- **University publishers:** Journals issued by universities, research institutes, or academies of sciences, including multilingual variations of such terms (e.g., Üniversitesi, szkoła).
- **Governmental organizations:** Journals managed or sponsored by governmental bodies, ministries, or national agencies.
- **Unknown:** Publishers with missing, ambiguous, or unverifiable information were categorized as "unknown."

This classification ensures comparability with prior bibliometric studies while providing a more nuanced representation of the actors sustaining Diamond OA publishing ecosystems.

Language metadata: To assess linguistic diversity, language information was compiled from ROAD, DOAJ, OpenAlex, and ULRICHSWEB. The resulting data were used to visualize the linguistic distribution of Diamond OA journals across continents. For comparability, languages were standardized into three broad categories:

- **English** – journals publishing exclusively in English;
- **Multilingual** – journals publishing in English and at least one additional language;
- **Other languages** – journals publishing exclusively in non-English languages.

Database coverage and indexing comparisons: Database coverage was analyzed to evaluate the visibility and discoverability of Diamond OA journals. ISSN-based matching was conducted across the Master Journal List (covering all Web of Science indexes), Scopus, OpenAlex, and ULRICHSWEB.

Preservation service coverage: To analyze long-term preservation practices, metadata were collected based on three key publicly available mechanisms identified in the findings.

- The first source was The Keepers Registry,¹³⁵ maintained by the ISSN International Centre. This registry documents participation in trusted digital preservation networks (such as CLOCKSS, LOCKSS, Scholars Portal, national libraries, HathiTrust, and Persée, among others).
- The second source analyzed was Portico,¹³⁶ a major independent preservation service for electronic journals.
- The third source was the PKP Preservation Network (PKP PN),¹³⁷ which provides preservation services specifically for journals using the Open Journal Systems (OJS) platform.

Geographical Distribution of Diamond OA Journals Across Regions

The compiled dataset includes 20,355 Diamond Open Access journals across three regions: Europe, Latin America, and Africa. The geographical distribution of these journals reflects both regional publication dynamics and the availability of open data sources. It should be noted that representation is uneven across countries, as some have national or project-based lists (for example, from the DIAMAS project or regional repositories), while others lack comprehensive records.

Europe

Europe accounts for a substantial share of journals in the dataset, with 13,202 titles. Countries such as Turkey (2,288), Spain (1,704) the United Kingdom (1,302), Poland (1,295), Germany (727), and France (638) stand out as major contributors (See Figure 13).

¹³⁵ <https://keepers.issn.org/>

¹³⁶ <https://www.portico.org/>

¹³⁷ <https://pkp.sfu.ca/pkp-pn/>

ALMASI European journals in the dataset

Figure 14 – European journals in the dataset

This strong representation is partly a result of the DIAMAS project’s outputs, which provided harmonized and validated lists through sources like the IPSP dataset and JUFO portal. The availability of national indexes (for instance, Livio & Kramer’s Dutch curated list, DergiPark) also improved coverage across the continent. Overall, Europe’s profile indicates a well-documented nonprofit publishing ecosystem.

Africa

The African segment includes 1,332 Diamond OA journals, with a high concentration in a few countries. Algeria (759), Morocco (157), South Africa (89) and Egypt (87) account for most of the region’s output (see Figure 14).

African journals in the dataset

Figure 15 – African journals in the dataset

AJOL is a key infrastructure for the discoverability of African Diamond OA, which was also a key data source used for mapping journals around the country covered by the platform. Particularly notable is also the SciELO South Africa platform, which provides good international visibility for journals included on the platform. Two national portals, ASJP (Algeria) and IMIST (Morocco) platforms contributed large, well-documented journal lists to the dataset which provided better coverage for activities in these countries specifically. Conversely, several countries remain underrepresented because of limited coverage of their journals in digital indexing infrastructures or incomplete metadata in international sources, so our picture of the African region may be somewhat limited.

Latin America

Latin America represents a vibrant region in the Diamond OA landscape, with 5,821 journals identified in total (see Figure 15). In our dataset, Brazil (2,653) dominates the region, followed by Colombia (759), Argentina (554), Mexico (414), and Chile (304).

Latin American journals in the dataset

Figure 16 – Latin American journals in the dataset

It is commonly known that the regional publishing ecosystem benefits from well-established infrastructures such as SciELO, RedALyC, and Latindex, as well as national OA policies that strongly support Diamond models.

Indexing Coverage and Visibility

The comparative analysis of database coverage reveals significant regional disparities in the visibility of Diamond OA journals when seen through the lens of international indexing services (see Figure 16). Latin American journals show the highest overall indexing rates, with 71.4% present in OpenAlex, 53.6% in ULRICHSWEB, and 43.5% in DOAJ. These figures reflect the region’s long-standing investment in cooperative infrastructures such as SciELO, RedALyC, and Latindex, which have consistently contributed structured metadata and ensured wide discoverability.

Indexing status of Diamond OA journals

Figure 17 – Indexing coverage and visibility of Diamond OA journals

European journals follow, with 68.8% indexed in OpenAlex and 56.7% in ULRICHSWEB. Around 26.9% of European Diamond OA journals appear in Scopus, and smaller proportions are indexed in the Web of Science family: 12.8% in ESCI, 2.9% in AHCI, 2.0% in SCIE, and 1.9% in SSCI. This pattern illustrates that Europe's inclusion across databases is driven by national infrastructures such as JUFO, Publikationsforum, DergiPark, and specific policy initiatives like DIAMAS, which encourage standardized metadata and interoperability across platforms.

In contrast, African journals display substantially lower coverage across all international indexing systems, with 32.4% present in OpenAlex, 19.6% in ULRICHSWEB, and 15.7% in DOAJ. Representation drops sharply in Scopus (8.3%) and Web of Science indexes, with 3.8% in ESCI and below 1% in AHCI, SCIE, and SSCI. Regional platforms such as AJOL, ASJP, and IMIST continue to expand visibility within African scholarly ecosystems and offer potential pathways for integration into global indexes.

The cross-continental comparison of DOAJ, OpenAlex, and ULRICHSWEB coverage further suggests structural imbalances in the visibility of Diamond OA journals. As shown in the Venn diagrams in Figure 17, European journals exhibit the most extensive overlap across all three indexes, which may reflect a more consistent integration of metadata and indexation pathways. In contrast, Latin American journals, although numerous, are concentrated within OpenAlex and DOAJ, potentially indicating a strong presence of regionally coordinated open access initiatives but limited linkage to traditional directories. African journals display the smallest intersection despite the growing influence of regional platforms such as AJOL and ASJP.

ALMASI Overlap of Journal Indexing Across Continents (DOAJ, OpenAlex, and Ulrich)

Figure 18 – Overlap of journal indexing across continents (DOAJ, OpenAlex, and Ulrich)

Publisher Types

The analysis of publisher types reveals distinct structural patterns across regions, reflecting the organizational foundations of Diamond OA publishing ecosystems (see Figure 18).

ALMASI Publisher types

Figure 19 – Publisher types of Diamond OA journals

In Latin America, the publishing landscape remains predominantly institutional, with 4,366 journals (77%) issued by research institutions. This reflects the region's strong university-led, publicly funded open access tradition. Scholarly societies contribute a smaller but visible share (603 journals, 11%), followed by publishing houses (206 journals, 4%) and governmental bodies (113 journals, 2%). The integrated infrastructures of SciELO, RedALyC, and Latindex continue to sustain this university-centered model.

In Europe, research institutions also dominate (7,367 journals, 56%), yet the continent exhibits greater diversity in publisher types. Learned societies account for 1,346 journals (15%), while professional and governmental publishers contribute 2,022 (16%) and 351 (4%), respectively. This plural structure reflects policy-driven support for bibliodiversity through initiatives such as DIAMAS, which fosters coexistence between university, society, and platform-based publishing models.

In Africa, research institutions again form the core of the identified Diamond OA ecosystem (230 journals, 17%), with societies (49 journals, 3%) and professional or governmental publishers (48 and 19 journals) representing smaller segments. Notably, 986 journals have no identifiable publisher type, pointing to persistent metadata limitations and informal publishing structures. Many such journals are likely hosted by universities or small editorial teams operating outside formal registration systems.

Publication Languages

The linguistic distribution of Diamond Open Access journals illustrates substantial regional variation across Latin America, Europe, and Africa (Figure 19). The data shows that European journals display the largest volume overall, while Latin American and African titles reveal different balances between English, multilingual, and other-language publishing.

Across all three regions, English-only journals form a minority segment. In Latin America, 1,150 titles are published exclusively in English, 2,882 in Europe, and 138 in Africa. The predominance of languages other than English and multilingual publishing is a defining feature of the Diamond OA ecosystem.

Multilingual journals, those published in English and at least one additional language, represent the largest group in every region, reflecting strong traditions of linguistic inclusivity and regional accessibility. Journals publishing exclusively in other languages (neither English nor multilingual) also remain substantial: 2,266 in Latin America, 4,626 in Europe, and 207 in Africa. This category covers publications in national and regional languages such as Spanish, Portuguese, French, and Swahili, depending on the local context.

Finally, a smaller but notable share of journals have unknown language information in the metadata, 761 in Latin America, 1,609 in Europe, and 559 in Africa, indicating persistent gaps in standardized language reporting.

Publication languages

Figure 20 – Publication languages of Diamond OA journals

Preservation Services

Preservation practices vary considerably across regions, and differences in infrastructure and participation in long-term digital archiving networks are also apparent (Figure 20). The following analysis is based on data collected from three key publicly available preservation mechanisms: the Keepers Registry, Portico, and PKP Preservation Network.

ALMASI

Preservation services

Figure 21 – Preservation practices of Diamond OA journals

Utilization of Keepers Registry, which tracks inclusion in trusted archives such as CLOCKSS, LOCKSS, and national libraries, remains limited overall. Only 5% of African journals are listed in the registry, compared to 14.1% in Europe and 34.1% in Latin America. The relatively high proportion in Latin America reflects strong engagement with cooperative preservation initiatives, particularly through regionally supported platforms and repositories.

A similar pattern appears for Portico, a major preservation service for electronic journals. Coverage is again lowest in Africa (4.1%), followed by 12.8% in Europe and 11.1% in Latin America. Although Europe and Latin America perform somewhat better, these figures indicate that the use of Portico remains below global averages for OA journals, likely due to its subscription-based model.

By contrast, the PKP-OJS Preservation Network (PKP PN) demonstrates much broader adoption among Diamond OA journals. It covers 27.3% of African journals, 41.8% of European, and 48.7% of Latin American titles. Overall, these findings suggest that community-based preservation infrastructures, such as PKP PN, which leverage the widespread use of the OJS platform, play a critical role in ensuring the long-term accessibility of Diamond OA journals, particularly where participation in commercial or centralized services remains limited.

Discussion

This bibliometric analysis has provided a mapping of the Diamond OA publishing ecosystems across Europe, Africa, and Latin America with the bibliometric data that is available about them today, revealing distinct structural differences between these regions. The findings clearly illustrate three different regional profiles:

- Latin America demonstrates a strong, institutionalized model, predominantly led by research institutions (77%) and supported by well-established, cooperative infrastructures such as SciELO and RedALyC. This region also shows some of the highest overall indexing and visibility rates.
- Europe exhibits a more "pluralistic" structure. While research institutions are dominant (56%), learned societies (15%) and publishing houses (16%) also play significant roles. The ecosystem is "well-documented", supported by policy initiatives like DIAMAS and national infrastructures such as DergiPark.
- Similarly for Africa where a publisher type was identifiable, research institutions are leading in Diamond OA publishing (17%), followed by learned societies (3.7%) and publishing houses (3.6%). However, there is a high proportion of "Unknown" publisher types (74%), suggesting that the current data provides a "somewhat limited" picture of the full ecosystem.

Beyond regional disparities, this analysis highlights two fundamental, cross-continental characteristics of the Diamond OA ecosystem. First, it is not "English-centric"; English-only journals are a minority segment, and publishing in multilingual and other national/regional languages is a defining feature of the ecosystem.

Second, and most critically, the ecosystem relies heavily on publicly supported, national, or community-based infrastructures for both journal hosting (e.g., DergiPark, ASJP, SciELO) and preservation (especially the PKP PN). The pivotal role played by these platforms underscores the critical need for their continued maintenance and sustainability if the Diamond OA ecosystem is to thrive and survive going forward.

5. Summary

This deliverable has outlined the scope for the project and formulated definitions and concepts that will help reach a common understanding of Diamond OA publishing activities around the world. The deliverable also collected together existing information about Diamond OA as it exists in the three regions central to the ALMASI project, work which also included a substantial bibliometric analysis component that aggregated information about journals from a wide range of sources.

This work has not been aimed to be comparative in nature despite its use of common concepts, a common general template for structuring collected evidence, and per country/region breakdowns of bibliometric results. The goal has from the start been one of mutual understanding and learning from each other across diverse environments. As such the summarising statements focus on providing general status and observations per-region rather than attempting to draw comparisons when the landscapes and evidence about them differs to such a high degree.

For the African region, Diamond OA publishing is driven by committed editorial teams and Boards, often as a volunteer effort with some institutional funding and in-kind support, as well as support from shared national and African platforms and communities of practice. It is a bottom-up practice, not largely supported with top-down policies and funding yet, hence there are sustainability challenges. Diamond OA publishing in Africa embodies openness and inclusion, strengthens equitable access to knowledge and reduces knowledge gaps and epistemic injustice.

Diamond Open Access in Latin America and the Caribbean is generally characterized as the result of a long-standing regional commitment to knowledge as a public good. The model has developed over several decades through the sustained efforts of universities, research networks, and public institutions, rather than commercial stakeholders. As a consequence, the region has established an ecosystem in which journals operate without charging authors or readers, aligning scholarly communication with principles of public responsibility and academic collaboration.

The scope of this model is extensive. It includes thousands of journals across a wide range of disciplines and languages, with a strong emphasis on research that reflects local and regional priorities. Non-profit infrastructures such as Redalyc, Latindex, Scielo, AmeliCA or LaReferencia play a central role in providing quality assurance, indexing, interoperability, and long-term preservation. These systems function without relying on article-processing charges, thereby reducing barriers for both authors and readers and supporting equitable participation in scholarly communication.

Overall, the Latin American and Caribbean approach to Diamond Open Access is frequently cited as evidence that a large-scale, non-commercial, and equitable publishing system is viable. Its sustainability depends on continued investment in open, community-governed infrastructures, yet it demonstrates that scholarly communication can operate effectively outside commercial

models. The regional experience provides a reference point for discussions about more inclusive and sustainable approaches to open access globally.

For the European region one particular characteristic for Diamond OA is the emphasis on national-level organisation where there are platforms or potential services offered, with e.g. international efforts only now being seriously started through activities of the EDCH. For Diamond OA in Europe institutional publishing is a strong presence with universities and learned societies having a very large footprint in the landscape. Diamond OA for books is something that has not yet come very far anywhere in the world, but Europe is a region where the leading infrastructure providers are located and there is currently a lot of experimentation with various collaborative funding models where universities and publishers are interested in contributing to them. A lot of effort that goes into European Diamond OA journals is volunteer or in-kind, which is something that over time should potentially be strengthened to make publishing more sustainable and also capable of growing if there is to be a shift towards increased publishing volume in specifically Diamond OA outlets.

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